

**DESIGN OF NEW QUARANTINE HOSPITAL FOR
INFECTIOUS DISEASES (IDH) IN KOTIKAWATTA,
MULLERIYAWA, SRI LANKA.**

**A Project Report Submitted to the Department of Construction Technology of University
of Vocational Technology, Sri Lanka**

in partial fulfilment of the requirements of the

Bachelor of Technology in Construction Technology and Resource Management

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DECLARATION

We certify that this project report does not incorporate without acknowledgement, any material previously submitted for a degree or diploma in any university, and to the best of my knowledge and belief it does not contain any material previously published or written by another person, except where due reference is made in the text.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

IDH – Infectious Diseases Hospital
RDA - Road Development Authority
MT - Metric Ton
SWOT – Strength, weaknesses, opportunities and threats
EIA - Environmental Impact Assessment
IEE - Initial Environmental Examination
CEA - Central Environmental Authority
N - Newton
MM - Milli Meters
BIQ - Basic Information Questionnaire
UDA - Urban Development Authority
TIA – Traffic Impact Assessment
H - Hour
R/F - Reinforced
KN - Kilo Newton
CEA - Central Environmental Authority
PPC - Preliminary Planning Clearance
COC - Certificate of Conformity
NEA - National Environmental Authority
Min – Minimum
GDP – Gross Domestic Product
ICU – Intensive Care Unit
RCC - Reinforced Cement Concrete
BS – British Standards
BS EN – British Standard European Norm
ASHRAE - American Society of Heating, Refrigerating and Air-Conditioning Engineer
c/c- Center to Center
EMP - Environment Management Plan
HVAC - Heat, Ventilation & Air Condition
LED - Light Emitting Diode
Lm- Lumen

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

COVID-19 diseases spread speedily worldwide in a very short period which resulted in millions of deaths worldwide. Sri Lanka is also struggled in order to get over this fatal pandemic and the local economy and social lifestyle have been faced to a tough time. Medication of infectious diseases should stay on stricter requirements than normal medical institution standards for medical environment and protective measures of treatment and prevention. In order to prevent further cross-infection between patients and medical staff and to reduce the risks of disease epidemic, the patients can only be taken care of in a specialized infectious diseases hospital. The pandemic can be contained and brought under full control with the rapid growth of medical technology and enhancements in public health management.

Quarantine Hospital for Infectious Diseases (IDH) in Kotikawatta, Mulleriyawa is a specifically architecturally planned hospital to treat infectious diseases, the land area is approximately 4.5 Acres Covid hospital complex, the main hospital building is 03 storied steel building. This is designed to facilitate 255 patients at a time.

This hospital is designed with the Green Concept for sustainable development. In this comprehensive report we explained the outline and the purpose of the project. This report describes a feasibility study and Alternative analysis, detailed design of this project. As some environmental problems may arise as a result of this project, it is very important to carry out an Initial Environmental Examination (IEE). On the other hand, a Traffic Impact Assessment (TIA) is required to visualize the traffic impact on the environment due to this project. Therefore, a detailed IEE and a detailed TIA were included in this report. This building design complies with the UDA building regulations and the architectural design was carried out to minimize spread of infectious diseases. All the necessary building services were designed.

All the design parts were created in accordance with Euro code (Super structure) and BS code (Sub structure) guidelines. Structural design calculations were done both manual and software methods to implement the design project. The computer analysis for the building was done by using STAAD.Pro software.

CHAPTER 1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to The Project

Infectious diseases are caused by pathogenic microorganisms which can be dispersed, directly or indirectly, from one person to another. The lung infectious disease has the highest infection rate among various types of infectious diseases, which stands the maximum danger to population health condition. There were deadly pandemics which accounts for millions of deaths in the world history, for instance Black death pandemic responsible for the death of one third of the world population in 1346-1353 and Spanish Flu pandemic infected one third of the world population and responsible for 50 million deaths in 1918-1920 (Networks, 2020).

COVID-19 diseases spread speedily worldwide in a very short period. On 11th March 2020 World health organization categorized COVID -19 as a pandemic after identifying the so-called virus in December 2019 in China (Zhi, 2020). COVID-19 is a global ongoing pandemic which resulted in millions of deaths. Sri Lanka is also struggling in order to get over this fatal pandemic and the local economy and social lifestyle have been faced to a tough time due to this epidemic where COVID-19 confirmed cases, Active cases and deaths are increasing rapidly island-wide.

Medication of infectious diseases should stay on stricter requirements than normal medical institution standards for medical environment and protective measures of treatment and prevention. In order to prevent further cross-infection between patients and medical staff and to reduce the risks of disease epidemic, the patients can only be taken care of in a specialized infectious diseases hospital. The pandemic can be contained and brought under full control with the rapid growth of medical technology and enhancements in public health management.

Most of the developed countries in world-wide have been affected a lot by this disease. As a developing country Sri Lanka is facing a mortal situation, mainly due to lack of hospital infrastructure facilities to face an unexpected pandemic situation like this. Resulting in insufficient medical resources and supplies, which lead to the proposal on the Construction of Emergency Hospitals.

1.2 Scope

In general, local health sector has been structured for a limited number of patients. However, Sri Lanka was not ready for this kind of pandemic situation in all social, economic and infrastructural aspects. Active cases surpassing the capacity of Hospitals. Moreover, these figures have arrived according to the testing capacity available in Sri Lanka as on date. If government could perform tests for all suspects on urgent basis, these figures could have reached higher.

On the other hand, all the COVID-19 patients are being treated amongst the other general patients, therefore all of them are exposed to the danger of infecting the disease. The medical staff is also facing a huge hazard due to lack of infrastructure and practice to this kind of pandemic situation.

Therefore, rapid construction of specialized hospitals for infectious diseases is essential, in order to overcome in this situation now and also in the future. Consequently, the decision of designing for a Quarantine Hospital for Infectious Diseases has been realized by the MOH, Sri Lanka and the project design will be performed by CECB as the consultant.

- Location: Kotikawatta, Mulleriyawa – 4.5 Acres of idle land belongs to existing IDH Hospital Kotikawatta, Mulleriyawa
- Coordinates: Latitude: 6.92°, Longitude: 79.92°

Figure 1-1 - Satellite views and details of proposed Land

Figure 1-2 - Detailed Views of the Proposed Project Land

Figure 1-3 – Selected land area for the proposed project

1.3 Objectives

1.3.1 Main Objective

To design a specialized hospital specifically addressing infectious diseases to cater the insufficient hospital capacity & facility in order to overcome the current COVID – 19 pandemic situations.

1.3.2 Specific Objectives

- To identify the main special features, include in an infectious diseases hospital in order to provide safe working environment for medical staff.
- To conduct Feasibility study for three design alternatives based on Technical, Environmental, Economic and Social parameters.
- To provide Environmental impact assessment or Initial Environmental Evaluation & Traffic Impact Assessment Report based on Project.
- To develop architectural, structural and Building Services designs with incorporating green building concept.
- To estimate the cost of the project.

1.4 Significance

Providing specialized infrastructure to treat infected patients can encourage the medical staff by creating them a safe working environment and by maximizing the rate of healing it is possible to overcome the current situation of the country in health, social and economic aspects. And it is very important to make the health sector ready for the unexpected pandemic situations in future.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

The novel coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2) is a newly emerging pathogen, and has the characteristics of strong infectivity and fast propagation. The transmission of SARS-CoV-2 occurs through droplets and can happen through close personal contact with infected persons without effective containment measures. The 2019 coronavirus disease (COVID-19) is an example, and China and other countries have identified and reported a large number of such cases. Facing the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic, with such high patient numbers overwhelming the admission capacities of infectious diseases hospitals, Zall Foundation proposed the construction of COVID-19 Emergency Hospitals in order to effectively respond to the surging number of COVID-19 cases. Emergency hospitals involve the conversion of existing hospitals that currently do not have, or have insufficient admission capacities for infectious disease patients, into emergency hospitals that focus solely on receiving COVID-19 cases. COVID-19 Emergency Hospitals have played an important role in China's epidemic prevention and control by efficiently easing the problems of insufficient ward beds and inadequate admission capacities of infectious diseases hospitals. Zall foundation propose the importance of dividing the space in to zones such as contaminated zones, Decontaminated zones, and transition zones in between contaminated and decontaminated zones to prevent viral transmission, which was successful in china. (Zhi, 2020)

Wuhan Leishenshan ("Leishenshan" for short) hospital is a makeshift emergency hospital for treating patients diagnosed with the novel coronavirus-infected pneumonia (NCIP). Engineering construction uses modular composite building finished products to the greatest extent, which reduces the workload of field operations and saves a lot of time. The building information model (BIM) technology assists in design and construction work to meet rapid construction requirements. Besides, based on the unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) data analysis and application platform, digitization and intelligence in engineering construction are improved. Simultaneously, on-site construction and overall hoisting were carried out to achieve maximum efficiency. Construction of Leishenshan Hospital as an example to illustrate how to adopt BIM technology and other high-tech technology such as big data, artificial intelligence, drones, and 5G for the fast construction of the fabricated steel structure systems in emergency engineering projects.

The entire Leishenshan Hospital adopts a “Three zones and two channels “structure. The three zones refer to clean, semi-contaminated and contaminated areas, and the two channels refer to the patient channel and the medical care channel. The ward nursing unit is a light combined modular building, and the medical technology area is a steel frame and light wall panel building combined structure. The plan is a “fishbone” layout, and each “fishbone” is an independent medical unit. The ward is divided into north and south areas, each with 15 wards, and the ward spacing is 12 m. Multiple H- shaped modules arrange the wards. Among them, the office area and medical staff passage are placed along the central axis. Each central module is responsible for four. There are two rows of wards in the nursing unit—patients from the ward outside the ward. Medical staff enters the ward through the “sanitary passage unit” from the central axis’s core through disinfection, dressing, and inspection.

The structural design of emergency hospitals must ensure safety and be completed in a short time. Therefore, modular containers are used to assemble medical units. For the ICU and medical, the technical department with special requirements, light steel structure, and steel composite panels are used for assembly.

Container-type prefabricated unit for the isolation ward (Provided by China Construction Third Engineering Bureau Co., Ltd.). Different from the isolation ward, the medical technology facility of the Leishenshan Hospital adopted steel structure since a container-type prefabricated unit was infeasible for this building, especially for the intensive care unit (ICU) and test room. First, the building needed a large-span without structural barriers to provide more space for medical treatment. Second, the room height of the ICU and test room had to exceed 4.2 m. (Chena, 2021)

Though the cost comparison reveals that steel-concrete composite design structure is more costly, reduction in direct cost of steel-composite structure resulting from speedy erection will make steel-composite structure economically viable. Further, under earthquake consideration because of the inherent ductility characteristics, steel-concrete structure will perform than conventional R.C.C. structure. (Renavikar Aniket V.1, July 2016)

According to UDA regulations (Part I, Schedule VII of Extraordinary Gazette No. 1597/8 – 2009) type of building can be categorized based on the use of building.

- Residential - Including Houses, Multiple Dwellings, Apartments, Home for Elders
- Commercial - Including Office Building, Hotels, Motels, Guest House, Public Lodging, Shopping Centers, Supermarkets, Restaurants, Car Parks
- Industrial - Including Factories, Workshops, Warehouse, Industrial Establishments, Infrastructure Services Center
- Institutional - Government Buildings, Semi-Government Buildings and Other Public Buildings

As the hospital falls on the category of Institutional building and has to follow rules and regulations under that category. And there is another category according to height and use of building. (UDA, 2009)

- Category A (High Rise) - G + 4 & above
- Category B (Low Rise) – Less than G + 3
- Category C (Low Rise) – Less than G + 2
 - Residential
 - Non residential

Nowadays, the software techniques were highly involved in a construction field for quick and better accuracy of an analysis report to execute the given project successfully. The most prominent using software for design and analysis of the respective buildings by STAAD.PRO software for accuracy and safety regards. A hospital building was designed and analyzed for G+3 storied structure by STAAD.PRO V8i software has been used for designing and analysis purposes mainly for the result of shear force and maximum bending moment without any complexity. (kumar, April-2017)

CHAPTER 3 METHODOLOGY

First three Layout Designs were prepared and took those as three alternatives mainly based of the shape of the building and feasibility studies were conducted (Social and Health, Technical, Financial, Environmental) about the project. Then evaluate three design alternatives and choose the appropriate design. Then prepare the architectural drawings and design the structural elements and services to the selected design. Using STADD.PRO software analyzes the design model and execute the calculations manually of the structural elements. Then prepared the BOQ. Adapt green rating system in Sri Lanka by GBCSL to implement the project design. At last finalized the project details and prepare the report.

Figure 3-1 - Methodology of Project

CHAPTER 4

PROJECT IMPLEMENTATION

4.1 Feasibility Study and Alternative Analysis

MOH as the client, is expecting to build an IDH in a rapid process to overcome the current emergency situation and for unexpected scenarios like Covid 19 in future and they are also expecting a safe working environment for medical staff by well-planned architectural design to serve around 150 patients in a very safe environment.

To evaluate the feasibility of the proposed IDH on the land selected by the client, several layout designs with different main hospital building shapes were considered and analyzed to choose the best Alternative. The best Alternative is selected by comparing scenarios for the following feasibilities. Out of these, Social and Health Feasibility is the most crucial.

- Social and Health Feasibility
- Technical Feasibility
- Financial Feasibility
- Environmental Feasibility

Following design Alternatives are compared together to select the optimum building arrangement for the land.

- ❖ Alternative 1 – Main Hospital building is cross shaped and three storied. Hospital premises is divided into two zones, i.e. Patient Admission Zone and Staff Zone.
(Annexure 01)
- ❖ Alternative 2 – Main Hospital building is “H” shaped and three storied. Hospital premises is divided into four zones, i.e. Patient Admission Zone, Medical Staff Zone, Supply and Services Zone and Waste Management Zone.
(Annexure 02)
- ❖ Alternative 3 – Main Hospital building is irregular shaped and three storied. Hospital premises is not divided into zones clearly. (Annexure 03)

	<u>Alternative 01</u>	<u>Alternative 02</u>	<u>Alternative 03</u>
<u>Floor Area</u>			
Total Floor Area of a Floor of Main Building (sqm)	3,200	2,000	2,400
Total Floor Area of Three Floors of Main Building (sqm)	9,600	6,000	7,200
<u>Bed Allocation</u>			
Normal beds in observation ward	200	–	80
Ventilator beds in critical wards	200	240	200
ICU beds	10	15	10
Total beds	410	255	290

Table 4-1 – Alternative design floor areas and bed allocation

4.2 Social & Health Feasibility

The impact that the proposed project can have on the social system in the project environment is considered in social feasibility. According to the Field Reconnaissance Survey and the Zoning Map of Kotikawatta Mulleriyawa Pradeshiya Sabha area, proposed project is within the administrative and institutional zone, where the existing IDH Hospital and Angoda Mental Hospital are dominating the area of the so-called zone. The surrounding area is mainly residential, and the density of buildings is low on the other side to the Mandavila Road in front of the proposed project. Furthermore, there are residential areas with high density of population and buildings. B231 Road – Kolonnawa-Angoda, is the main access road to the proposed hospital. So, it is really significant to take measures to protect social and health conditions of the surrounding environment. According to the following Decision Matrix Analysis, Alternative 2 (“H” Shaped Hospital Building) was selected as the best option.

Criteria	Weighting	Options					
		Alternative 01		Alternative 02		Alternative 03	
		Score	Total	Score	Total	Score	Total
Patient admission procedure	1	3	3	5	5	3	3
Utilization of beds in wards and ICU	1	3	3	4	4	3	3
Attempts to protect medical staff with architectural separations	2	4	8	5	10	4	8
Minimize impact to residential areas	1	3	3	5	5	3	3
Minimum impact on traffic	1	3	3	5	5	3	3
Internal parking and roadway arrangement	1	4	4	5	5	3	3
Attention on differently abled people	1	4	4	4	4	4	4
Equity for gender discrimination	1	4	4	4	4	4	4
Total			32		42		31
Rank			2		1		3

Score	1	2	3	4	5
Definition	Very Poor	Poor	Not Bad	Good	Very Good

Table 4-2 - Social & Health Feasibility Analysis Matrix

When considering the admission criteria in Alternative 01 and 03, this has designed considering that any patient can come and if tested positive only, patients can be admitted themselves in to acute care wards or short stay wards or critical case wards according to their criticality level. This admission criteria is the current admission state in Sri Lanka. These kinds of hospitals will generate more traffic and could affect the social life of the residential people and will be difficult to control architecturally control contaminated and decontaminated zones. In Alternative 02, the admission criteria have overcome that issue, by admitting only critical patients who need to be hospitalized. In Sri Lankan context, rapidly scaled laboratory testing, contact tracing and home quarantine by the public health sector and epidemiology unit is very strong, MOH Officers and Public Health Officers in every Grama Niladhari Division, continuous testing programs island wide, Transportation of suspected patient is arranged through “1990 On-call Ambulance (Suwaseriya) Service” to the hospitals and home quarantined patients can contact to epidemiology units through 1390 Hotline. But still Sri Lanka is lacked of specially planned Hospitals for Covid 19 where at present medical staff and general patients are in a huge threat.

Currently, there are daily new cases around 1,000 where the hospital capacity could not cater for such capacity, so it is possible to identify patients who need to be hospitalized in the ground level public health sector and direct to this proposed IDH with a intercommunication database between epidemiology unit and IDH. This admission criteria will reserve this specialized hospital giving priority for the patients who definitely need a ventilator bed or ICU treatments, meanwhile reducing the traffic of roads to a great extent.

In all the Alternative designs, intermediate sanitization and disinfection zones to separate contaminated zones from decontaminated zones are used, but in Alternative 02 the use of transition zone is very effective.

In Alternative 01 layout plan, two major zones are identified; a contaminated zone of patients and a decontaminated zone of medical staff and in Alternative 02 there are 04 major zones, contaminated zone is further divided in to Patient Admission Zone and Waste Disposal Zone. Decontaminated zone can be further divided in to Medical Staff Zone and Supply & Services Zone using the advantage of the unique “H Shape” building 4 corners. There is no clear separation of zones in the layout plan of Alternative 03.

In Alternative 02 design Disabled toilets, Disabled Parking, Separate floor separation for females and labor room facilities are clearly defined.

According to the analysis Alternative 02 is the most feasible option in social and health criteria.

4.3 Technical Feasibility

Assessing the viability of a project in a technical perspective is of great significance, as it provides information about technical requirements of the project. Those requirements have to be compared with the technical capability of the company that undertakes the construction. This ensures that a project can be completed within the expected time period as all the technical requirements are fulfilled. Proper geotechnical investigation has to be carried out prior to the construction, in order to obtain information about the soil condition below the surface. The type of foundation is then decided, depending on the nature of soil condition. If the bearing capacity is lesser, either a raft foundation or a pile foundation is preferred over individual footing and combined footing foundations. Advanced technical methods have to be applied according to the available technical methods to meet the requirements. And also need to consider about the following factors too, i.e. availability of materials, services and construction applications, methods of transporting inputs and outputs to the project location.

As the MOH want a rapid construction, modular construction is the most preferred option. RCC structure needs more material consumption and currently, there is a risk of unavailability of materials and rising of prices which is a huge problem and comparatively construction process will be decelerated. Steel framed structure is the most preferred option with rapid construction and material availability considerations.

Figure 4-1-. The effect of steel framed structure building compared to RCC structure

According to the SWOT analysis, there are many positives and fewer negatives in the steel structure frame system. As the main consideration of this project is rapid construction, steel frame structure is the best option. Although the initial cost is a bit high, steel frame structure is economical as rapid construction gives quicker benefits and has a scrap value.

According to the following Decision Matrix Analysis, Alternative 2 (“H” Shaped Hospital Building) was selected as the best option.

Criteria	Weighting	Options					
		Alternative 01		Alternative 02		Alternative 03	
		Score	Total	Score	Total	Score	Total
Ventilation	2	3	6	4	8	3	6
Structural stability of the building shape	2	4	8	4	8	3	6
Separation of zones	2	3	6	5	10	4	8
Optimal use of site (Land use & planning)	2	4	8	5	10	4	8
Uniqueness and aesthetical appearance of shape	1	4	4	4	4	2	2
Total			32		40		30
Rank			2		1		3

Score	1	2	3	4	5
Definition	Very Poor	Poor	Not Bad	Good	Very Good

Table 4-3 - Technical Feasibility Analysis Matrix

Maximum distance between two opposite walls of Alternative 01, 02 and 03 is 18ft, 15ft and 20ft respectively. When considering the natural ventilation of the building, “H” Shaped building (Alternative 2) seems to be expedient due to its lesser span. And when considering structural stability of the shape of the building H shape and cross shape buildings provide more stability and safety for earthquakes and wind with the

symmetricity of the shape. Separation of zones is trouble-free, since the four corners of the H Shape can be used as four entrance corridors for separate different purposes. Further, it will be a more advantage for the proper planning of the site.

Moreover, the aerial view of the H Shaped hospital building can be viewed as a symbol for a Hospital, which will be aesthetically unique.

According to the analysis Alternative 02 is the most feasible option in technical criteria.

4.4 Financial Feasibility

As the client MOH is funding the project from government funds. Proposed IDH is adding to the public health care system of Sri Lanka to overcome the currant pandemic situation, to face future pandemic situations and to serve as a specialized hospital for infectious diseases. Government hospitals in Sri Lanka are of charity basis without direct incomes. But specialized and properly planed hospitals can contribute to the economic development of country indirectly. Expenditure on health is one of the world development indicators and increase the GDP of a country.

Social distancing and lockdowns can minimize widespread infection, prevent hospitals from being overwhelmed, and save thousands of lives. But those same measures will restrain schools, businesses, and factories, specially affect tourism industry and slow down the economy. So, by improving public health by specialized techniques can overcome the pandemic situation.

This is a public project so initial cost is a major concern. And by using discounting investment decision techniques checked the profitability only for the purpose of selecting a financially feasible alternative by considering reasonable assumptions.

Net present value method is used for the calculation process by considering the discount rate of 10%. Assumed the lifetime of the hospital as 40 years. Gave a assumed monetary value for the beds of the hospital considering prevailing private hospital chargers.

- normal bed in observation ward - 4,000 Rs/bed/day
- ventilator bed in critical wards - 12,000 Rs/bed/day
- ICU bed - 25,000 Rs/bed/day

Other assumptions are mentioned in the financial analysis calculation sheet (*Annexure 04 - Initial Cost & Discounting Investment Decision Calculation Sheet*).

	Project cost (Rs)	NPV (Rs)	IRR (%)
Alternative 01	1,072,163,400.00	1,396,852,781.23	12
Alternative 02	692,637,000.00	1,634,863,547.59	22
Alternative 03	819,145,800.00	1,305,671,879.61	15

Table 4-4 - Financial Analysis

According to the above analysis, Alternative 02 is the most financially feasible. Since, by satisfying the best Social and Health and Technical feasible design, it also the least expensive option and also with the highest NPV and IRR. By managing overall architectural space to satisfy health factors and also can treat more than 150 patients' capacity, as per the client requirement.

4.5 Environmental Feasibility

Criteria	<u>Alternative 01</u>	<u>Alternative 02</u>	<u>Alternative 03</u>
Total Floor Area of a Floor of Main Building (sqm)	3,200	2,000	2,400
Total Nr. Of beds	410	255	290
Approximate health care waste Generation (kg/ /day/bed) (Haniffa, 2004)	2.35	2.35	2.35
Approximate health care waste Generation of the hospital building (kg/day)	963.5	599.25	681.5

Table 4-5 - Environmental Feasibility Analysis

When considering a Covid 19 Hospital, health care waste generation is the most critical. According to the above analysis, Alternative 02 generates the least amount of health care waste.

All the alternatives are proposing rain water harvesting, solar panels and green covers as green building approach. The only critical thing to consider is health care waste generation.

In that point of view, Alternative 02 is the best environmentally feasible option.

When considering the structural aspects steel structures have a scrap value. Structural components can be reuse or recycle so steel structures can save natural resources.

4.5.1 Conclusion

Feasibility Studies	Rank		
	Alternative 01	Alternative 02	Alternative 03
Social & Health Feasibility	2	1	3
Technical Feasibility	2	1	3
Financial Feasibility	3	1	2
Environmental Feasibility	3	1	2

Table 4-6 - Conclusion of Feasibility Study

According to the overall feasibility study. Alternative 02 (H Shaped Building) is the best option.

4.6 Initial Environmental Examination (IEE)

4.6.1 General

Considering the general requirement of conducting an Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) or Initial Environment Examination (IEE). When development work has begun it is necessary to find out and measure the impact on the environment with respect to the regulations implemented by the government. So, project proponent needs to verify that the proposed project falls within the identified "Prescribed Project" list according to the Central Environmental Authority with referred to the Government Gazette No.772/22 of 24.03.1993, 859/14 of 23.02.1995, 1104/22 of 06.11.1999, and 1108/1 of 29.11.1999. So, a project that falls in this prescribed category needs to conduct an EIA/IEE from an approved agency. Following are some boundary conditions and the Act should consider for conducting an EIA.

Within 100 m from the boundaries of or within any area declared under -

- National Heritage Wilderness Act No. 3 of 1988; the Forest Ordinance (Chapter 451);
- wholly or partly within the Coastal Zone as defined in the Coast Conservation Act No. 57 of 1981.

Within the following areas whether or not the areas are wholly or partly within the Coastal Zone:

- Any erodible area declared under the Soil Conservation Act (Chapter 540)
- Any Flood Area declared under the Flood Protection Ordinance (Chapter 449) and any flood protection area declared under the Sri Lanka Land Reclamation and Development Corporation Act 15 of 1968 as amended by Act No. 52 of 1982.
- Any reservation beyond the full supply level of a reservoir
- Any archaeological reserve, the ancient or protected monument as defined or declared under the Antiquities Ordinance (Chapter 188).
- Any area declared under the botanic Gardens Ordinance (Chapter 446)
- Within 100 meters from the boundaries of or within any area declared as a Sanctuary under the Fauna and Flora Protection Ordinance (Chapter 469)

- Within 100 meters from the high flood level contour of or within a public lake as defined in the Crown Lands Ordinance (Chapter 454) including those declared under section 71 of the said Ordinance.

So according to the given guidelines given in Part I, Part II, Part III, of the act the proposed IDH project does not belong to any specified category, which means it does not necessary to conduct an EIA. Any way the proposed project is a high-rise development project so it is a must to conduct an Initial Environment Examination.

Project proponent requires to handover BIQ to Central Environment Authority for reviewing purposes about conducting EIA/IEE. (*Annexure 05 – BIQ*)

4.6.2 Introduction

The main purpose of this IEE report is to identify the existing environment in the proposed project area and to determine if the implementation of the project will adversely affect the existing environment. In particular, the IEE report will cover specific areas, such as physical, biological, ecological and socio-economic aspects, from a broader perspective. The potential environmental impacts of the project's activities and the necessary steps that must be taken to mitigate them are described in the IEE report.

4.6.3 Background of The Project

As per the current condition of the country it is essential to Provide specialized infrastructure to treat infected patients can encourage the medical staff by creating them a safe working environment and by maximizing the rate of healing it is possible to overcome the current situation of the country in health, social and economic aspects. And it is very important to make the health sector ready for the unexpected pandemic situations in future.

To evaluate the feasibility of the proposed IDH on the land selected by the client, three layout designs with different main hospital building shapes were considered and analyzed to choose the best Alternative. The best Alternative is selected by comparing scenarios for the social and health, technical, financial and environmental feasibilities. Out of these, Social and Health Feasibility is the most crucial.

According to the feasibility study H shaped building design and the lay out is the most feasible option

4.6.4 Project objectives and justification

- Provide a clear description of all project activities to be carried out during the project period.
- Identify all possible physical, ecological, and socio-economic impacts that can arise
- due to the proposed project.
- Provide mitigation measures to control/ reduce negative environmental and socioeconomic impacts of project activities.
- Ensure that the proposed project is environmentally sound and sustainable, while being economically feasible.
- Make use of the available land up 100% efficiently.
- Adapt the green concept to the building.
- Provide IDH facilities to the civilians and securing health and safety of people.
- Minimize the negative impacts to the environment.
- Protect the environment same time contribute to the socio-economy and health status of the country.

4.6.5 Scope of the Study

Initial Environmental Examination is performed as a requirement of laws and regulations implemented by the Central Environmental Authority. IEE covers all 4.5 acres in the project area. According to the IEE report planning to execute the mitigatory measures for minimize the impacts.

The scope of the study can be outlined as follows,

- Field data collection regarding physical, social, economic and environment background
- Preparation of BIQ and submission to CEA for environment clearance
- Preparation of Leopold matrix for identifying the major impacts
- Assessment of potential Environmental impacts and development of preventive and/or mitigation measures for significant impacts,
- Preparation of Environmental Management Plan (EMP) and Environmental Monitoring Plans

4.6.6 Brief outline of the methodologies adopted in IEE preparation

- Collect field data on physical, social, economic and environmental backgrounds.
- Public consultation with affected people and other relevant authorities.
- Preparing Leopold matrices to identify key effects.
- Assess potential environmental impacts, develop preventive or mitigation measures for significant impacts.
- Preparation of environmental management plan and environmental monitoring plan.
- Preparing an Integrated Initial Environmental Examination Report.

4.6.7 Applicable laws regulations, government policies, standards and requirements covering the proposed project

Before commencement of any construction work at the site it is necessary to obtain the necessary clearances from the statutory bodies for the proposed development project in accordance with the existing regulations and the law. It is necessary to get approval from the Following statutory bodies approval for the proposed development project.

- ❖ Approval from Ceylon Electricity Board
- ❖ Clearance from Municipal Council of Kotikawatta – Mulleriyawa
- ❖ Clearance from Fire Department
- ❖ Approval from CEA.
- ❖ Approval of National Water Supply and Drainage Board.
- ❖ Approval of Urban Development Authority.
 - PPC
 - Building permit
 - COC
- Approval of Road Development Authority

Acts

- The National Environmental (Amendment) Act No. 56 of 1988 -

Under this, the concept of environmental impact assessment was introduced as a strategic move to develop a sustainable built environment in the entire country with the implementation of some regulations.

- Urban development authority acts No:04 of 1982 -

Under this amendment, the development plan for the urban development area of Panadura (07/10/2016) was gazette. In this amendment, certain regulations were implemented according to the land use in the city area for development purposes.

- Flood Protection Ordinance No:04 of 1924 -

Under this act declared the flood area so certain protection measures needed to be implemented.

4.6.8 Description of The Proposed Project

4.6.8.1 Project Location

Figure 4-2 - Proposed Project Location

- Province - Western Province
- District - Colombo District
- Local Authority – Kotikawatta-Mulleriyawa Municipal Council
- Coordinates: Latitude: 6.92°, Longitude: 79.92°

4.6.8.2 Zoning map of Kotikawatta – Mulleriyawa Pradeshiya Sabha area

Project location is in the administrative and institutional zone of the Zoning map of kotikawatta – mulleriyawa pradeshiya shaba area where the existing IDH hospital already exists in that zone. Wetland nature conservation area is more than 200m away from the project location. According to the NEA any project with in 100 m is a prescribed project. Urbanized and commercial areas are also away from about 100 m radius from project location.

Figure 4-3 - Zoning Map of Kotikawatta Mulleriyawa

4.6.9 Brief Description About Major Component of The Project

4.6.9.1 Permanent structures

❖ Main hospital building

- Ground Floor – Consists of major 04 zones which separated with proper architectural planning.
 - Patient admission corridor zone (Contaminated area) - Patient Admission & Guidance Room, Patient Supporting staff rest room, Patient waiting area, Sampling Room, PTU & ETU, Pharmacy
 - Medical Staff corridor zone (Decontaminated zone)- Nurses ' Rest Area, Doctors Rest Area
 - Supply and services corridor zone (Decontaminated zone)- Medical Equipment Store, Pharmaceutical Store, Server Room, Intercom Room, ICT Room, CCTV Controlling Room, Eng. Services
 - Cleaning staff & Waste Disposal Corridor zone (Contaminated zone)– Cleaning Equipment Store, Cleaning Staff Rest Area, Cleaning staff management.
- 01st and 02nd floor
 - Decontaminated zone - Theater, Radiology Unit, ICU, Medical staff waiting Area
 - Contaminated Zones – Wards
 - Third Floor arrangement is similar to second floor except Theater area is changing to a Labour room in third floor
 - Transition zones are provided to separate Contaminated zones and Decontaminated zones

❖ Subsidiary buildings of the hospital

- Contaminated zone – Waste Management unit, Judicial Medical Unit, Mortuary
- Decontaminated zone - Blood Bank, Admin. Block, Kitchen and store, Quarters

- ❖ Service structures – Water Sump, fire water sump, pump house, Generator room, Transformer room, oxygen Room
- ❖ Parking – separate Parking for medical staffs in the decontaminated zone and separate parking for Ambulance service, public, and waste management
- ❖ Waste management zone – waste generated in the hospital specially bio hazardous waste collect and transport to specialized treatment plants in suburbs areas of Colombo.

4.6.9.2 Temporary Structures

- Laborers billets are going to placed one corner side of the land to prevent the most of the social conflicts with the neighbors.
- Contractors and Engineers Site Office
- Contractor's stores buildings, yards, dumping sites will be in separate locations.

4.6.10 Methodology of Construction

Following procedure is followed in the construction

- Site preparation
- Constructing the temporary structures such as billets and site office
- Excavation work
- Sub structure construction (pad Foundation)
- Erath filling and compaction
- Superstructure construction
- Final Finishes and service installation
- Internal road ways and parking
- Landscaping

4.6.11 Methodology of Operation

- Water Supply – Taken from the National Water Supply and Drainage Board collect in a sump pump to overhead tanks and distribute.
- Electricity – Electricity is supplied from the Ceylon Electricity Board. There is a separate transformer room and as backup power there is a generator.
- Repairs and Maintenance – There will be a separate crew for the maintenance of the building and cleaning and sanitization.
- Solid Waste Management – All the solid waste and bio hazardous waste collect in a separate zone with proper management and transport away bio hazardous waste to treatment plants and treat organic waste in the zone. Those collected solid waste is collecting by the Municipal Council Kotikawatta Mulleriyawa.
- Waste Water – All the waste water collected in the apartments are collected and followed through a treatment process and the treated water will be used for gardening
- Fire Fighting System – Fire extinguishers, hose reels, wet riser system is applied to the building to protect it from the sudden fire.
- Storm Water – There is a rain water harvesting system to collect storm water.

4.6.12 Proposed Schedule for The Implementation

Present feasibility and detailed engineering design of the project will be completed within the time frame. Once detailed designs and bid documents are completed, tenders will be awarded to the successful contractors. It is planned to finish the all constructions within 08 Months.

4.6.13 Description of The Existing Environment

4.6.13.1 Physical Environment

- ❖ Topography – Flat land with firm gravely soil.
- ❖ Meteorology – Wet Zone which get the higher rainfall during the rainy seasons.

- ❖ Hydrology – Commonly used City Main Water Supply. Surface runoff is moderate urban areas are about min. 200 m away from the proposed project.
- ❖ Land Use – Proposed land is in the Administrative and institutional zone and Residential zone is highly populated which is min. about 200m away from proposed land
- ❖ Biological/Ecological environment – There is wet land conservation area min. Distance about 200m away from the project land.
- ❖ Social and Archaeological environment – Village temple, play grounds, Schools, shopping malls located within 5km² area. Mostly Sinhala Buddhist people lives in that area.
- ❖ Climate – Average temperature 27-32 Celsius, located in wet-zone
- ❖ Soil and Vegetation – Existing firm soil and free of natural disasters. (floods/landslides)
- ❖ Human use and human health effect – Due to the urbanization facilities also developed in this area and better lifestyles and improved health facilities readily available.

4.6.14 Anticipated Environmental Impacts Due to Proposed Project

According to the Leopold matrix, following negative impacts are highly affected to the environment,

- ❖ Due to the removal of top soil, excavation works, and other earth works existing covered soil layers are damaged and exposed to weather which will lead to soil erosion and loss of sediments and nutrition to flora.
- ❖ Due to the waste water disposal, nontreated sanitary disposal, surface runoff, erosion, Improper Solid waste and bio hazardous disposal may affect to the ground water may pollute. Contamination of ground water can affect the flora and fauna and domestic water usages from wells.

- ❖ IDH is specifically designed to facilitate air borne disease so it is mandatory to provide fresh air to patients and protect medical staff and supportive staff from infecting virus through air. And to protect civilians and Air may get polluted due to the dust occur in construction works (excavation, sand, quarry, by vehicles).
- ❖ If not concerned about health and safety of the human resources, project works can delay if any accidents happen. And high cost needed if there any accidental situations. From the surfaces of the IDH it is possible to infect the virus and there is a high risk of carrying virus from hospital to the outside community.
- ❖ Due to the heavy machineries used for the construction higher level of noise and vibration eliminate and it may affect for the natural habitats and the surrounded community.
- ❖ When operational period generators sound makes vulnerable to the patients, medical staff and neighborhood.
- ❖ Usage of materials and disposals lot of vehicles need to access the site. It may affect to traffic of the 10th lane users.
- ❖ Bio hazardous waste, solid waste and waste water disposal, disturbance to the existing soil layer, excessive noise, disturbance to the eco system affect to the flora and fauna severely.
- ❖ Disposal of bio hazardous waste, solid waste, waste water caused uncomfortable for the residential, commercial and industrial works. And also, it may cause for the health and safety of the community too.

Positive Impacts,

- ❖ This kind of infrastructure improves the health facility in Sri Lanka and can minimize the deaths and infected patient counts in the country in a infectious diseases pandemic situation currently and in future.

- ❖ In a pandemic situation social, health and economic situation of the country is in a critical situation, by these kinds of infrastructure it is possible to minimize the threat.
- ❖ In infectious disease pandemic situation extra amount of waste adding to the environment such as surgical masks, shields, etc. It is important to have a specialized hospital for infectious diseases and take measures to control and prevent the spread of virus and get rid of the pandemic situation.
- ❖ Maintaining a good vegetation greenery component in site the building will help residents to feel the clean atmosphere with an eye-catching environment

4.6.15 Proposed Mitigatory Measures

(Annexure 06 - Leopold Metrix Chart for Identification of Impacts)

4.6.15.1 Ground water pollution

Minimize the surface runoff and improve the ground water recharge through the treated waste water and rain water collection pits. Implement the landscaping with the usage of flora. proper treating method should be implemented for the black water and gray water and proper disposal of solid waste and chemicals.

4.6.15.2 Soil pollution

High intensity rainfall in the area can induce severe erosion on loosely exposed soils. Use cover methods and compaction and plant cover crops or landscape. Landscaping, turfing, paving, tree cover can prevent soil erosion.

All quarry/burrow sites operated by the contractor should be licensed as appropriate and at contract closing, all burrow/quarry sites should be fully rehabilitated. If contractor would procure earth/quarry material, he should do so from sources that are operating with the required licenses.

4.6.15.3 Solid Waste and bio hazardous waste

A huge amount of solid waste during the construction and operation stages and specially bio hazardous waste produce in the operations stage generates so specialty management unit and cleaning and sanitization staff should be there as a separate unit

to manage the waste properly. The proper bin system needs to maintain on the site and need to collect the garbage and solid waste separately and periodically discharge to the collection truck of the hospital or local authority and also its recommended to minimize the generation of solid waste and reuse for different purposes at the site as possible

4.6.15.4 Noise and Vibration

Apply appropriate schedule to avoid any works that may cause noise and vibration during 10 pm – 6 am. Any night time activities should be done using noise reducing means or low-noise technologies, use vehicles and equipment that meet standards for noise and vibration in Sri Lanka. Use sound proof generators in the operations stage. Trees can be used to act as a barrier for noise.

4.6.15.5 Air pollution

This Hospital is specifically designed to air borne diseases so architectural separations should be use, natural ventilation should be use instead of air conditioning and tree plantation can use as a air purifier and also barrier for micro particles in air. proper watering methods are required to reduce the impact specially unloading loose materials like sand and metals and also required the watering of the tires of the construction vehicles when moving in and out from the site. Proper consideration should be given the selecting the construction vehicles used for the construction all should be licensed for the emission according to the given standards. Tree Plantation as shelters for parking and along the boundary can reduce air pollution.

4.6.15.6 Health and Safety of the human resources in the construction stage and safety of patients, staff and community in operational stage

One of the most important factors in maintaining the health and safety procedures is to ensure the safety of the construction workers. This helps to avoid unwanted accidents on the site and a healthy working environment for the workers. Never allow the workers to take unwanted risks on the site that will put them in danger. So, it's always required to maintain a high standard of health and safety policy on the site. That includes proper training should be prior to the works, wearing required PPE at the site, and regular safety meetings at the site. Safety of the workers and the residents.

Antiviral surface finishes should be use as much as possible and proper sanitization methods should be use.

4.6.16 Environment Management Plan

Table 4-7 - Environmental Management Plan

Factor	Impact	Mitigatory Measure
Ground water pollution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Due to the waste water disposal, non-treated sanitary disposal, surface runoff, erosion, Improper Solid waste and bio hazardous waste disposal may affect to the ground water • Contamination of ground water can affect the flora and fauna and domestic water usages from wells. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Minimize the surface runoff and improve the ground water recharge through the treated waste water and rain water collection pits. • Implement the landscaping with the usage of flora. • Proper treating method should be implemented for the black water and gray water and proper disposal of solid waste and chemicals. • Separate Waste management unit, and separate area deserved for disposal of waste which is facilitated to prevent leachate and sort the waste in order to dispose away to a treatment plant through waste disposal trucks of the hospital waste management unit and municipal waste disposing trucks
Soil pollution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Harmful effects of dust • Erosion of sediments and disturbance to the ecosystem 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Turfing, landscaping and tree plantation • Use silt/sedimentation traps. • All quarry/burrow sites operated by the contractor should be licensed and At contract closing, all burrow/quarry sites should be fully rehabilitated. If

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarry/burrow sites pits. (Health and safety issues) 	<p>contractor would procure earth/quarry material, he should do so from sources that are operating with the required licenses.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Slope protection for the soil to avoid collapsing of soil to the excavation pits and retaining walls. • Regular watering of service roads for dust suppression & Imposing speed controls for construction vehicles. • Use proper drain system and runoff water control methods.
Air pollution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Air borne diseases can spread through air and infect medical staff and civilians, and also patients need fresh air as the respiratory system is weaken by this virus. • Respiration and various health issues of workers and community in the construction stage. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Architectural separations and natural ventilation can use and tree plantation can use as an air purifier and also barrier for micro particles in air. • Employ construction machines with low emissions to reduce pollution. • Arranging sources of emission far from the residents. • All construction machines and vehicles should meet the standard on emissions and have passed the emission test. • No burning of wastes on site. • Limit traffic congestion through proper planning and operating of traffic diversions.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Do not let machines idle when not necessary.
<p>Safety of the human resources in the construction stage and safety of patients, staff and community in operational stage</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> From the surfaces of the IDH it is possible to infect the virus and there is a high risk of carrying virus from hospital to the outside community. Delay the project works if any accidents happen. High cost needed if there any accidental situations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Antiviral surface finishes should be use as much as possible and proper sanitization methods should be use. Proper briefing and training of workers on safety precautions, and their responsibilities for the safety of themselves and others. Implement the usage of Personal Protective Equipment`s to be used at every time involved in when construction activities and high visibility jackets at night. Arranging for the provision of first aid facilities, readily available trained paramedical personnel and emergency transport to the nearest hospital. Provision of traffic management plans during construction including barricading of openings and lighting at night where required.
<p>Noise and Vibration</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Excessive noise cause hearing problems and disturbs calmness of the hospital. Vibration harmful to the 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Schedule to avoid any construction works that may cause noise and vibration during 10 pm – 6 am. Tree cover can use as a noise barrier Any night time activities should be done using noise reducing means or low-noise

	adjacent buildings and disturbs calmness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> technologies, use vehicles and equipment that meet standards for noise and vibration in Sri Lanka.
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4.6.17 Environmental Monitoring Programme

Implement Agency of the Environment monitoring programme is the contractor and the supervising agency is the consultant.

Table 4-8 - Environmental Monitoring Plan

Parameters to be monitored	Mitigation Measures	Timing (Frequency)	Mitigation Cost
Ground water pollution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Minimize the surface runoff and improve the ground water recharge through the treated waste water and rain water collection pits. Implement the landscaping with the usage of flora. Proper treating method should be implemented for the black water and gray water and proper disposal of solid waste and chemicals Separate Waste management unit, and separate area deserved for disposal of waste which is facilitated to prevent leachate and sort the waste in order to dispose away to a 	When works execute and Continuous inspection in operation period	Construction cost and inspection in the construction period Included in the initial cost of project and the operations cost

	<p>treatment plant through waste disposal trucks of the hospital waste management unit and municipal waste disposing trucks</p>		
Soil pollution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Turfing, landscaping and tree plantation • Use silt/sedimentation traps. • All quarry/burrow sites operated by the contractor should be licensed and At contract closing, all burrow/quarry sites should be fully rehabilitated. If contractor would procure earth/quarry material, he should do so from sources that are operating with the required licenses. • Slope protection for the soil to avoid collapsing of soil to the excavation pits and retaining walls. • Regular watering of service roads for dust suppression & Imposing speed controls for construction vehicles. • Use proper drain system and runoff water control methods 	<p>When works execute and Continuous inspection in operation period</p>	<p>Construction cost and inspection in the construction period Included in the initial cost of project and the operations cost</p>

Air pollution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Architectural separations and natural ventilation can use and tree plantation can use as a air purifier and also barrier for micro particles in air. • Employ construction machines with low emissions to reduce pollution. • Arranging sources of emission far from the residents. • All construction machines and vehicles should meet the standard on emissions and have passed the emission test. • No burning of wastes on site. • Limit traffic congestion through proper planning and operating of traffic diversions. • Do not let machines idle when not necessary. 	When works execute and Continuous inspection in operation period	Construction cost and inspection in the construction period Included in the initial cost of project and the operations cost
Safety of the human resources in the construction stage and safety of patients, staff and community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Antiviral surface finishes should be use as much as possible and proper sanitization methods should be use. • Proper briefing and training of workers on 	When works execute and Continuous inspection in operation period	Construction cost and inspection in the construction period Included in the initial cost of

<p>in operational stage</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • safety precautions, and their responsibilities for the safety of themselves and others. • Implement the usage of Personal Protective • Equipment`s to be used at every time involved in when construction activities and high visibility jackets at night. • Arranging for the provision of first aid • facilities, readily available trained paramedical personnel and emergency transport to the nearest hospital. • Provision of traffic management plans during • construction including barricading of openings and lighting at night where required. 		<p>project and the operations cost</p>
<p>Noise & vibration</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Schedule to avoid any construction works that may cause noise and vibration during 10 pm – 6 am. • Tree cover can use as a noise barrier 	<p>When works execute and Continuous inspection in operation period</p>	<p>Construction cost and inspection in the construction period Included in the initial cost of</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Any night time activities should be done using noise reducing means or low-noise • Technologies, use vehicles and equipment that meet standards for noise and vibration in Sri Lanka. 		project and the operations cost
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4.6.18 Conclusion and Recommendations of IEE

IEE study has observed that, owing to its magnitude and design, the proposed project will have comparatively low negative impacts on the environment. Mainly identified impacts are bio hazardous waste generation, solid waste and waste water generation, air pollution, Noise and vibration etc. Most of these impacts are location specific and short term, which will arise during the construction period. No significant impacts on bio-physical environment can be anticipated. Mitigatory measures have been proposed in the Environmental Management Plan to mitigate such impacts. It is strongly recommended to maintenance at least the recommended environmental flow at all times to reduce the impacts of water pollution due to the project. However, there are lot of advantages can get from this project.

4.7 Traffic Impact Assessment [TIA]

4.7.1 Introduction

The traffic impact assessment is a study which is determined the impact on the existing traffic due to a proposed development. This traffic impact analysis is done during the initial stage of development. It can be used to properly plan development activities while minimizing the impact on existing traffic and avoiding inconveniences. It is also legally obliged to prepare a Traffic Impact Assessment for specific development activities by the developer in accordance with the Urban Development Authority Law, No. 41 OF 1978, recently issued by the Urban Development Authority, the agency responsible for urban planning and design in Sri Lanka.

This Traffic Impact Assessment was prepared for Design of New Quarantine Hospital for Infectious Diseases (IDH) in Kotikawatta, Mulleriyawa, Sri Lanka. Based on the following legal conditions.

A Traffic Impact Assessment (TIA) shall be submitted for the development stipulated hereunder: -

- i. Residential development which exceeds 50 units;
- ii. Commercial floor area which exceeds 10,000 m²;
- iii. Warehousing floor area which exceeds 20,000 m²;
- iv. Any shopping mall/ super market/ departmental store where the regulatory parking requirement exceeds 25 parking stalls;
- v. Any development having entry and exit from a main road and regulatory parking requirement exceeds 25 parking stalls and which is located:
 - Within 100 m from a traffic signal light or a signalized junction
 - National Highway
 - Within 15 m to either sides from a bus halt or bus bay area
 - Within 25 m to either sides from a pedestrian crossing
 - An access-controlled highway to an Expressway
 - Where the Relevant Authority deems necessary

According to the condition V of requirements for a TIA by UDA, this hospital project has to undergo a TIA assessment as the main access is provided from the national road B231 Mandavila road and exceed 25 parking stalls.

4.7.2 The Current Situation Around the Site

The proposed hospital is to be constructed in Kotikawatta-Mulleriyawa. B435 Awissawella road, B439 Kotikawatta Road, B 469 Buthgamuwa road are feeding B231 Mandavila road or Hospital road which gives the access to the proposed hospital. These roads already giving access to the National mental hospital Angoda, other institutions in the area and for the residents of the area.

4.7.3 Existing Traffic Network

Figure 4-4 - Existing Traffic Network

Figure 4-6 - Gothatuwa Junction

Figure 4-5 - Road Infront of Proposed Project

Figure 4-7 – Mandavila Junction

4.7.4 Traffic flow around the site

To determine current and future traffic conditions, existing traffic data from the road network must be computed. For the proposed hospital project, we need traffic data on the main road of B231 Mandavila road. Traffic counts were carried out in 24/01/2022 to determine the current traffic conditions on the site manually.

In the first phase, traffic calculations were carried out on both sides from 7 a.m. to 8:30 a.m. Then we performed the calculations from 1:00 p.m. to 2:30 p.m. taking into account the school hours and from 4:00 p.m. to 5:30 p.m. the traffic was calculated in terms of working hours.

Traffic survey details, (*Annexure 07*)

Service Flow Rate = 154 PCU /Hr.

Service Flow for 7.00 am to 7.00 pm = $154 \times 12 = 1848$

Traffic flow in the next 10 years (A) = $P(1 + r)^n$

= $1,848(1 + 0.015)^{10}$

= 2,144 (**2,150**)

Note:

P – No. of vehicles per last count

A – Traffic in the year

r – Rate of growth of traffic (**Assumption: Traffic Growth Rate is 1.5%**)

n – No. of years

From 7.00 am to 7.00 pm traffic flow is about 1848 vehicles in B231 Mandavila road. Mostly, that vehicle is mainly composed of light vehicles. Therefore, assuming a 1.5% vehicle growth rate, in the next 10 years from 7.00 am to 7.00 pm, this road would be carrying nearly a total of 2150 vehicles per day. The majority of vehicles on B231 Mandavila road in peak hours are motorcycles (45%). This is followed by vehicles with passenger cars (17%). Majority of traffic is from light vehicles of about 85% in peak hours and heavy vehicle movements are only 15% of total movement. As per the survey this is not a heavily trafficked road.

4.7.5 Traffic generation based on the proposed site

Although traffic generation is known to be a function of land use and development, some general assumptions had to be made due to the lack of local standards. Therefore, the following traffic forecasting method was used in the study. The proposed development will have 100 parking spaces (according to UDA guidelines), and this value has been used for traffic generation calculations.

On the more general assumption that when the proposed development is in full operation, every 15 minutes 10% of the parking spaces receive a new vehicle and the previous vehicle leaves the bay. This is probably an estimate of the higher-order since in practice the chances for longer parked vehicles are higher as staff vehicles spend more than 60 minutes.

Hence a higher factor of safety is assumed. Therefore every 15 minutes 10 vehicles arrive and 10 vehicles depart the development area.

Vehicles entering from B231 road (For 15 Min :) =10

vehicles entering to B231 road (For 15 Min :) =10

Total number of vehicles on B231 =20

(Assumption: that all incoming and outgoing vehicles are light vehicles and that all light vehicles PCU factor will 0.8)

Service Flow Rate for Mandavila main road from the proposed hospital = $20 \times 4 \times 12 \times 0.8$ (From 7.00 am to 7.00 pm) = 768 PCU.

Traffic flow in the next 10 years (A) = $P(1 + r)^n$

(Assumption: Traffic Growth Rate is 1.5%)

$$= 768(1 + 0.015)^{10} = 891 \text{ (900)}$$

4.7.6 Identification of Potential Impacts

This part describes construction-related effects that may occur in Preferred around a proposed site. This can be determined into two stages. Such as during construction stage and after the construction stage.

Identification of Potential Impacts During the Construction Phase

Traffic jam due to heavy vehicle traffic	In the construction phase lots of heavy vehicles are involve for transport of materials as well as transport of pre-fabricated steel elements to the site. As the Mandavila road is a undivided 2way road there can be a traffic congestion
Damage the roadway due to heavy traffic	Mandavila road is a carper road which is constructed years ago and due to the heavy vehicle movement specially the prefabricated elements roadway can damage.

Table 4-9 - Potential Impacts During the Construction Phase

Identification of Potential Impacts After the Construction Phase

Road safety matters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of road signs and non-functioning • There is no public proper parking space. • No lane marks and pedestrian crossing. • Narrow shoulders • Uncovered drain system • Consideration on Disabled people
Increased traffic jam	The proposed hospital is more than 240 bed capacity so it will affect the traffic congestion.
Road surface Damages	Increased traffic movements can damage the road surface.

Table 4-10 - Potential Impacts After the Construction Phase

4.7.7 Proposed Mitigatory Measures

A traffic impact assessment (TIA) is a technical analysis of traffic and safety issues related to a specific development and proposed mitigation measures of the identified impacts. The main objective of the TIA report is to determine whether a specific development project will affect the safety and efficiency of the adjacent roads.

- Create road lanes according to rules and regulations of RDA and proper road markings, pedestrian crossings, humps, roads signs where necessary
- A drainage system that works well and properly cover of drains is essential for both roads safety and road durability.
- Expanding road width and expand the width of shoulders can improve the durability of road and provide space for emergency parking.
- Creating traffic lights in Gothatuwa junction. Can minimize traffic jam
- Road network capacity improvements
- Traffic control Improvements within the site,
 - Proper Internal circulation improvements
 - Access improvements
 - Adequate parking arrangements
- Provide separate pedestrian tiled walkways and establish security rails at the roadside as needed
- Introduced speed limitation on the road specially near the hospital and use humps, pedestrian crossings with signal lights,

4.7.8 Parking Space

As per the UDA guidelines minimum requirement for parking is 01 parking space for 05 beds as the hospital has the capacity of 240 bed capacity parking requirement is 48. And the parking capacity is as follows.

Area	Parking slots provided (No)
Ambulance parking	22
Drivers area	25 (Bike)
Public area	22
	03(disabled)
	17(Bike)
Medical staff and admin area	38
	50 (Bikes)
Supply and services area	03
	02 (Lorries)
Waste Management Area	04
	03 (Lorries)

Table 4 11 - Parking Spaces in Proposed Project

Figure 4-8 - Parking Slot Sizes

Figure 4-9 - Parking arrangement and internal road sizing in Ambulance parking and public parking area.

Figure 4-10 - Parking and internal roadway arrangement in medical staff parking area

4.8 Architectural Concept Development

4.8.1 Details of Proposed Site Layout and Comparison with Ascendant Regulations.

- Project – Design of New Quarantine Hospital for Infectious Diseases (IDH) in Kotikawatta, Mulleriyawa, Sri Lanka
- Location – Kotikawatta -Mulleriyawa
- Building category – Hospital.
- Regulation ascendant – Urban Development Authority Law No 41 of 1978. (UDA, 2021)

Table 4-11 - Accordance with UDA Regulations

Element	Specified Regulation	Actual Scenario	Satisfactory Level
Land	Located in administrative and institutional zone	Hospital building	Satisfy
Maximum Plot Coverage	Maximum 66 2/3 % for residential	Floor area ratio = $\frac{\text{Ground floor plinth area}}{\text{Total land area}}$ $= \frac{2000}{18167} \times 100$ $= 11\%$	Satisfy
Road Frontage	Minimum 12 m	167 m	Satisfy
Rear Space	Minimum 3 m	More than 03 m	Satisfy
Minimum Plot Size	12 Perches	718 Perches	Satisfy
Building Line	09m(from B class Rd)	More than 09m	Satisfy

Internal Height	(Clear Height)		
Toilets	Minimum 2.2 m	3.5 m	Satisfy
Room for patient	Minimum 2.8 m	3.5 m	Satisfy
Natural Light and Ventilation	(% From Floor Area)		Satisfy
Toilets	0.2sq.m opening area & 100% openable	0.3 Sq.m opening area & 100% openable	Satisfy
Stair Case			
	Width – 105cm	125cm	Satisfying
	Thread – 22.5 cm (min.)	22.5 m	Satisfying
	Riser – 17.5 cm (Max.)	170 m	Satisfying
Toilets			
Male toilets	03per 50 beds	15	Satisfying
Female toilets	03per 50 beds	15	Satisfying
Male urinals	03per 50 beds	15	Satisfying
Male wash basins	03per 50 beds	15	Satisfying
Female wash basins	03per 50 beds	15	Satisfying

4.9 Architectural Design

4.9.1 General

The architectural form is the visual characteristic of a building which gives it a unique identity and differentiates it from the others. And the other word architectural form is the point of contact between mass and space. Building architecture is not only about achieving its aesthetic appearance, but also about using limited space effectively.

During the feasibility stage, various alternatives for building shape were analyzed and finally the H shaped building was identified as the best choice in terms of social and health, Financial, technical and environmental feasibility studies.

4.9.2 Building Shape

Shape of the building is symmetrical but it is a unique shape and expression of symbolic shape for the hospital in aerial view. Shape of the building also enhances the natural ventilation capacity and facilitate proper separation of contaminated and decontaminated zones itself.

Figure 4-11 – Front elevation

Figure 4-12 - Side Elevation

(Annexure 08 – Architectural Drawings)

4.10 Structural Design

4.10.1 Design of Superstructure

When doing super structural design, the selection of a structural system basically involved conceptual design phase, preliminary design phase, software analysis and the manual detailed design.

4.10.1.1 Conceptual design phase

The concept design represents the design team's first reaction to the project assignment. According the SWOT analysis which was done in the technical feasibility study there are lot of positives and less negative in the steel structure frame system. As the main consideration of this project is rapid construction steel frame structure is the best option and though the initial cost is bit high steel frame structure is economical as rapid construction gives quicker benefits, reusable reduce foundation cost, enhance internal spaces and reduce number of columns and have a scrap value.

When conceptual designing considered advantage of using longer spans and proper utilization of circulation space. Building width of 15m achieved by 2 spans of 7.5m used for naturally ventilated floors and also natural lighting was considered.

The structural arrangement is carried out by placing the structural elements in accordance with the architectural drawings, taking into account the architectural aspects. This was a difficult task.

The load path extends from the roof over each structural element to the foundation. Vertical loads are mainly transmitted by columns and lateral loads are transmitted by Bracing. Loads are transferred different structural elements through joint. All x directions beams were connected with fixed joints and all Z direction beams were considered as pinned jointed. And all the supports were considered as pinned supports.

Composite slab generally comprised profile steel floor deck with cast in place concrete cast over the deck. The deck acts as permanent shuttering and spans in the direction transverse to the secondary beams primary and secondary beams in composite steel frame are rigidly connected to the floor slab by shear studs which are connected to the beams by threw duck welding technique this allow the floor slab and the beam beneath to act compositely.

Composite beams typically consisting with steel I section acting structurally with the concrete slab by means of shear. Connectors attached to the top flange of the section. The beams are generally designed simply supported due to the composite action of steel beam and concrete slab it is possible to take sections with smaller size. The composite action of beams and slab also increases stiffness in beams so Z directions beams are restrained laterally due to decking and fixing. And restrict lateral torsional buckling

The reinforcement used in composite slab construction is relatively light weight and act as transverse reinforcement to the composite beams.

4.10.1.2 Preliminary Design

In the preliminary structural design, some rule of thumb in designer manuals and preliminary design sources were followed (Steel Buildings in Europe, n.d.)

In sources suggested maximum beam spanning was 12m and in this project maximum beam span is 7.5m. Primary beam primary beam span to depth ratio was suggested as 15-18.

4.10.1.3 Analysis of Structure Using STADD. Pro V8i SS6 Software

4.10.1.3.1 Introduction

STAAD Pro is a structural analysis & design software which is one of the popular and widely used software for structural analysis and design all around the world. It ensures on-time and budget-friendly completion of structures and designs related to steel, concrete, timber, aluminum, and cold-formed steel projects and helps structural engineers to automate their tasks by removing the tedious and long procedures of the manual methods.

STAAD Pro is a software that does structural analysis and design for the civil engineering structures such as buildings, bridges etc. and any design related to steel, concrete, timber, Aluminum etc. This software id under the ownership of BENTLY systems. STAAD Pro stands for structural analysis and design programme.

This software ensures fast, economized and accurate analysis and design and by using this user-friendly software it is possible to overcome tedious, and long procedure manual detail design, saves time of the professionals and minimize human errors which can be happen in manual design.

So, to analysis and design of this project was done with the software STAAD Pro software V8i SS6 version.

4.10.1.3.2 Methodology of the Design Processes

The following steps were taken to design the structure of our IDH and to analyze the structure

- Preparation for general layout of floor plan and selecting the element sizes according to the rules of thumb.
- Modeling of structure.
- Define and Assign Members.
- Assign connection type.
- Define and Assign gravitational loads.
- Define and Assign wind loads.
- Define Load Combinations.
- Analysis Design and optimization.

Preparation for general layout of floors

Architectural drawings were used to make the general layout. According to the architectural drawings, columns, beams, slabs, secondary beams, trusses were decided. Secondary beams have been added to support the slab.

Figure 4-13 – Layout Plan

Modeling of structure

Figure 4-14 – Modeling of structure

Define and Assign Members

Selected British UB and UC shapes and European standard SHS and CHS from section properties table.

Figure 4-15 - Section properties table

Properties of each shape can be checked as following figure.

RECNO	StaadName	AX cm^2	D mm	Bf mm	Tf mm	1 n
1	UC356X406X634	808.00	474.60	424.00	77.00	
2	UC356X406X551	702.00	455.60	418.50	67.50	
3	UC356X406X467	595.00	436.60	412.20	58.00	
4	UC356X406X393	501.00	419.00	407.00	49.20	
5	UC356X406X340	433.00	406.40	403.00	42.90	
6	UC356X406X287	366.00	393.60	399.00	36.50	
7	UC356X406X235	299.00	381.00	394.80	30.20	
8	UC356X368X202	257.00	374.60	374.70	27.00	
9	UC356X368X177	226.00	368.20	372.60	23.80	
10	UC356X368X153	195.00	362.00	370.50	20.70	
11	UC356X368X129	164.00	355.60	368.60	17.50	
12	UC305X305X283	360.00	365.30	322.20	44.10	
13	UC305X305X240	306.00	352.50	318.40	37.70	

Options
 Select Single Section
 Select Sections to Project Database

Buttons: New, Add, Remove, Add All, Import, Select, Close

Figure 4-16 – Section properties library

Plate Element/Surface Property

Plate Element Thickness

Node 1: 0.13 m
 Node 2: 0.13 m
 Node 3: 0.13 m
 Node 4: 0.13 m

Material
 CONCRETE

Buttons: Change, Assign, Close, Help

Figure 4-17 - Slab element properties

Figure 4-18 - 3D view of structure

Figure 4-19 - Assigned properties

Assign connection type

The screenshot shows the 'Member Specification' dialog box with the 'Release' tab selected. The 'Location' is set to 'Start' and the 'Release Type' is 'Partial Moment Release'. Under 'Partial Moment Release', the 'MP' checkbox is checked with a value of 0.95. Other checkboxes (MPX, MPY, MPZ) are unchecked with values of 0. The 'Release' section contains checkboxes for FX, KFX, FY, KFY, FZ, KFZ, MX, KMX, MY, KMY, MZ, and KMZ, all with values of 0. The units for FX, FY, FZ, KFX, KFY, KFZ are kN/m, and for MX, MY, MZ, KMX, KMY, KMZ are kN-m/deg. The 'Apply to this Member Only' checkbox is checked. Buttons at the bottom include 'Change', 'Close', 'Assign', and 'Help'.

Figure 4-20 - Pin connection with partial moment release

The screenshot shows the 'Member Specification' dialog box with the 'Release' tab selected. The 'Location' is set to 'Start' and the 'Release Type' is 'Release'. Under 'Partial Moment Release', the 'MP' checkbox is unchecked with a value of 0. Other checkboxes (MPX, MPY, MPZ) are also unchecked with values of 0. The 'Release' section contains checkboxes for FX, KFX, FY, KFY, FZ, KFZ, MX, KMX, MY, KMY, MZ, and KMZ, all with values of 0. The units for FX, FY, FZ, KFX, KFY, KFZ are kN/m, and for MX, MY, MZ, KMX, KMY, KMZ are kN-m/deg. The 'Add' button is highlighted. Buttons at the bottom include 'Add', 'Close', 'Assign', and 'Help'.

Figure 4-21 - Fixed connection

Figure 4-22 - pinned Supports assigned

Define and Assign gravitational loads

Following loads were calculated manually and entered to software. (see manual design for calculations)

Gravitational Load	Magnitude
<u>Dead Load</u>	
Floor Load	3.58 KN/m ²
Load on truss	3.85 KN/m
Load on corner truss	1.925 KN/m
Wall load	9 KN/m
Self-weight	Automatically calculating
<u>Live Load</u>	
Floor	3.8 KN/m ²
Truss	0.6 KN/m
Corner truss	0.3 KN/m

Table 4-12 – Assigned gravitational loads

Figure 4-23 - Assigned gravitational loads (diagram)

Define and Assign wind loads

Wind load was defined according to ASCE-7 codes and Following common data was entered as required considering conditions of the site location. Building risk category was selected as Essential facility, Basic wind speed was selected as 80mph which is a typical velocity of a hurricane. Exposure condition B was selected because Mulleriyawa is a sub urban area and structure type was selected as building

Figure 4-24 – Input common data

Figure 4-25 – Automatically assigned wind intensities as per common data

Wind intensity for height automatically calculated depending on the input common parameters. Then assigned wind load.

Figure 4-26 - Assigned wind load in Z- Direction

Define Load Combinations.

Following Euro code lode combinations were assigned

- Dead + Imposed
- 1.35Dead + 1.5Imposed
- 1.35 Dead + 1.5 Imposed + 0.9Wind (WX+)
- 1.35 Dead + 1.5 Imposed + 0.9Wind (WX-)
- 1.35 Dead + 1.5 Imposed + 0.9Wind (WZ+)
- 1.35 Dead + 1.5 Imposed + 0.9Wind (WZ-)

Analysis Design and optimization.

Run analysis command was given to start the analysis and found Zero errors and zero warnings, so went to post processing mode and then select the code EN 1993-1-1:1995. Then define the steel grade parameters.

- I and h sections - S275
- CHS and SHS sections – S355

Figure 4-27 – Checking errors and warnings

Then performed analysis. Utility check option indicates failed members by automatically checking the ratio of critical load / Design load it should be equal or less than 1 ideally close to 0.9, if it is more than 01 the member is failed. If it is too low member is uneconomical. So, by utility check option it is possible to identify failed members and to economize the structure. (*Annexure 09 – STAAD.Pro report*)

Economized sections

Element	Section
Columns - Ground floor and first floor	UC254X254X73
Columns - Second floor	UC203X203X60
Primary Beams - X direction	UB457X191X133
Primary Beams - Z direction 7 to 7.5m span	UB457X191X98
Primary Beams - Z direction 5 to 6m span	UB356X127X39
Secondary beams	UB254X146X43
Tie beams - roof level	UB178X102X19
Truss top and bottom chords	100X6.3SHS
Truss intermediate chords	70X5SHS
Bracing	219.1X10CHS

Table 4-13 – Assigned sections

Diagrams

UB 457×191×98 beam maximum displacement only annotated. it is possible to annotate every member automatically for the convenience of reference.

Figure 4-28 - Displacement diagrams

Figure 4-29 - Bending moment diagrams of structure whole structure

Figure 4-30 - Bending moment diagrams – front view of structure

Figure 4-31 - Axial force diagrams of structure - whole structure

Figure 4-32 - Axial force diagrams of structure – front view of structure

4.10.1.4 Manual Detailed design

Codes used for detail design,

- EN 1990 Basis of structural design
- EN 1991 Actions on structures
- EN 1992 Design of concrete structures
- EN 1993 Design of steel structures
- EN 1994 Design of composite steel and concrete structures

The information given in the Structural Eurocodes is based on limit state design.

Ultimate limit states

Ultimate limit states are those that relate to the failure of a structural member or a whole structure. Design verifications that relate to the safety of the people in and around the structure are ultimate limit state verifications.

Serviceability limit states

Serviceability limit states concern the functioning of the structure under normal use, the comfort of the people using the structure and the appearance of the structure.

Beam

Characteristic actions – Floors above ground level

Density of concrete -24KN/m³

(Also add 1KN/m³ for reinforcement and 1KN/m³ for operational load)

, Slab thickness -130mm

Self-weight of floor = $26\text{KN/m}^3 \times 0.130\text{m} = 3.38\text{kN/m}^2$

Self-weight of ceiling & services = 0.2 kN/m²

STAAD.Pro Analysis verified beams were checked in detail manual structural design. For example, consider floor beam at Level 1 – Gridline 5 D-E verified section 457 × 191 × 98 UKB

Mass per meter = 98.3kg/m (Steel, 2018)

Self-weight of beam = 98.3kg/m \times 7.5m = 737.25 \times 9.81/1000= 0.7KN

Total permanent action is,

$$g_k = 3.58 + 0.2 + 0.7 = \underline{4.48 \text{ kN/m}^2}$$

Imposed floor load for offices (category C3) = 3.0 kN/m²

Imposed floor load for moveable partitions of less than 2 kN/m run = 0.8 kN/m²

Total variable action is,

$$q_k = 3.0 + 0.8 = \underline{3.8 \text{ kN/m}^2}$$

Ultimate limit state (ULS)

Partial factors for actions

Partial factor for permanent actions $\gamma_G = 1.35$

Partial factor for variable actions $\gamma_Q = 1.5$

Reduction factor $\xi = 0.925$

The combination factor (ψ_0) is not required as the only variable action is the imposed floor load. The wind has no impact on the design of this member. (Eurocode01, 2002)

Combination of actions at ULS

Design value of combined actions,

$$\xi \gamma_G g_k + \gamma_Q q_k$$

$$= (0.925 \times 1.35 \times 4.48) + (1.5 \times 3.8) = 11.29 \text{ kN/m}^2$$

Design moment and shear force was calculated then Trial section selection is done.

Assumed the nominal thickness (t) of the flange and web is less than or equal to 16 mm, the yield strength (f_y) = 275 N/mm²

The required section needs to have a plastic modulus about the major-axis (y-y) that is greater than:

$$W_{pl,y} = M_{y,Ed} \gamma_{M0} / f_y$$

$W_{pl,y}$ - Maximum bending moment at mid span

γ_{M0} - 1

and the analysis was performed to verify whether the shear resistance, shear buckling, moment resistance and other checks are satisfactory and found that 457 × 191 × 98 UKB, S275 is satisfied. (*Annexure 10 – Manual Detail Design*)

Slab

ComFlor 60 composite floor profile offers the ultimate in lightweight steel decking for all multi-rise buildings. It combines exceptional spanning capabilities with reduced concrete usage to provide a cost-effective and attractive floor solution that is easy to install.

The state-of-the-art profile has been developed using modern roll-forming techniques. Capable of unpropped continuous spans to 4.5 meters and propped spans to 6.8 meters. In this design the span between secondary beams are 3.5 meters propped span so CF deck can adapt

Figure 4-33 – Decking Slab

Total depth of slab $h = 130 \text{ mm}$

Corus profiled steel sheeting CF60 – From designer's manual (ComFlor, n.d.)

Thickness of profile $t = 1.0 \text{ mm}$

Depth of profile $h_p = 60 \text{ mm}$

Span $L = 3.5 \text{ m}$

Effective cross-sectional area of the profile $A_{pe} = 1424 \text{ mm}^2/\text{m}$

Second moment of area of the profile $I_p = 106.15 \text{ cm}^4/\text{m}$

Yield strength of the profiled deck $f_{yp} = 350 \text{ N/mm}^2$

Design value of bending resistance (sagging) $MR_d = 11.27 \text{ KNm/m}$

Height of neutral axis above soffit: $= 30.5 \text{ mm}$

Concrete

Normal concrete strength class C25/30

Density (normal weight, reinforced) 26 kN/m^3 (wet)

25 kN/m^3 (dry)

Cylinder strength $f_{ck} = 25 \text{ N/mm}^2$

Modulus of elasticity $E_{cm} = 31 \text{ kN/mm}^2$

Actions

Concrete weight

Self-weight of the concrete slab (volume from decking manufacturer's data)

$$0.097 \times 26 \times 10^{-6} = 2.52 \text{ kN/m}^2 \text{ (wet)}$$

$$0.097 \times 25 \times 10^{-6} = 2.43 \text{ kN/m}^2 \text{ (dry)}$$

Then calculated characteristic actions and found the ULS design load by the load combination then did the analysis.

Design moment and shear force was calculated and the analysis was performed to verify whether the bending resistance, shear resistance and other checks are satisfactory and found that the CF60 Corus profiled steel sheeting decking G25 130mm thick slab is satisfied. (*Annexure 10 – Manual Detail Design*)

Transverse reinforcement was designed as A193 mesh reinforcement in the secondary beam design. And shear stud.pro requirement was designed as 12 Nos. of 19mm dia. stud shear connectors per half span.

Fabric type	Mesh square mesh size(mm)	Dia.(mm)	Mass per m ²	Nos of sheets per ton
A193	200×200	7	3.02	29

Table 4-14 - Mesh manufacturers data

Total permanent action is = $0.45 / \cos 15 = 0.46 \text{ kN/m}^2$

Total Variable action is = 0.6 kN/m^2

Column

The columns in the structure carry the load from the beams and slabs to the foundation. Calculated the ULS axial load, or it is possible to take the node reaction from the design software STAAD. Pro.

In this design verified section in the software was rechecked in detailed design process, or there are sources (*Steel Buildings in Europe, n.d.*) to assume a trial section,

Number of floors supported by column section	typical column size (h)
1	150
2 – 4	200
3 – 8	250
5 – 12	300
10 – 40	350

Table 4-15 – thumb rule of column size selection (*Steel Buildings in Europe, n.d.*)

Checked Flexural buckling resistance, Lateral torsional buckling resistance moment and verified that 254×254×73 UKC, S275 section is satisfactory.

Roof Truss

Figure 4-34 – Roof truss

The truss is 15 m span with 15° pitch. The truss uses hollow sections for its tension chord, rafters, and internal members. The truss is fully welded. Truss analysis is carried out by placing concentrated loads at the joints of the truss. All of the joints are assumed to be pinned in the analysis and therefore only axial forces are carried by members.

Imposed roof actions

Self-weight of roof construction	0.40 kN/m ²
Roof sheeting	0.07 KN/m ²
Insulation	0.01 KN/m ²
Purlins	0.07 KN/m ²
Self-weight of ceiling and services	0.15 kN/m ²
Self-weight of Solar panels	0.15 kN/m ²
Self-weight of roof construction	0.45 kN/m ² (On slope)

Total permanent action is = $0.45 / \cos 15 = 0.46 \text{ kN/m}^2$ (on plan)

Total Variable action is = 0.6 kN/m^2

Design value for combined actions is calculated and truss analysis was done to find reactions and compression and tension forces. Checked the verified section from STAAD.Pro. for compressive design resistance, flexural buckling resistance under ULS and check for deflection under SLS combination. And following sections were verified.

- Design of bottom chords - $100 \times 100 \times 6.3$ SHS, S355
- Design of bottom chords - $100 \times 100 \times 6.3$ SHS, S355
- Design of internal members - $70 \times 70 \times 5$ SHS, S355

Bracing

The bracing system must carry the equivalent horizontal forces (EHF) in addition to the wind loads. The braced bays, acting as vertical pin-jointed frames, transfer the horizontal wind load to the ground. Total overall unfactored wind load is considered as, $F_w = 925$ kN for each of leeward and backward directions of X & Z direction. When the wind is applied in the opposite direction, the bracing member considered in compression will be loaded in tension.

Cross sectional resistance to axial compression, Flexural buckling resistance was checked and 219.1×10.0 mm thick (CHS), grade S355 section was verified.

Connection design

Basically, there are two types of joining methods adapted, they are bolted connections and welded connections, in this design there are different types of connections.

- Shear connection – Pin supported Z direction beams
- Moment connection – Fixed supported x direction beams
- Splice connection – Connection of two different column sizes
- Column base plate – To transfer column forces to footing

Base plate connection

Connection of base plate to column It is assumed that the axial force is transferred by direct bearing, which is achieved by normal fabrication processes. Only nominal welds are required to connect the baseplate to the column, though in practice full profile 6mm fillet welds are often used. The column is assumed to be pin-ended. However, it is crucial the column is stable during the erection phase therefore 4 bolts outside the column profile should be used.

Base plate was designed 20mm thick base plate in S275 material

Beam-to-column flexible end plate connection

Considering shear force of beam (V_{Ed}), properties steel sections, and taking $f_y = 275$ N/mm²; $f_u = 410$ N/mm².

Trial assumption -

10 mm endplate is proposed & 6 M20 bolts are proposed.

Bolt details -

The bolts are fully threaded, non-preloaded, M20 8.8, 60 mm long,

Tensile stress area of bolt $A_s = 245$ mm²

Diameter of the holes $d_0 = 22$ mm

Diameter of the washer $d_w = 37$ mm

Yield strength $f_{yb} = 640$ N/mm²

Ultimate tensile strength $f_{ub} = 800$ N/mm²

Shear resistance was verified after analysis.

4.10.2 Design of sub-structure

4.10.2.1 Site investigation

The purpose of a site investigation is to determine the soil conditions that could affect the proposed development.

As per the reconnaissance survey and presidency studies on 11.12.2021, it was found that bearing capacity of the building which is about 800m away from the proposed land boundary is a five storied housing scheme project which is supported by a Pad Foundation which was constructed by SEC. And the soil investigation details suggest that bearing capacity of soil more than 200 KN/m².

- Carried out 04 No. Trial Pits to a maximum depth of 3.0m GL (*Annexure 11*)
- Geotechnical field test DCPT was done.

The trial pits were excavated using a JCB 3CX excavator and geotechnical engineer identified the soil type and assumed properties by experience.

The sequence of strata encountered were consistent across the site and are generally comprised;

- Topsoil
- Cohesive Deposits
- Granular Deposits

Dynamic cone penetrometer test was carried out to measure the resistance of soil strata.

Blows/100 mm	Allowable bearing capacity (kPa)
≤1	≤50 kPa
1–2	50–100 kPa
2–5	100–200 kPa
6–9	200–400 kPa
≥10	>400 kPa

Figure 4-35 - DCP correlation to allowable bearing capacity

Considering base reactions and taking the bearing capacity of soil as 250 KN/m² Isolated pad footings were designed manually. (*Annexure 10 – Manual Detail Design*)

4.10.2.2 Analysis of Sub structure by STAAD. Foundation software.

According to DCPT results which could refer in the manual detail design foundation selection section, isolated footing foundation type adapted for the structure. Computerized analysis and design were done using STAAD. foundation V8i software. Exported reaction values from STAAD. Pro software.

Figure 4-36 – Column numbers and location

Load combinations

Figure 4-37 - Generate load combinations

Software automatically generate load combinations and this project foundation was designed as per BS8110-97.

- Dead + Imposed
- 1.4Dead + 1.4Imposed
- 1.2Dead + 1.2Imposed

Then input design parameters 62 No. of footings were analyzed and designed.

Footing No	Column No in STADD pro	Foundation Geometry			No of footings
		Length	Width	Thickness	
1	1,9,148,156,260,268,411,419	1.350 m	1.350 m	0.305 m	7
2	2,4,6,8,149,155,261,267,412,414,416,418	1.650 m	1.650 m	0.305 m	12
3	3,7,413,417	1.500 m	1.500 m	0.305 m	4
4	54,15	1.800 m	1.800 m	0.355 m	2
5	73,81,151,153,194,196,216,218,238,240,263,265,338,346,	1.900 m	1.900 m	0.405 m	14
6	74,80,339,345	2.250 m	2.250 m	0.455 m	4
7	75,79,340,344	2.100 m	2.100 m	0.405 m	4
8	76,78,341,343	2.200 m	2.200 m	0.455 m	4
9	77,342	2.450 m	2.450 m	0.505 m	2
10	150,262	1.950 m	1.950 m	0.355 m	2
11	152,195,217,239,264	2.300 m	2.300 m	0.455 m	5
12	154,266	2.050 m	2.050 m	0.455 m	2

Table 4-16 - Isolated footing design

Figure 4-38 - Isolated footing section

(Annexure 12 – Structural Drawings)

4.11 Design of Building Services

4.11.1 The Importance of Building Services

Building services are systems installed in buildings to make them comfortable, functional, efficient and safe. They include fire protection, HVAC (heating, ventilation and air conditioning), lighting, plumbing, ICT (information and communication technology), and more.

Building Services Engineering plays a central role in the design of buildings. This is important not only in terms of overall strategy and standards to be achieved, but also in terms of effective engineering, weight, size, location and location of key equipment and devices.

Building Services Engineers influence building construction and can have a significant impact on building sustainability and energy needs Health and Welfare of occupants.

A new concept that has become common place in hospitals is to strongly promote health rather than simply treat disease. Design plays a very important role. Today we see that huge amounts of money are spent on the construction of new hospital structures for the health of people and the treatment of various diseases. Since hospital structures are planned only once in a lifetime, and major changes cannot be implemented later, future requirements, including all the factors, must be considered from the outset. The building infrastructure design must be attractive and functional and also meet the needs of patient care. That's why a properly planned building services system is necessary for the hospital building.

4.11.2 Regulations with relative regulatory bodies, resources, and acts

- The urban development authority planning and Building regulations 1986.
- Sri Lanka Government Gazettes (2021/7/8 – 2235/54)
- National Medical Regulatory Authority (acts no 08, 2015)
- Official Publications of ministry of health
- BS code 6465
- Health Technical Memorandum UK– 64
- Plumbing Engineering Design guide – IOP2002

Here we follow below guide lines and regulations of above regulatory bodies and institutions for our design and design calculations. From above parties.

4.11.3 Water Supply System

Design of water supply system and storage capacities

Potable water Consumption of the building

Total fully occupied - 415 persons

(255 patients, 60 Visitors, 15 Doctors, 45 Nurses, 30 Miner Staff and Admin staff, 10 Services and other staff)

Water usage (building) – 71,800 L

(From Plumbing Engineering Design guide)

255 patients -220L per bed	= 56100L
50 Visitors-45L per head	= 2250L
15 Doctors- 45 L per head	= 675L
45 Nurses- 45 L per head	= 2025L
30 Miner Staff and Services staff- 45 L per head	= 1350L
20 Admin and other staff- 45 L per head	= 900L
Other usage like washing and cleaning	= 8500L

Type of building	Storage per occupant (litres)
Hospitals, per staff on duty	45
Hostels	90
Hotels	135
Houses and flats	135
Offices with canteens	45
Offices without canteens	35
Restaurant (* per meal)	7
Schools, boarding	90
Schools, day	30

Table 4-17 – Storage of cold-water storage per occupant

We plan this to achieve this requirement for Overhead tank for 1/2day and water sump for 1 1/2days water demand of the hospital building. Main water distribution system is gravity type and overhead tank. So,

Total requirement = 72 m³ per Day

We plan to locate two separate overhead tanks for cold water supply at both side of the main building. And it makes easy pipe lying and as well as cost saving in piping.

Dimensions (internal) for one rectangular tank ($36\text{m}^3/2 = 18\text{m}^3$ each tank) = $3 \times 3 \times 2$
= 18 m^3

Required floor rate to fill the overhead tank = $18000 / (3\text{hrs} \times 3600)$

= 1.66 l/s

Pump size calculation for Sump,

$Ph(\text{kW}) = q \rho g h / (3.6 \times 106)$

= $q p / (3.6 \times 106)$ (1)

where

$Ph(\text{kW})$ = hydraulic power (kW)

q = flow (m^3/h)

ρ = density of fluid (kg/m^3)

g = acceleration of gravity (9.81 m/s^2)

h = differential head (m)

p = differential pressure (N/m^2 , Pa)

Valve -

Hydraulic Power: 0.33 (kW) 0.44 (hp)

Shaft Power: 0.55 (kW) 0.73 (hp)

There for we use 2 hp pump for each tank which is available in market.

We use 2hp pump for sump tank.

Pipe Size

From Plumbing Engineering Design Guide Graph 4

Flow rate = 1.66 l/s

Assume head loss in meters per meter run as 0.05 for higher accuracy.

Required minimum diameter of Supply pipe is 50mm

So, we select upper level size as a pipe size 63mm

Ground Sump Tank = $1.5 \text{ times } 18 \text{ m}^2 = 54 \text{ m}^3$

Cold water supply Pipe sizes, (design calculations given in Appendix)

- Main distribution pipe sizes = 63mm From Tank
- Main Supply pipe sizes = 63mm
- Secondary distribution pipe sizes = 50mm
- Block distribution pipe sizes = 32mm
- Internal distribution pipe sizes = 25mm and 20mm (See *Annexure 13*)

4.11.4 Waste water Disposal

A facility in a building that collects or conveys sewage through a drain pipe by gravity, to an on-site public sewer or septic tank is called an on-site wastewater treatment system. When designing sewage treatment for this three-story building, it is recommended to provide a two-story pipe network system. This system has two pipes. One pipe collects dirty soil and toilet waste, and the second pipe collects dirty water from, bathrooms, washing machines, rainwater, etc. The soil pipe is directly connected to the drain pipe and the pipe waste is connected through the catch chute. All traps used in this system are fully vented.

Loading Units of fittings,

Here we do design calculation for two types of Bath room blocks which have maximum LUs.

- Consider WC with 6L cistern - DU = 1.7 l/s
- Slab urinal per person - DU = 0.2 l/s
- Shower with plug - DU = 0.4 l/s
- Wash hand basin - DU = 0.3 l/s

Small Toilet and bath room Blocks (Visitor/Staff)

Fitting	Qty	Loading Unit	Total LU
For Gray water pipe			
Wash Basin	2	0.3	0.6
Sink	1	0.2	0.2
Shower	2	1.3	2.6
For Black water pipe			
Water closet	2	1.7	3.4

Table 4-18 – loading unit

Total Discharge -

- Gray water – 3.4 L/s
- Black Water – 3.4 L/s

Large Toilet and bath room Blocks (words)

Fitting	Qty	Loading Unit	Total LU
For Gray water pipe			
Wash Basin	3	0.3	0.9
Shower	3	1.3	3.9
Urinal	3	0.2	0.6
For Black water pipe			
Water closet	3	1.7	5.1

Table 4-19 – Loading unit (words)

Total Discharge -

- Gray water – 5.4 L/s
- Black Water – 5.1 L/s

There for,

Drainage Pipe Sizes, (design calculations given in Appendix)

- All Black water pipe line -110mm
- All Gray water pipe line – 110mm
- All waste individual lines from fittings – 50mm and 63mm
- Washing waste pipe line – 63mm

(See *Annexure 13 - Design Calculations for Plumbing and Waste Water Disposal*)

4.11.5 Septic tank and soakage pit design

Septic tank

A septic tank is an on-site, underground, small-scale sewage treatment plant that collects wastewater for decomposition activity by the action of bacteria. Wastewater is a collection of domestic, commercial, or industrial wastewater (mainly sewage).

These wastewaters cause environmental pollution such as disturbance of the marine environment, foul living conditions, pollution of land and surface waters, and many diseases. To overcome this waste water, it must be treated. sewage is not connected to the public sewage system, septic tanks are required to treat the sewage, and these septic tanks are equipment of the public or private sewage sector. It must be emptied (the tank is completely watertight and has a manhole for cleaning). Treated septic tank wastewater is still dirty. This means that only 60-70% of septic tank wastewater is treated. This impure water was then transferred to a soakage tank for further treatment.

Figure 4-39 - Double chamber septic tank

Figure 4-40 – Single chamber septic tank

(From Quantity of sewage produced= population X per capita)

Assuming usage = 415 persons

required capacity of tank = 37 m³

Assuming depth of tank = 2.7m

Assuming free board surface 0.3m.

Therefore, depth (d) = 3m

Therefore, a septic tank of size 7.4mX1.85mX3m

Note - A vent pipe of 75 mm diameter shall be provided extending outside the tank to a height sufficient to avoid odor nuisance. The vent pipe covered with a mosquito proof mesh at the top.

Soakage pit

Water slowly seeps into the ground. Septic tanks, lined with porous materials that provide basic support to prevent basements from collapsing, can also be used to separate and treat gray water.

Figure 4-41 – Soakage pit

Area ground water table - Not greater than 5m

We assume the percolation rate between 100- 125 mm/hr. according to past reports of near constructions.

According to the SLS 745 satisfied the criteria's mentioned for the soakage pit design. Such as,

- At least 50ft (15m) away from the nearest well or other drinking water source.
- At least 5 m away from the nearest building.
- A minimum distance from other soakage pits, either existing or proposed, within or outside the property shall be maintained as specified (20m distance due to the separated Grey water and black water system).
- The required effective area for 125 mm/hr. percolation rate is, 6.6 m² / m³ per day.
- The depth of the soakage pit shall be such that a minimum distance is maintained between the bottom of the pit and the highest seasonal groundwater table according to the 125mm/hr. percolation rate, is 3 m.

Black water generation = 24000L /day = 24 m³/day

Grey water generation= 48000 /day = 48 m³/day

One soakage pit used just for the black water conveyed through the septic tank (24 m³/day). And used two soakage pits for the grey water generation of 48 m³/day.

We do this, for cost controlling, due to high water table level and easiness of pipe laying.

- Required effective area of the soakage pit for black water = $12 \times 6.6 = 79.2 \text{ m}^2$
- Required effective area of the soakage pit for grey water = $24 \times 6.6 = 158.4 \text{ m}^2$
- Due to the depth of ground water table here, depth can be going up to 4m.

Effective area of one soakage pit = $(4\text{m} \times 4\text{m} \times 4\text{sides}) + (4\text{m} \times 4\text{m} \text{ bottom}) = 80 \text{ m}^2$
Number of soakage pits for black water = $79.2 \text{ m}^2 / 80 \text{ m}^2 = 1 \text{ pit}$

Number of soakage pits for grey water = $158.4 \text{ m}^2 / 80 \text{ m}^2 = 2 \text{ pits}$

Soakage pits provided with a permanent cover that prevents the ingress of surface water, insects and rodents into the pit. The cover can withstand the imposed loads applied in operational periods. (See *Annexure 14 - Design Calculations of Septic Tank and Soakage Pit*)

4.11.6 Electrical Supply

An electric system consists of all of the elements needed to distribute electrical power, including overhead and underground lines, fittings and other equipment. The electric system in a small industrial unit will normally be powered by a three-phase supply.

This project also we need three-phase power supply.

Lighting system

Hospital lighting is an important part of hospital construction and management. It plays a key role in delivering healthcare and therapeutic outcomes, patient rehabilitation and physician-patient relationships, and hospital operations management and cost control. However, no attention has been paid to this in the process of hospital construction and actual operation. The reason is, firstly, there is little hospital construction side of the role of lighting, so the academic research on hospital lighting is relatively small. On the other hand, the lighting industry's understanding of hospital lighting needs is not well received in the market. The selection of professional lighting fixtures is relatively small.

Primary Purpose of Hospital Lighting

we know that good lighting promotes,

- Safety for those who use a building.
- Work and other activities conveniently carried out in buildings.
- Create a comfortable environment that benefits the residents.
- Creates a sense of well-being.

The main purpose of hospital lighting is to introduce

- Daylighting scenarios in office buildings.
- Improving employee health and productivity.

For This Building We are planned to use LED Panel Lights as follows,

Fittings A

- 18W LED Panel Day Light/Warm White
- Color Temperature: 3000/6500k
- Input Voltage: 200-240V
- PF: 0.9
- Ra: >80
- Stable Lumen: 1400 Lm
- Size (mm): 195mm x 195mm x 16mm
- Working Temp: -20-40 C
- Life Time: 50,000Hrs
- Body Material: PC
- Beam Angle: 120°
- Hole Size: 175mm
- No Mercury
- Not Dimmable
- Recyclable

Figure 4-42 – Panel light - Fitting A

Fittings B

- 12W LED Eco Panel Day Light/ Warm White
- Color Temperature: 3000/6500k
- PF: 0.5
- Ra: >80
- Stable Lumen: 840lm
- Working Temp: -20-40 C
- Life Time: 50,000 Hrs.
- Body Material: PC
- Beam Angle: 120°
- Hole Size: 160mm

- No Mercury
- Not Dimmable
- Recyclable

Figure 4-43 - Panel light - Fitting A

Lighting Design

A simple, basic approach to calculating lighting needs is to divide the total light need of a space by the light output (lumens) from a single lamp. This is the basic approach for the average room.

Equation for calculate, No of Light fitting required - >

No of light fittings = $\frac{\text{Area} \times \text{Illumination Level (Lux)}}{\text{Lumen per fitting} \times \text{Utilization Factor} \times \text{Maintenance Factor}}$

Lumen per fitting x Utilization Factor x Maintenance Factor

Where,

Lux. Level = as per Regulation (see table below)

Utilization factor (UF) = 0.8

Maintenance factor (MF) = 0.65

Lumen/ fitting

18W = 1400 lm

12W = 840 lm

(See *Annexure 15 - Design Calculations Electrical*)

Typical electricity usage for hospital buildings is as follows,

- Medical Equipment
- Defibrillators

- Anesthesia Machines
- Patient Monitors
- Ventilators
- Sterilizers
- X-Ray Machines
- EKG/ECG Machines
- Ultrasounds
- Electrosurgical Units

Equipment for General use and Office work

- Computers
- Photo copy machine/Scanner
- TV
- Sound system
- CCTV

Kitchen, Sanitary and Cleaning Equipment

- Refrigerators
- Cooling box
- Heaters
- Electrical oven
- Washing machine
- Driers
- Irons
- Pressure washers

Electrical Equipment for Other Building Services

- Air Conditioners
- Fire System
- Lift/Elevators
- Pumps

Electricity demand calculations

Other Assumptions and Usages

- We use 48-inch ceiling fan runs on 65 watts
- All AC machines are Inverter types
- 24000 BTU (2 ton) air conditioner uses around 2000 watts,
- 36000 BTU (3 ton) AC unit uses around 3000 watts.
- Power for socket outlet - 200W
- Power for Water pump - 2000W
- Power for fire pump - 2000W
- Power for passenger lift - 20KW
- Total Electrical Medical Equipment Demand is – 240 KW

Total lighting fittings capacity for the building = 746527W = 74.5 kW
(12W and 18W LED)

Total 13A Schocket Outlet capacity for the building = 737 x 200 = 147.4 kW Power

Total industrial Schocket Outlet capacity for the building = 77 x 500 (avg) = 38.5 kW Power

Fan Points = 117 x 75 = 8.77 Kw

Requirement for Air Conditioning

24000 BTU = 42 x 2000 = 84 kW

36000 BTU = 4 x 3000 = 12 kW

Pump = 3 x 2000 = 6KW

Passenger lift = 20KW

Total Electrical Medical Equipment/services Demand = 240 KW

Total electrical demand of building (P) = 631.2 KW = 632Kw

$$\text{Current (A) – 3 phase} = \frac{P \times \text{Diversity factor}}{\sqrt{3} \times \text{Voltage} \times \text{Power factor}}$$

$$\text{Current (A) – 3 phase} = \frac{632 \times 1000 \times 0.60}{\sqrt{3} \times 400 \times 0.80} = 684.9 \text{ A}$$

Where,

Voltage – 400

Diversity factor -60%

Power factor – 0.8

MCB Calculation

$$\text{Current (A)} = \frac{P}{\sqrt{3} \times \text{Voltage} \times \text{Power factor}}$$

Unit	Watts per unit	Three Phase AC current (V)	Power factor	Current (A)	MCB (TYPE C)
Water pump	2	400	0.8	3.6	10A
Fire pump	2	400	0.8	3.6	10A
Passenger lift	20	400	0.8	36.1	63A
Fan	75	400	0.8	0.13	6A
AC Unit	2	400	0.8	3.6	16A
AC Unit	3	400	0.8	5.4	16A

Figure 4-44 – MCB selection

From the above calculations we obtained the following results and conclusions,

- We have to provide bulk power supply by individual transformer belongs to the site.
- Total power demand will be divided into following parts
 - Lighting demand – with 100mA RCD
 - Power demand – With 30mA RCD
- We have to provide capacitor bank. It helps to reduce power loss.
- It is necessary to provide Generator for this, especially for critical areas with ATS panel.
- Generally, we use MCB as follows,
 - Lighting – 10A (type C)
 - Socket outlet- 16A (type)

(See Annexure 15 - Design Calculations Electrical)

4.11.7 Staircase

A staircase is a set of steps leading from one floor of a building to another, usually inside a building. Here we fabricate U Shaped Stairs for the building by using structural Steels. Because of the building structure is almost steel and it is easy and practical to construct steel staircase here.

Comparison	Concrete Stairs	Steel Stairs	Best choice
Strength & Durability	★ ★ ★	★ ★ ★ ★	Steel Stairs
Aesthetics / Design	★ ★	★ ★ ★ ★	Steel Stairs
Cladding	★ ★	★ ★ ★ ★	Steel Stairs
Maintenance	★ ★ ★ ★	★ ★ ★ ★	Steel Stairs
Cost	★ ★ ★	★ ★ ★ ★	Steel Stairs
Sustainability	★ ★ ★	★ ★ ★ ★	Steel Stairs

Table 4-20 – selection of staircase type

There for this type of public building, steel stair is most suitable and erecting also easy and quick.

Figure 4-45 – staircase detail

According to the regulation of staircase, General requirements are,

SCHEDULE III

(Regulation 44)

Form "K"

STAIR CASES

Type 1	Width of staire centimeters 2	Minimum Head Room meters 3	Riser Centimeters 4	Tread Centimeters 5
Internal stairs serving one upper floor only	75	2.0	19	22.5
stairs building used as place of public assembly & public building	105	2.1	17.5	22.5
All other types	90	2.1	17.5	22.5

Figure 4-46 – General Regulations - staircase

Design calculations

(BS 5395-3:1985)

size of riser, -

Riser Size = 7" (inch)

Nos. of Riser = Clear level difference between two floors / Size of Riser

$$= 13'-0" / 7"$$

= 22 nos. = (12 for first flight and 10 for second flight) Now, can calculate the size of thread,

Number of threads on single flight = Nos. of Rising of single flight – 1

$$= 12 - 1 = 11 \text{ nos.}$$

$$= 10 - 1 = 9 \text{ Nos.}$$

The thread is 12" width.

There is a landing after 12 steps.

4.11.8 Elevators design

Important design considerations for choosing an elevator for a project are the number of floors, building height, number of people carried, required passenger waiting time, and frequency of use. The design, installation, and use of elevator systems are typically based on a variety of international, national, statewide, and local standards. Most buildings typically require multiple passenger elevators to handle the traffic. Here elevators are designed according to certain rules and regulations from previous projects.

Hospital elevators must be dimensioned to accommodate at least one stretcher and attendant. Hospital elevator cabins must comply with health-related sanitary regulations and must take antimicrobial precautions. The interior of hospital elevators, also called patient elevators, is rust-proofed and the lighting is kept at a level that does not disturb patients. Hospital elevator cars have lower buttons and wider doors than other types of elevators. Be prepared for any power outage situation.

Hospital lifts are preferred as semi-automatic, fully automatic or hydraulic lifts.

Important! Hospital elevators should be overhauled by regular and general elevator maintenance performed by a licensed elevator maintenance company.

The corresponding calculation is shown below.

Elevator Calculations

Calculating the passenger lift requirement

Assumptions:

A passenger handled in 5 minutes is 7%. Lift speed: 1.6 m/s

Expected number of occupants per Both floors is = 78

5% of 255 patients	= 13
50% of 60 Visitors	= 30
33% of 15 Doctors	= 5
33% of 45 Nurses	= 15
33% of 30 Miner Staff and Admin staff	= 10
50% of 10 Services and other staff	= 5

Travel Height of the building = 26.5 ft = 11 m

Passengers handled in 5 minutes = $78 \times 10\% = 7.8$
= consider as 8

So, we use 5 no's lifts for the building.

But lift size should be good enough for one stretcher and attendant. So generally, without stretcher it can use for 16 attendants. Because we have to design it suitable detention for fit with stretcher. (See *Annexure 16 - Design Calculations - Elevator*)

4.11.9 Design of Fire Fighting System

A system of equipment used to prevent, extinguish, locate, or stop a fire in an enclosed space. Automatic fire extinguishing systems are installed in buildings and premises where the risk of fire is relatively high. A distinction is made between systems that are automatically activated and operate according to a predetermined program and systems that are activated by an operator, the former being called automatic fire protection systems and the latter fire protection units. The automatic fire extinguishing system includes sensors capable of detecting combustion,

Alarm signaling devices, fire extinguishing devices, starting and stopping devices, and supplies of extinguishing media. In some cases, it includes controls to protect the production process. Atomizers, foam generators, and tubular nozzles form and direct jets of liquid, foam, powder, or gas extinguishing agents. Extinguishing media is supplied to the system from a central source. Water supply or supply from independent or combined sources.

Firefighting systems are perhaps the most important appliances, as they are intended to protect life and property strictly in that order. This building consists of following main parts

- fire extinguisher unit
- Fire Detection system and alarm system
- Fire hose reel and large store of water in tanks (fire sump)

A fire extinguisher is a container of extinguishing media such as water or chemicals. Designed to extinguish small fires, not large ones. Fire extinguishers are labeled based on the fact that the fire for which they are intended to be used originates from wood or cloth, flammable liquids, electrical or metal sources. The wrong type of extinguisher in a fire can significantly aggravate a fire. Using a fire extinguisher will keep the fire contained and not spread. Fire extinguishers are readily available.

Detail of fire extinguisher

 Type Extinguisher Type	Class A	Class B	Class C	Class D	Electrical	Class F	Businesses that may need this type of Extinguisher
	Organic Materials (e.g Paper & Coal)	Flammable Liquids (e.g Petrol & Paint)	Flammable Gases (e.g Butane & Methane)	Flammable Metals (e.g Lithium & Magnesium)	Electrical Equipment (e.g Computers & Servers)	Cooking Oils (e.g Olive Oil & Fat)	
Water	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	- Schools - Hospitals - Offices - Shops
Foam	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	- Apartments - Hospitals - Offices - Shops
Dry Powder	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	- Garages - Welding - Boiler Rooms - LPG Plants
CO2	✗	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗	- Server Rooms - Offices
Wet Chemical	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	- Kitchens - Canteens

Figure 4-47 – Fire Extinguisher

Fire Alarm System

A fire alarm system has a number of devices working together to detect and alert people through visual and audible devices when smoke, fire, carbon monoxide, or other emergencies occur. Alarms are either motorized bells or wall-mountable sounders or horns.

A fire alarm system has two types. The main difference between the two is that conventional systems only show the zone in which a device was activated, whereas an addressable fire detection system can determine exactly which device has been activated.

Fire detectors

Fire detectors identify one or more products or phenomena caused by fire, such as smoke, heat, ultraviolet light, or gas. At home, smoke detectors are often standalone devices. In non-residential buildings, fire detection usually takes the form of fire alarm systems. Here, the building uses a smoke alarm system.

They are installed in locations such as:

all medical units, entrance areas, corridors, parking lots, machine rooms, fan and electrical rooms, warehouses and stores, duct areas near stairs to upper floors, etc.

According to BS 5839-1, smoke detectors individually cover a radius of 7.5m, but these radii must overlap to avoid "blind spots". Therefore, usually it is estimated at 80 m²).

Figure 4-48 – Fire Alarm System

Fire Hose Reel Design

Building occupants are provided with a fire hose reel to perform initial strike actions against fires. As part of a fire protection system, it provides occupants with unrestricted access to water to extinguish fire and protect against radiant heat. However, fire protection experts point to the following benefits of fire hose reels:

- Spray from a fire hose reel can be used to protect against radiant heat.
- Fire hose reels can put out up to 10 times more fire than a fire extinguisher.

Hose reels can be placed on each tier, taking into consideration the length of the hose. Hose reels should be long enough to go anywhere on each floor. The main concern is therefore the length of the hose reel and the water supply system to the hose reel. However, the location of fire hose reels is regulated by BS 5306-1:2006 for on-site firefighting equipment and firefighting equipment.

Here we plan 6 hose reel use for this (2 for each floor). Generally, it located at near common lobby or passage area. Because then we can use it easy and we can cover maximum area for firefighting.

Figure 4-49 – Fire hose reel

Here we do sum assumption from expert who already done this type of works.

No. Of people in the building = 415 capita demand = 72 m³ liters per day

Ground sump size = 54 m³

For firefighting 54 m³ / 3 = 18 m³

Assuming,

45min have to operate until fire brigade comes.

Rate - 0.5 L/s

Capacity need = 60 x 60 x 5 x 0.5 = 9000 L

So, storage is good enough.

The theoretical pump power,

- Hydraulic Power: 0.04 (kW) 0.5 (hp)
- Shaft Power: 0.07 (kW) 0.9 (hp)

we can use 1.5 hp pumps.

(See Annexure 17 - Design Calculations of firefighting system)

Here we construct separate but interconnect fire sump tank with normal sump for emergency firefighting. We interconnect this to main water sump, because firefighting is not a day today activity and water will get dirty when we not use it and after long storage time.

4.11.10 Air conditioning

An air conditioning system is a system or machine that processes air in a defined, normally closed room through a refrigeration circuit where warm air is removed and replaced by cold air. In construction, a complete heating, ventilation, and air conditioning system is called HVAC.

An air conditioning system generally consists of five mechanical components:

- Compressor.
- Fan.
- Condenser Coil (Hot)
- Evaporator Coil (Cool)
- Chemical Refrigerant

Figure 4-50 – working of air conditioner

There are eight main types of air conditioning equipment out there in the market. Each type of air conditioner is designed for a certain space & fulfills a certain purpose. The different AC types are as follows:

- Central Air Conditioner
- Ductless Split (wall mount and ceiling mount)
- Window Air Conditioner
- Portable Air Conditioner
- Floor Mounted AC
- Hybrid / Dual Fuel Air Conditioner
- Smart Air Conditioner
- Geothermal Air Conditioner

In this project we are use only Split type air conditions only. A wall air conditioner or split system air conditioner consists of two different units. indoor unit and outdoor unit. Indoor units are wall mounted and outdoor units are usually floor or wall mounted. The two units are connected by a pipe that runs through the wall. The two units work together to cool the air in building and expel warm air and moisture efficiently. Indoor units are usually very quiet, while outdoor units tend to be loud when running.

A wall air conditioner draws in room air. It passes through the condenser and is cooled thanks to the refrigerant. A refrigerant used in many refrigeration products. Cold air is pushed back into the room, and hot air and moisture are expelled from the outdoor unit.

It is important to have enough space around the wall unit so that air can move in and out easily. Installing a wall-mounted air conditioner is the job of a professional engineer.

Cassette units' function like wall-mounted split-system units, except that the cassette is recessed or mounted in the ceiling instead of the wall.

The indoor unit itself fits snugly against the ceiling and he of the unit distributes the conditioned air to two, three or four sides.

The outdoor unit of the cassette air conditioner is installed outdoors in the same way as the conventional wall-mounted division method.

As a result of the COVID-19 pandemic, indoor air quality and ventilation systems are more important than ever from a public health perspective.

Infected and healthy people are in the same place in some hospitals, increasing the risk of infection from coronavirus transmission. Therefore, wards with COVID-19 patients

should be well ventilated to prevent the spread of disease and protect both patients and staff.

It is important to understand that a properly managed commercial ventilation system may not always protect building occupants from infection. However, proper installation and use of ventilation systems can control air distribution and reduce airborne diseases.

This project of ours is primarily aimed at treating corona infected patients. Since the spread of germs in infectious disease treatment centers like this is very fast and very dangerous, ventilation is done through natural ventilation in all the places except the necessary places.

Especially in tropical ecosystems, because the spread of the disease happens very fast, having such places air-conditioned is a very dangerous situation and it affects the hospital staff.

- Followings are the general regulations and rules what we going to use when calculating the capacity of Air conditions.
- The entire selected area has same BTU requirement generally in electrical equipment.
- Calculation table shows all variable according to previous practice and codes
- If there are more than two people living in the area, should add 750 BTU each person.
- When considering electrical appliances person will use an equipment and its power is 200 watts, and it operates 16 hrs. per day.
- All other conditions are as mentioned in calculation table

After considering such matters, we have decided to install air conditioners only in the following places. (design calculations given in Appendix)

Category 01

For following area will not provide natural ventilations or window openings. There for we have to assume no heating effects from surround areas and maximum persons will use the location is 4.

- Server Room
- Network Room

- Intercom Room
- ICT Room
- CCTV Room
- Pharmacy

Calculated BTU for above category is 47,555 BTU (max)

There for we used 2 Nos. of 24000 BTU Air conditions for each above area.

Category 02

For following location have medical equipment and as well as lights more than above.

Also, we assume 4 people will use the area in one time.

- Laboratory
- Pharmaceutical Store
- Medical equipment store
- Medicine store

Calculated BTU for above category is 79427 BTU (max), There for we used 2 Nos. of 24000 BTU Air conditions and 36000BTU Air conditions above areas.

Category 03

For following location have medical equipment and as well as lights more than above.

Also, we assume 25 persons will use the area in one time.

- ICU
- Theater
- Radiology Unit

Calculated BTU for above category is 296400 BTU (max).

There for

we used 12 Nos. of 24000 BTU Air conditions for ICU

we used 6 Nos. of 24000 BTU Air conditions for Theater

we used 4 Nos. of 24000 BTU Air conditions for Theater

See (*Annexure 18 - Design calculations of Air Conditioning System*)

(*Annexure 19 – Services Drawings*)

4.12 Analysis with GREENSL Rating System for New Construction V.2.1

4.12.1 General

Mankind has a great responsibility for climate changes and damages to the environment due to the increasing population and related economic activities, there is a tendency to increase the global temperature in a very negative way, and at the same time, the environment and the existence of all living beings have been threatened by the negative effects. Human is already suffering the negative results of their activities that are harmful to the environment. Therefore, it is extremely important to make economic development an environmentally friendly sustainable development.

In the distant past, mankind was inspired to build dwellings to avoid the various problems and difficulties in the natural environment that hindered its existence, and later it was inspired to use them not only for comfort and safety but also as a tool to display one's wealth and ability. In this process, natural resources were used indiscriminately and most of the building that were created were without sunlight and ventilation instead of using artificial light, air conditioning and heat control methods. As a result of that many environmental, economic and technical problems have been occurring.

Today, with the rapid population growth in the world, natural resources such as stone, sand and gravel are being used unlimitedly for the construction of houses and buildings. As a result, the lifetime of buildings contribution to global CO₂ emission is close to 40% and is the largest single contributor to global warming. It is projected that one ton of cement production contributes approximately one ton of CO₂ emissions. When the total energy use is taken into account, the building sector is responsible for more than one-third. Furthermore, it accounts for about 12% of water use and 40% of waste that ends up in landfills and water resources. Therefore, we should take necessary action to reduce harmful scenarios to the environment and go forward with eco-friendly construction methods. Also, it is our responsibility to protect the resources for the use of future generation.

4.12.1.1 Design Consideration

Listed below are the main considerations when designing the building to achieve the GREEN SL Rating System for Built Environment Version 2.1 which align with 8 main categories. Namely, (GBCSL, 2022)

1. Management (MN) - 04 Points
2. Sustainable Sites (SS) - 25 Points
3. Water Efficiency (WE) -14 Points
4. Energy and Atmosphere (EA) - 22 Points
5. Material and Resources (MR) - 14 Points
6. Indoor Environmental Quality (EQ) - 13 Points
7. Innovation and Design Process (ID) - 04 Points
8. Social and Cultural Awareness (SC) - 04 Points

100 Points

The certification from the GREEN SL Rating System for Built Environment be awarded according to the following scales;

40 – 49 = Certified

50 – 59 = Silver

60 – 69 = Gold

70 – 100 = Platinum

Certification Process

1. Register project at GBCSL
2. Appoint a GREEN SL Accredited Professionals
3. Carry out Pre-Assessment with the appointed GREEN SL Accredited Professionals
4. Site Visits
5. Final evaluation report and presentation
6. Award of the certification

4.12.2 Analysis with Green Rating System for Design Features

Adapted green features as follows,

1. Management
 - GBCSL Accredited professionals attending at 50% of all design meetings and at least 75% of all building services meetings throughout the project.
 - Preparing a building commissioning plan.
 - Preparing a building users' guide.
 - Preparing a building information modeling.
 - Green Facility manager involve in the construction stage and obtaining a progress report
 - Consultant ecologist involve in the design stage and obtaining a report.
 - Preparing an Environment Management plan.

2. Sustainable Sites
 - Selected site doesn't affect to the environmental hazards, not disturbing to the natural habitats and also not a prime agricultural land.
 - Designing the land with the landscape design.
 - Provide adequate parking spaces according to the TIA
 - Provide vertical vegetation on the inside of the boundary walls and roadside.
 - Maximize the infiltration by reducing impervious cover and landscape with native planting.
 - Proposed more than 50% area of the roof top to install the solar system for generate electricity power.
 - The building has been designed to maximize natural light penetration through windows, manually switch off lights, and introduce LED lighting.

3. Water Efficiency
 - Installing tube well. (100% landscaping and irrigation can be done by tube well water)
 - Use of water efficient water closet and can be reduce indoor water usage.

4. Energy and Atmosphere
 - The building project is complied with ASHRAE/IESNA standards and sustainable energy authority standards.
 - Proposed energy saving methods to optimize the design.
 - Hospital building electrical supply done by the solar panel system (Net-Metering System)
 - Well qualified experienced consultant team member conducts review to achieve building's optimized use.
 - Consultant need to hire a person as the energy auditor, a person who have the "Energy Manager" certified from the Sustainable Energy Authority of Sri Lanka.
5. Material and Resources
 - Separation of solid waste done by at the site. Colored and labelled bins used to collect separated waste. Handover those separated waste to municipal waste collection daily.
 - More than 50% of the material that have been used for the building are manufactured locally (Portland cement – Puttalam, Fly ash bricks – Puttalam)
 - 100% of the timber used in the building is certified timber in accordance with the Department of Forest Conservation and State Timber Cooperation.
 - According to the IEE contractor should manage the construction waste an environmental sensitive manner.
6. Indoor Environmental Quality
 - 2m height (Vertical vegetated) boundary wall used for the project design to cover the building.
 - Common area CO2 level monitoring equipment fixed to monitor the levels.
 - Louvers supply the fresh air to the common lobby areas for implement the cross ventilation.
 - Low VOC emitting paints used for the building.
 - Door closer provide for each and every door of the building.
 - Transparent glasses used for the windows to get outside view comfortably and to penetrate the maximum daylight to the inside the building.

7. Innovation and Design Process

Most common areas (Lift lobbies, staircases) occupied light sensors used to turn on and off lights.

8. Social and Cultural Awareness

- Garden landscaped area provides as a rest area for the visitors.
- The design fully complies with the fire regulation and local authority regulations.
- All areas of the building consist of appropriately sized doorways and ramps for accessibility to persons with disabilities and the elderly.

The following table summarized the green points claimed by the apartment building through the project design with accordance to criteria of Green Rating System for New Construction V.2.1, 2022. See (*Annexure 20 - IDH Hospital Building Green Rating System for Built Environment Report.*)

Description	Points Available	Points Claimed
1.0 Management	4	4
2.0 Sustainable Sites	25	21
3.0 Water Efficiency	14	4
4.0 Energy and Atmosphere	22	16
5.0 Materials and Resources	14	9
6.0 Indoor Environmental Quality	13	10
7.0 Innovation and Design Process	4	0
8.0 Social and Cultural Awareness	4	4
Total	100	69

Table 4-21 - Green Rating System Obtained points for the Proposed Design

According to the expected points (69 points) Gold certificate can be achieved for the proposed Hospital building Kotikawatta, Mulleriyawa from the GBCSL. According to the above details Hospital building can recommended as an eco-friendly, productive and economical building project. Therefore, this project will motivate the construction industry to execute projects by adapting green concepts.

4.13 Bill of Quantities

SUMMARY

ITEM	DESCRIPTION	AMOUNT
A	PRELIMINARIES	580,000.00
B	EARTH WORK	5,702,820.00
C	CONCRETE	42,929,914.00
D	FORMWORK	13,184,900.00
E	REINFORCEMENT	10,410,768.00
E	STRUCTURAL STEEL	60,916,800.00
F	MASONRY WORK	20,989,440.00
G	ROOF AND ROOF PLUMBING	39,070,519.80
H	DOORS & WINDOWS	27,059,800.00
I	FLOOR, WALL & CEILING FINISHES	71,190,584.00
J	PAINTING	6,145,187.00
K	INTERNAL PLUMBING	8,140,524.00
L	METAL WORK	3,050,560.00
N	ELECTRICAL WORK	39,599,400.00
O	AIRCONDITION INSTALLATION	54,045,000.00
P	FIRE SAFTYUBIT INSTALLATION	14,743,000.00
	TOTAL (Excluding VAT)	<u><u>417,759,216.80</u></u>

Table 4-22 - BOQ Grand Summary

See (Annexure 21 – Detailed BOQ)

CHAPTER 5 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

There were Deadly Pandemics in world history such as Black Death, Spanish Flu, SARS, MERS, EBOLA and the recent Pandemic – COVID 19 accounts for Over 6 Mn. Deaths worldwide Over 16,000 deaths in Sri Lanka. Rapidly increased island-wide confirmed cases and active cases surpassed the testing capacity and capacity of general hospitals. Medical staff and general patients in hospitals were in a huge threat. Providing specialized infrastructure to treat infected patients can encourage the medical staff by creating them a safe working environment and by maximizing the rate of healing it is possible to overcome the pandemic situation of the country in health, social and economic aspects. And it is very important to make the health sector ready for the unexpected pandemic situations in future. Accordingly, a specialized hospital for infectious diseases was designed in a bare land of 4.5 acres belongs to MOH in the existing IDH hospital premises in Kotikawatta, Mulleriyawa.

Three Alternative designs were done with different main building shapes and concepts and evaluated those three alternatives in social and health feasibility, technical feasibility, financial feasibility and environmental feasibility. Social and health feasibility study was done with expert judgement with panel of doctors and decision matrix method was followed to evaluate decisions and found alternative 02 (H shaped G+2 building) is the most social and health feasible option. Technical feasibility study was done with a panel of engineers and decisions were evaluated by decision matrix analysis and found alternative 02 (H shaped G+2 building) is the most technically feasible option and SWOT Analysis was done and found steel framed structure is the best option. Discounting investment decision techniques were applied assuming this hospital as a private hospital and found that alternative 02 (H shaped G+2 building) is the best investment decision and most importantly the lowest initial cost option which is the main consideration in public project. And also, alternative 02 is the best environmentally feasible option when considering the most critical criteria of health care waste generation, it generates least amount of waste. So alternative 02 (H shaped G+2 building) was selected from a comprehensive feasibility study as the most viable option. To check weather this project has any harmful impacts on the sensitive environment IEE was done. And TIA was done to identify impact on traffic.

This project was designed with architecturally separated zones and architectural features to minimize the spread of virus. Contaminated and decontaminated zones were identified and separated those zones with precisely planned transition zones. Also adheres to UDA regulations.

In the preliminary design stage structural layout was planned using thumb rules to match with the architectural design and then structural design and analysis was done. Superstructure was designed and analyzed using the STAAD. Pro V8i SS6 Software and All the structural components were designed manually and detailed using AutoCAD. After soil investigation it was found that the soil bearing capacity is adequate and isolated footing shallow foundation type is enough. Using the base reaction values of STAAD. Pro V8i SS6 Software, STAAD. Foundation V8i Software was used to design the isolated footings and also manual detail design was done.

Construction is of high economic or social significance and there can be impacts on the environment. So sustainable development is considered as a way for the construction industry to move forward protecting the environment. So, here we can achieve the green rating points of 69 for the IDH Hospital project design adapting GREENSL Rating System for New Construction V.2.1.

We would like to recommend STAAD. Pro V8i SS6 Software for steel building design because it is a user-friendly software and after the super structure designs there are plugins provided to design the substructure and for the design of connections such as RAM Connection and IDEA Statica. We have used Euro cods for the design and there are lot of codes incorporated in this software. There are auto generate options when defining wind loads. And optimization can be done using the utility check option. Manual design also suggest that the software design is accurate. The design using the software gave an optimized economized design and saves lots of time and minimized human errors of the designer.

In this design project we have neglected the earthquake loads because Sri Lanka is free from that risk but in future there can be a risk as per recent investigations. it is possible to follow similar seismic codes such as such as IS 1893-1: 2002 and AS 1170.4: 2007 and it is recommended to establish a national code for seismic loads considering future probabilities of earthquake risk.

Historically there were infectious disease pandemic events happened but the probability of that event is low. It is important to get ready for a pandemic situation and these kinds of specialized hospitals are recommended to establish and use as a general hospital which can be a specialized hospital in a pandemic situation.

The green concept has earned wider awareness from construction practitioners worldwide with the growing alertness of environmental protection. Applying sustainable building construction practices has been recommended as a way of minimizing the impact on the environment while achieving economic and social targets. proposed IDH hospital design can be recommended as an eco-friendly project based on green building rating of GBCSL. Therefore, this project will inspire the construction industry to execute projects by adapting green building concepts.

CHAPTER 6

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CHAPTER 7
ANNEXURE

Annexure 01 - Alternative 01

SITE PLAN NO - 01

PROJECT LOCATION
 WESTON PROVINCE
 COLOMBO DISTRICT
 MULLERIWA

**PROPOSED COVID
 HOSPITAL FOR
 INSECTICIDE
 DISSIPATION
 HOSPITAL AT
 MULLERIWA**

NOTE:

DATE	DISCRPTION	REV

DRAWN BY	H.M.W.G.C.G.WATHTHEGEDARA
DATE	2022-01-25
SIZE	A1

SCALE 1:1000
 118

SCALE 1:1000

GROUND FLOOR PLAN

SCALE 1:500

PROJECT LOCATION

WESTON PROVINCE
COLOMBO DISTRICT
MULLERIAWA

PROPOSED COVID
HOSPITAL FOR
INSECTICIDE
DISSIPATION
HOSPITAL AT
MULLERIAWA

NOTE:

DATE	DISCRPTION	REV

DRAWN BY	H.M.W.G.C.G.WATHTHEGEDARA
DATE	2022-01-25
SIZE	A1

SCALE 1:500

FIRST FLOOR PLAN
SCALE 1:500

PROJECT LOCATION

WESTON PROVINCE
COLOMBO DISTRICT
MULLERIAWA

PROPOSED COVID
HOSPITAL FOR
INSECTED
DISSISES
HOSPITAL AT
MULLERIAWA

NOTE:

DATE	DISRIPTION	REV

DRAWN BY	H.M.W.G.C.G.WATHTHEGEDARA
DATE	2022-01-25
SIZE	A1

SCALE 1:500

Annexure 02 - Alternative 02

Existing IDH Hospital Premises

Internal Road of existing IDH Hospital

Boundary wall & tree/shrub cover

Existing Hospital Entrance to Mandavila Rd.

Waste Management Zone

Public parking

Drivers Area

Ambulance parking

Ambulance Road way

B231 - Mandavila Road

Colombo

SITE LAYOUT PLAN

SCALE - 1:450

- Legend :
1. C.L.F - Chain Link Fence (To separate Zones)
 2. S.R - Security Room
 3. S.T - Septic Tank
 4. W.W.P - Waste water pit
 5. B.L - Building Line

Notes :

1. All dimensions are in meters.

Client Name : Ministry of Health

Design of New Quarantine Hospital for Infectious Diseases (IDH) in Kotikawatta, Mulleriyawa, Sri Lanka.

Drawn by : L.G.S. De Silva Date - 26/10/2021

MOH/IDH/ARCH/LAYOUT/A2/01

Scale - 1:450

GROUND FLOOR - BUILDING SPACE LAYOUT PLAN
SCALE - 1:250

FIRST & SECOND FLOOR - BUILDING SPACE LAYOUT PLAN
SCALE - 1:250

- NOTES :
1. Second Floor is the male ward.
 2. Third Floor is the Female ward.
 3. Third Floor arrangement is similar to second floor except Theater area is changing to a Labour room in third floor
 4. Transition zones are provided to separate Contaminated zones and Decontaminated zones

Client Name : Ministry of Health

**Design of New Quarantine Hospital
for Infectious Diseases (IDH)
in Kotikawatta, Mulleriyawa, Sri Lanka.**

Drawn by : L.G.S. De Silva Date - 27/10/2021

MOH/IDH/ARCH/LAYOUT/A2/02

Scale - 1:250

**BASIC LAYOUT PLAN
GROUND FLOOR**

DRAWING TITLE :- PROPOSED BASIC LAYOUT PLAN FOR COVID HOSPITAL PROJECT at MULLERIYAWA
DRG . NO :- 01
FLOOR AREA :- APPROXIMATE FLOOR AREA OF MAIN BUILDING - 25000 SQFT
DRAWN BY- S.D.T.D. DASANAYAKA

DRAWING TITLE :-
PROPOSED DETAIL LAYOUT PLAN FOR COVID
HOSPITAL PROJECT at MULLERIYAWA

DRG . NO :- 02

**APROXIMATE FLOOR AREA OF MAIN BUILDING -
25000 SQFT**

**DRAWN BY-
S.D.T.D. DASANAYAKA**

**DETAIL LAYOUT PLAN
GROUND FLOOR**

Annexure 04 - Initial Cost & Discounting Investment Decision Calculation Sheet

Project Initial cost

Criteria	Alternative 01	Alternative 02	Alternative 03
Total Floor Area of a Floor of Main Building (sqm)	3,200	2,000	2,400
Total Floor Area of Three Floors of Main Building (sqm)	9,600	6,000	7,200
Approximate Construction Cost (LKR per sqm) (By considering cost per Sq.F is LKR 9,000)	96,840	96,840	96,840
Approximate Total Construction Cost of main building (LKR)	929,664,000	581,040,000	697,248,000
Area of the hospital premises other than the main building	15,010	16,210	15,810
Approximate cost for Construction of subordinate buildings, other services, Internal road, parking & landscaping. (By considering cost per sq.m is LKR 3000)	45,030,000	48,630,000	47,430,000
Contingencies (10% of total construction cost) (LKR)	97,469,400	62,967,000	74,467,800
Approximate Total Project Construction Cost (LKR)	1,072,163,400	692,637,000	819,145,800
Approximate Total Project Construction Cost (LKR Billion)	1.07	0.69	0.82

	Alternative 01	Alternative 02	Alternative 03
normal beds in observation ward	200	—	80
ventilator beds in critical wards	200	240	200
ICU beds	10	15	10
Total beds	410	255	290

Asumption

- normal bed in observation ward - 4,000 Rs/bed/day
- ventilator bed in critical wards - 12,000 Rs/bed/day
- ICU bed - 25,000 Rs/bed/day

Revenue from normal beds in observation ward per day	800,000.00	—	320,000.00
Revenue from ventilator beds in critical wards per day	2,400,000.00	2,880,000.00	2,400,000.00
Revenue from ICU beds per day	250,000.00	375,000.00	250,000.00
Revenue from Total beds per day	3,450,000.00	3,255,000.00	2,970,000.00
Occupancy (Assume avg.as 50%) per day	1,725,000.00	1,627,500.00	1,485,000.00
revenue per year	629,625,000.00	594,037,500.00	542,025,000.00
Expenses-running cost(Assume 60% from revenue)	377,775,000.00	356,422,500.00	325,215,000.00
Profit (per year)	251,850,000.00	237,615,000.00	216,810,000.00

NPV - Alternative 01

year	Cashflow	Present value
0	1,072,163,400.00	(1,072,163,400.00)
1	251,850,000.00	228,954,545.45
2	251,850,000.00	208,140,495.87
3	251,850,000.00	189,218,632.61
4	251,850,000.00	172,016,938.73
5	251,850,000.00	156,379,035.21
6	251,850,000.00	142,162,759.28
7	251,850,000.00	129,238,872.08
8	251,850,000.00	117,489,883.71
9	251,850,000.00	106,808,985.19
10	251,850,000.00	97,099,077.44
11	251,850,000.00	88,271,888.58
12	251,850,000.00	80,247,171.44
13	251,850,000.00	72,951,974.04
14	251,850,000.00	66,319,976.40
15	251,850,000.00	60,290,887.63
16	251,850,000.00	54,809,897.85
17	251,850,000.00	49,827,179.86
18	251,850,000.00	45,297,436.24
19	251,850,000.00	41,179,487.49
20	251,850,000.00	37,435,897.72
21	251,850,000.00	34,032,634.29
22	251,850,000.00	30,938,758.44
23	251,850,000.00	28,126,144.04
24	251,850,000.00	25,569,221.85
25	251,850,000.00	23,244,747.14
26	251,850,000.00	21,131,588.31
27	251,850,000.00	19,210,534.83
28	251,850,000.00	17,464,122.57
29	251,850,000.00	15,876,475.06
30	251,850,000.00	14,433,159.15
31	251,850,000.00	13,121,053.77
32	251,850,000.00	11,928,230.70
33	251,850,000.00	10,843,846.09
34	251,850,000.00	9,858,041.90
35	251,850,000.00	8,961,856.27
36	251,850,000.00	8,147,142.07
37	251,850,000.00	7,406,492.79
38	251,850,000.00	6,733,175.26
39	251,850,000.00	6,121,068.42
40	251,850,000.00	5,564,607.66
scrap value	278,899,200.00	6,162,257.79
NPV		1,396,852,781.23
IRR		12%

NPV - Alternative 02

year	Cashflow	PV
0	692,637,000.00	(692,637,000.00)
1	237,615,000.00	216,013,636.36
2	237,615,000.00	196,376,033.06
3	237,615,000.00	178,523,666.42
4	237,615,000.00	162,294,242.20
5	237,615,000.00	147,540,220.18
6	237,615,000.00	134,127,472.89
7	237,615,000.00	121,934,066.26
8	237,615,000.00	110,849,151.15
9	237,615,000.00	100,771,955.59
10	237,615,000.00	91,610,868.72
11	237,615,000.00	83,282,607.93
12	237,615,000.00	75,711,461.75
13	237,615,000.00	68,828,601.59
14	237,615,000.00	62,571,455.99
15	237,615,000.00	56,883,141.81
16	237,615,000.00	51,711,947.10
17	237,615,000.00	47,010,861.00
18	237,615,000.00	42,737,146.36
19	237,615,000.00	38,851,951.24
20	237,615,000.00	35,319,955.67
21	237,615,000.00	32,109,050.61
22	237,615,000.00	29,190,046.01
23	237,615,000.00	26,536,405.46
24	237,615,000.00	24,124,004.97
25	237,615,000.00	21,930,913.61
26	237,615,000.00	19,937,194.19
27	237,615,000.00	18,124,721.99
28	237,615,000.00	16,477,019.99
29	237,615,000.00	14,979,109.08
30	237,615,000.00	13,617,371.89
31	237,615,000.00	12,379,428.99
32	237,615,000.00	11,254,026.36
33	237,615,000.00	10,230,933.05
34	237,615,000.00	9,300,848.23
35	237,615,000.00	8,455,316.57
36	237,615,000.00	7,686,651.43
37	237,615,000.00	6,987,864.94
38	237,615,000.00	6,352,604.49
39	237,615,000.00	5,775,094.99
40	237,615,000.00	5,250,086.35
scrap value	174,312,000.00	3,851,411.12
NPV		1,634,863,547.59
IRR		22%

NPV - Alternative 03

year	Cashflow	PV
0	819,145,800.00	(819,145,800.00)
1	216,810,000.00	197,100,000.00
2	216,810,000.00	179,181,818.18
3	216,810,000.00	162,892,561.98
4	216,810,000.00	148,084,147.26
5	216,810,000.00	134,621,952.05
6	216,810,000.00	122,383,592.77
7	216,810,000.00	111,257,811.61
8	216,810,000.00	101,143,465.10
9	216,810,000.00	91,948,604.64
10	216,810,000.00	83,589,640.58
11	216,810,000.00	75,990,582.35
12	216,810,000.00	69,082,347.59
13	216,810,000.00	62,802,134.17
14	216,810,000.00	57,092,849.25
15	216,810,000.00	51,902,590.22
16	216,810,000.00	47,184,172.93
17	216,810,000.00	42,894,702.66
18	216,810,000.00	38,995,184.24
19	216,810,000.00	35,450,167.49
20	216,810,000.00	32,227,424.99
21	216,810,000.00	29,297,659.08
22	216,810,000.00	26,634,235.53
23	216,810,000.00	24,212,941.39
24	216,810,000.00	22,011,764.90
25	216,810,000.00	20,010,695.36
26	216,810,000.00	18,191,541.24
27	216,810,000.00	16,537,764.76
28	216,810,000.00	15,034,331.60
29	216,810,000.00	13,667,574.19
30	216,810,000.00	12,425,067.44
31	216,810,000.00	11,295,515.86
32	216,810,000.00	10,268,650.78
33	216,810,000.00	9,335,137.07
34	216,810,000.00	8,486,488.25
35	216,810,000.00	7,714,989.31
36	216,810,000.00	7,013,626.65
37	216,810,000.00	6,376,024.23
38	216,810,000.00	5,796,385.66
39	216,810,000.00	5,269,441.51
40	216,810,000.00	4,790,401.37
scrap value	209,174,400.00	4,621,693.34
NPV		1,305,671,879.61
IRR		15%

Application No.	
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Central Environmental Authority
BASIC INFORMATION QUESTIONNAIRE

Essential information to determine the environmental approval requirement of projects
(Note: Use separate sheets as and when required)

1. **BACKGROUND INFORMATION**

1.1 Project Title: [Design of New Quarantine Hospital for Infectious Diseases \(IDH\) in Kotikawatta, Mulleriyawa, Sri Lanka.](#)

1.2 Name of the Project Proponent: [Ministry of health](#)

1.3 Details of the Project Proponent:

Postal Address: [Ministry of Health, 385, Ven. Baddegama Wimalawansa Thero Mawatha, Colombo 10. Ven Baddegama Wimalawansa Mawatha, Colombo 01000](#)

Phone No: [011-2676449](#)

Fax No: [0112676449](#)

E-mail Address: postmaster@health.gov.lk

1.4 Details of the Contact Person:

Name: [L.G. S. De Silva](#)

Designation: [Project coordinator](#)

Phone No: [071-2143049](#)

Fax No: -

E-mail Address: gayansilvalive@gmail.com

2. **PROJECT LOCATION DETAILS**

2.1. Location of the project:

Province/s: [Western](#)

District/s: [Colombo](#)

Divisional Secretariat Division/s: [kotikawatta](#)

Local Authority/s: [Kotikawatta Mulleriyawa Municipal Council](#)

(Provide location in 1:50,000 scale Toposheet)

2.2. Physical scale or the extent of the project site (in ha): **0.045ha**
(Provide Survey plan)

2.3. Does the project wholly or partly fall within any area specified below?

Area	Yes	No	Remarks
100m from the boundaries of or within any area declared under the National Heritage Wilderness Act No. 4 of 1988		✓	
100m from the boundaries of or within any area declared under the Forest Ordinance (Chapter 451)		✓	
Coastal Zone as defined in the Coast Conservation Act. No. 57 of 1981		✓	
Any erodable area declared under the Soil Conservation Act (Chapter 450)		✓	
Any flood area declared under the Flood Protection Ordinance (Chapter 449)		✓	
Any flood protection area declared under the Sri Lanka Land Reclamation and Development Corporation Act No. 15 of 1968 as amended by Act No. 52 of 1982		✓	
60 meters from the bank of a public stream as defined in the Crown Lands Ordinance (Chapter 454) and having width of more than 25 meters at any point of its course.		✓	
Any reservation beyond the full supply level of a reservoir.		✓	
Any archaeological reserve, ancient or protected monuments as defined or declared under the Antiques Ordinance (Chapter 188)		✓	
Any area declared under the Botanic Gardens Ordinance (Chapter 446)		✓	
Within 100 meters from the boundaries of or within, any area declared as a Sanctuary under the Fauna and Flora Protection Ordinance (Chapter 469)		✓	
Within 100 meters from the high flood level contour of or within a public lake as defined in the Crowns Lands Ordinance (Chapter 454) including those declared under section 71 of the said Ordinance		✓	
Within a distance of one mile of the boundary of a National Reserve declared under the Fauna and Flora Protection Ordinance		✓	

2.4. Present ownership of the project site:

State	Private	Other (Specify)
✓		

(If state owned, please submit a letter of consent of the release of land from the state agency)

2.5 Present land use type of the project site (approximate % of the total project site):

Land use type	%	Land use type	%
Marsh/mangrove		Bare land	
Water bodies		Paddy	
Dense forest		Tea	
Sparse forest		Rubber	
Scrub forest	25%	Coconut	
Grassland	70%	Built-up area	05%
Home gardens		Any other (Specify)	

3. **PROJECT DETAILS**

3.1. Objective/s of the project:

3.2. Present stage of the project in the project cycle:

(i)	Pre-feasibility	
(ii)	Feasibility	
(iii)	Design	✓
(iv)	Other (specify)	

3.3. Type of the project (Please tick the relevant cage/s):

Land development/clearing		Hotels / Recreational Facilities	
Timber extraction/tree felling		Housing and building	✓
Reclamation of Land/ wetland		Resettlement	
Conversion of forests into non-forest uses		Laying of gas and liquid (excluding water) transferring pipelines	
Urban development		Mining	
Port and Harbour Development		Tunneling	
Transportation system		Fisheries and aquaculture	
River basin development/Irrigation		Disposal of solid/liquid/hazardous wastes	
Power generation and transmission		Salterns	
Surface/groundwater extraction		Any other (Specify)	
Industry/Industrial Estates and Parks			

3.4. Physical scale or the magnitude of the project: 03 storied and total floor area 6000sq.ft hospital building

3.5. Major components of the project: Hospital building, Parking, subordinate buildings

3.6. Project layout plan (Conceptual)

3.7 Project process/s in terms of:
This is a steel building construction project

3.8. Does the project involve any of the following activities other than the major project activities?

	Activity	Yes	No	If yes please quantify
(i)	Reclamation of land/wetland		✓	
(ii)	Conversion of forests into non-forest uses		✓	
(iii)	Clearing of lands	✓		.045 ha
(iv)	Extraction of timber		✓	
(v)	Mining and mineral extraction			
(vi)	Laying of pipe lines	✓		200m
(vii)	Tunneling		✓	
(viii)	Power generation & transmission		✓	
(ix)	Resettlement		✓	
(x)	Extraction of surface/ground water		✓	
(xi)	Disposal of wastes (solid/liquid/hazardous)	✓		700kg

3.9. Amount of capital investment:

Foreign:	
Local:	0.68Billion

3.10. Proposed timing and schedule including phased development: 08 months

3.11. Details of availability of following services/infrastructure facilities:

- (i) Roads/access (Specify): Internal roads
- (ii) Water (Specify):NWSDB
- (iii) Power (Specify):CEB
- (iv) Common waste water treatment facilities (Specify): Through primary treatment, chemical treatment and soakage pit
- (v) Common solid waste management facilities (Specify): Dispose and sort in a separate area reserved for disposal and transport away for a waste treatment plant.

3.12. Will the development result in displacement of people or property :
(Quantify)? No

3.13. Will the development result in change of :
way of life of local people? No

3.14. Will the project has plans for future expansion with/without land/space :
demands?
No

3.15. Information on likely impacts of the project (Please tick the relevant cage/s):

Impact/s	Yes	No	Short term	Medium term	Long term
• Impacts on people & human health		✓			
• Impacts on fauna/flora/sensitive habitats		✓			
• Impacts on soils and land use		✓			
• Impacts on water quality (surface and ground)	✓				
• Impacts on drainage /hydrology		✓			
• Impacts on air quality		✓			
• Generation of excessive noise and vibration		✓			
• Impacts on landscape/visual environment	✓				
• Impacts on historical and cultural resources		✓			
• Presence and aggravation of hazards	✓				
• Any other (Specify)		✓			

3.16. Information and measures being considered to mitigate likely impacts of the project cited under 3.15 :

Factor	Mitigatory Measure
Ground water pollution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Minimize the surface runoff and improve the ground water recharge through the treated waste water and rain water collection pits. ❖ Implement the landscaping with the usage of flora. ❖ proper treating method should be implemented for the black water and gray water and proper disposal of solid waste and chemicals

3.17.

I here by certify that the information provided above is true and correct to the best of my knowledge. I am aware that this information will be utilized in decision making.

Name:L.G.S. De Silva

Designation:Project Coordinator.....

Date:21/01/2022.....

For Office Only

1. Date of receipt of the application:

2. Payment of EIA administration fee:

Date of payment:

Amount:

Receipt No:

Code No:

3. Site inspection information:

Date of inspection:

Name/s of the officers:

Special comments regarding significant environmental concerns (based on the site inspection):

4. Required approval under Part IV C of NEA:

Yes

No

5. If need to go through the EIA process appropriate PAA:

6. Other remarks:

Annexure 06 - Leopold Matrix Chart for Identification of Impacts

Leopold Matrix

Activity			PRE CONSTRUCTION STAGE			CONSTRUCTION STAGE													OPERATIONAL STAGE							
			Reconnaissance Survey	Land Survey	Investigation	Planning and Designing	Development of Access Roads	Site Clearing	Site office Establishment	Locate the labour camps	Setting out	Construction Material Transportation	Land Levelling	Excavation	Pad foundation	Soil Filling & compaction	Concreting	Structural steel fabrication and erection	Finnishing	Building services	Landscaping	Bio hazardous waste disposal	Solid waste disposal	Waste water disposal	generators	Imergency fire
A.) Physical and Chemical Characteristics	1.) Earth	a) Mineral Resources				1						2		1							1	1	1			
		b) Construction Material														1	1									
		c) Soil			1	2	1	1	1	1		1	2	2	2						0	1	1	1		
		d) Land Forms (Paddy)																								
		e) Topography				2	1					1	1													
	2.) Water	a) Surface				1	1					1	1		1	1						1	2	2		
		b) Underground					1						2		2							3	3	3		
		c) Quality				1	1					1		1								3	3	3		
		d) Temperature															1				0					
		e) Quantity																								
		f) Recharge																								
	3.) Atmosphere	a) Quality				1	1	1				1	2						1	1	0	2	2	2		1
		b) Climate																								
		c) Temperature				1	1										1				0					1
	4.) Processes	a) Floods											1													
		b) Erosions			1	1	1						2		2						0					
		c) Deposition											1										2			
		d) Settlements											1		1											
		e) Soil Stability				1	1						1		1						0					
		f) Noise					1	1	1	1			2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1						
g) Vibration														1										2		
h) Road Traffic											2		1	1		2	1								1	
key			(1) Lower Negative Impact			(2) Medium negative impact						(3) Severe negative Impact				(0) Positive impact										

Activity			PRE CONSTRUCTION STAGE				CONSTRUCTION STAGE														OPERATIONAL STAGE				
			Reconnaissance Survey	Land Survey	Geological Investigation	Planning and Designing	Development of Access Roads	Site Clearing	Site office Establishment	Locate the labour camps	Setting out	Construction Material Transportation	Land Levelling	Excavation	Pad foundation	Soil Filling & compaction	Concreting	Structural steel fabrication and erection	Finishing	Building services	Landscaping	Bio hazardous waste disposal	Solid waste disposal	Waste water disposal	Generators
B.) Biological Conditions	1.) Flora	a) Trees				1	3													0					
		b) Shrubs		1	1		2	3					1		1					0					
		c) Grass		1	1		2	3	1	1	1		1	1	1					0					
		d) Crops																							
		e) Aquatic Plants																							
		f) Endangered Species			1			2						1						0	1	1	1	1	
	2.) Fauna	a) Birds (Avifauna)					1	2						1					0					1	
		b) Land Animals including Reptiles					1	2					1	1	1				0	1	1	1			
		c) Fish																					1		
		d) Insects		1	1		3	3	1				1	3	2				0	2	1	1			
		e) Endangered Species												1					0	2	2	2			
		f) Migratory Avifauna						1					1												
C.) Ecological Relationships	a) Eutrophication																				1	1			
	b) Food Chains																				1	1			
	c) Natural Habits					1	1					1									1	1	1	1	
	d) Eco System					1	1					1						0			1	1	1		
key -			(1) Lower Negative Impact				(2) Medium negative impact						(3) Severe negative Impact				(0) Positive impact								

Activity			PRE CONSTRUCTION				CONSTRUCTION STAGE														OPERATIONAL STAGE						
			Reconnaissance Survey	Land Survey	Geological Investigation	Planning and Designing	Development of Access Roads	Site Clearing	Site office Establishment	Locate the labour camps	Setting out	Construction Material Transportation	Land Levelling	Excavation	Pad foundation	Soil Filling & compaction	Concreting	Structural steel fabrication and erection	Finishing	Building services	Landscaping	Bio hazardous waste disposal	Solid waste disposal	Waste water disposal	Generators	Emergency fire	
D.) Socio - Economic and Cultural Factors	1.) Land Use	a) Wilderness and Open Spaces																					2	2			
		b) Wetlands																									
		c) Agriculture																									
		d) Residential																			0		2	2	2		
		e) Commercial																			0		1	1	1		
		f) Industry																			0		1	1	1		
	2.) Recreation	a) Fishing																									
		b) Boating																									
	3.) Aesthetic and human Interest	a) Scenic views and vistas					2	2													0						
		b) Landscape design					1	1													0		1	1			
		c) Parks																									
	4.) Cultural states	a) cultural Patterns				2																					
		b) Health and safety							1	1					1	1	1	2	2	1	1	0	1	3	3	3	
		c) Employment																									
d) population Density																							1	1			
e) Social harmony																											
E.) Others	a) Infrastructure																			0				1			
	b) Income Level																					2					

key - (1) Lower Negative Impact (2) Medium negative impact (3) Severe negative Impact (0) Positive impact

Annexure 07 - Traffic Survey Details

SUMMARY OF VEHICAL COUNT - MANDAVILA MAIN ROAD

Time	Vehical Type								Total(To the closest number)
	Morter Cycle	Three wheel	Passenger Cars(,Car, Van, Jeep)	Busses(One Door)	Busses (Two Door)	Light Truck (Four Wheel)	Medium Truck (SixWheel)	Long Vehicals (Containers)	
7.00 am - 7.15 am	30	6	8	1	2	4	2	2	55
7.15 am - 7.30 am	18	8	9	2	3	2	2	1	45
7.30 am - 7.45 am	25	9	12	_	2	3	1	_	52
7.45 am - 8.00 am	20	10	8	_	2	5	_	_	45
Morning Peak Hour	93	33	37	3	9	14	5	3	197
1.30 pm - 1.45 pm	15	12	12	_	3	4	1	1	84
1.45 pm - 2.00 pm	35	12	15	1	2	3	2	_	126
2.00 pm - 2.15 pm	20	9	14	_	3	2	3	_	90
2.15 pm - 2.30 pm	25	8	12	_	2	4	1	-	86
Afternoon Peak Hour	80	29	41	1	7	9	6	0	302
4.00 pm - 4.15 pm	20	8	15	1	2	3	1	_	78
4.15 pm - 4.30 pm	20	7	10	1	3	5	1	1	90
4.30 pm - 4.45 pm	24	10	15	_	3	2	_	1	88
4.45 pm - 5.00 pm	23	9	14	_	2	3	2	_	96
Evening Peak Hour	87	34	54	2	10	13	4	2	352
Total (For 3 Hrs)	260	96	132	6	26	36	15	5	
Total (For 1 Hrs)	87	32	44	2	9	12	5	2	192
Vehical Percentage %	45	17	23	1	5	6	3	1	

Type of Vehicals	Number of Vehicals(3 Hrs)	PCU Value	Flow(PCU in 3 Hrs)	Flow(PCU in 1 hr)	PCU %
Morter Cycle	260	0.4	104	35	22.51
Three wheel	96	0.8	76.8	26	16.62
Passenger Cars ,Car,Van,Jeep	132	1	132	44	28.57
Mini/ Medium Busses (One Door)	6	1.8	10.8	4	2.34
Busses (Two Door)	26	1.8	46.8	16	10.13
Light Truck (Four Wheel)	36	1.5	54	18	11.69
Medium Truck (SixWheel)	15	1.5	22.5	8	4.87
Long Vehicals (Containers)	5	3	15	5	3.25
Total	576			154	

Annexure 08 - Architectural Drawings

- Legend :
1. C.L.F - Chain Link Fence (To separate Zones)
 2. S.R - Security Room
 3. S.T - Septic Tank
 4. W.W.P - Waste water pit
 5. B.L - Building Line

Notes :

1. All dimensions are in meters.

SITE LAYOUT PLAN
SCALE - 1:450

Client Name : Ministry of Health

Design of New Quarantine Hospital for Infectious Diseases (IDH) in Kotikawatta, Mulleriyawa, Sri Lanka.

Drawn by : L.G.S. De Silva Date - 26/10/2021

MOH/IDH/ARCH/LAYOUT/A2/01

Scale - 1:450

GROUND FLOOR - BUILDING SPACE LAYOUT PLAN

SCALE - 1:250

Client - Ministry Of Health
Design of New Quarantine Hospital for Infectious diseases(IDH) at Kotikawatta, Mulleriyawa, Sri Lanka.
Design & Drawn Team - Group J
Drawn Title :

FRIST FLOOR - BUILDING SPACE LAYOUT PLAN
 SCALE - 1:250

Client - Ministry Of Health
Design of New Quarantine Hospital for Infectious diseases(IDH) at Kotikawatta, Mulleriyawa, Sri lanka.
Design & Drawn Team - Group J
Drawn Title :

SECTION A-A
SCALE - 1:250

SCHEDULE OF DOOR & WINDOWS

TYPE	SIZE	SILL	DESCRIPTION	G.F	F.F	S.F	TOTAL
D1	5'-8" X 7'-0"	-	ALUMINIUM FRAMED GLASS DOUBLE SWING DOOR	07	16	16	39
D2	2'-8" X 7'-0"	-	ALUMINIUM FRAMED GALSS DOOR	32	10	10	52
D3	2'-6" X 7'-0"	-	FIBER GLASS FRAMED FIBER GLASS DOOR WITH DOOR LOCKS & INDICATOR BOLTS	10	07	07	24
W1	8'-0" x 10'-0"	-	GLAZED ALUMINIUM WINDOW WITH FIXED GLASS	04	04	04	12
W2	15'-5" X 10'-0"	-	GLAZED ALUMINIUM WINDOW WITH FIXED GLASS	06	06	06	18
W3	10'-5" X 8'-5"	-	GLAZED ALUMINIUM WINDOW	01	-	-	01
W4	5'-5" X 8'-5"	-	GLAZED ALUMINIUM WINDOW WITH FIXED GLASS	01	-	-	01
W5	8'-0" X 5'-6"	-	GLAZED ALUMINIUM WINDOW WITH GLASS ON TOP	15	32	32	79
W6	2'-0" X 8'-5"	-	GLAZED ALUMINIUM WINDOW WITH FIXED GLASS	07	01	01	09
W7	16'-7" x 10'-0"	-	GLAZED ALUMINIUM WINDOW	-	02	02	04
W8	8'-4" X 10'-0"	-	GLAZED ALUMINIUM WINDOW	-	04	04	08
W9	4'-0" X 5'-6"	-	GLAZED ALUMINIUM WINDOW WITH GLASS ON TOP	-	01	01	02
FL	2'-0" X 2'-0"	-	GLAZED ALUMINIUM FANLIGHT	04	06	06	16

Client - Ministry Of Health
Design of New Quarantine Hospital for Infectious diseases(IDH) at Kotikawatta, Mulleriyawa, Sri lanka.
Design & Drawn Team - Group J
Drawn Title :

Annexure 09 - STAAD.Pro report

Software licensed to	Job No	Sheet No 1	Rev
	Part		
Job Title Group J - IDH	Ref		
	By	Date 17-Sept-22	Chd
Client	File Group J - Final Project.st	Date/Time 17-Sep-2022 13:17	

Job Information

	Engineer	Checked	Approved
Name:			
Date:	17-Sept-22		

Structure Type	SPACE FRAME
-----------------------	-------------

Number of Nodes	446	Highest Node	446
Number of Elements	792	Highest Beam	843
Number of Plates	160	Highest Plate	952

Number of Basic Load Cases	-2
Number of Combination Load Cases	6

Included in this printout are data for:

All	The Whole Structure
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Included in this printout are results for load cases:

Type	L/C	Name
Primary	1	DL
Primary	2	LL
Primary	3	WX+
Primary	4	WX-
Primary	5	WZ+
Primary	6	WZ-
Combination	7	DL+LL
Combination	8	1.25DL+1.5LL
Combination	9	1.25DL+1.5LL+1.05WX+
Combination	10	1.25DL+1.5LL+1.05WX-
Combination	11	1.25DL+1.5LL+1.05WZ+
Combination	12	1.25DL+1.5LL+1.05WZ-

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3D Rendered View

Plan view

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front view

side view

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Client

Dead load

wind load - positive x direction

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wind load - positive z direction

Section Properties

Prop	Section	Area (cm ²)	I _{yy} (cm ⁴)	I _{zz} (cm ⁴)	J (cm ⁴)	Material
2	UC254X254X73	93.100	3.91E+3	11.4E+3	57.625	STEEL
3	UC203X203X60	76.400	2.06E+3	6.12E+3	47.230	STEEL
4	UB457X191X133	170.000	3.35E+3	63.8E+3	292.355	STEEL
5	UB178X102X19	24.300	137.000	1.36E+3	4.408	STEEL
6	100X6.3SHS	23.200	336.000	336.000	518.274	STEEL
7	70X5SHS	12.700	88.500	88.500	137.312	STEEL
8	UB254X146X43	54.800	677.000	6.54E+3	23.884	STEEL
9	219.1X10CHS	65.700	3.6E+3	3.6E+3	7.2E+3	STEEL
10	UB356X127X39	49.800	358.000	10.2E+3	15.097	STEEL
11	UB457X191X98	125.000	2.35E+3	45.7E+3	121.287	STEEL

Plate Thickness

Prop	Node A (cm)	Node B (cm)	Node C (cm)	Node D (cm)	Material
1	13.000	13.000	13.000	13.000	CONCRETE

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Node Displacement Summary

	Node	L/C	X (mm)	Y (mm)	Z (mm)	Resultant (mm)	rX (rad)	rY (rad)	rZ (rad)
Max X	143	12:1.25DL+1.5I	215.676	-14.181	-205.774	298.430	-0.169	0.038	-0.185
Min X	332	11:1.25DL+1.5I	-218.020	-14.194	208.063	301.702	0.168	0.037	0.184
Max Y	237	5:WZ+	0.007	1.170	1.792	2.140	0.000	0.000	-0.000
Min Y	237	12:1.25DL+1.5I	-0.040	-20.765	-1.871	20.849	0.007	-0.000	0.000
Max Z	393	11:1.25DL+1.5I	0.457	-7.835	2.82E+3	2.82E+3	-2.346	0.521	0.001
Min Z	401	12:1.25DL+1.5I	0.394	-7.829	-2.87E+3	2.87E+3	2.367	-0.529	0.001
Max rX	63	12:1.25DL+1.5I	-0.472	-7.829	-2.86E+3	2.86E+3	2.372	0.529	-0.001
Min rX	393	11:1.25DL+1.5I	0.457	-7.835	2.82E+3	2.82E+3	-2.346	0.521	0.001
Max rY	72	12:1.25DL+1.5I	0.332	-7.867	-638.379	638.427	2.355	0.650	-0.000
Min rY	410	12:1.25DL+1.5I	-0.410	-7.866	-653.035	653.082	2.348	-0.649	0.000
Max rZ	333	12:1.25DL+1.5I	-215.975	-14.182	-205.950	298.767	-0.168	-0.038	0.185
Min rZ	142	11:1.25DL+1.5I	215.638	-14.192	205.880	298.476	0.169	-0.038	-0.185
Max Rst	401	12:1.25DL+1.5I	0.394	-7.829	-2.87E+3	2.87E+3	2.367	-0.529	0.001

Beam Displacement Detail Summary

Displacements shown in italic indicate the presence of an offset

	Beam	L/C	d (m)	X (mm)	Y (mm)	Z (mm)	Resultant (mm)
Max X	201	12:1.25DL+1.5I	5.215	215.677	-14.181	-205.773	298.430
Min X	537	11:1.25DL+1.5I	0.000	-218.021	-14.194	208.063	301.703
Max Y	705	5:WZ+	2.800	-0.086	10.088	2.584	10.414
Min Y	608	10:1.25DL+1.5I	2.607	-3.784	-84.877	10.258	85.578
Max Z	696	11:1.25DL+1.5I	7.000	0.459	-7.835	2.82E+3	2.82E+3
Min Z	703	12:1.25DL+1.5I	7.000	0.397	-7.829	-2.87E+3	2.87E+3
Max Rst	703	12:1.25DL+1.5I	7.000	0.397	-7.829	-2.87E+3	2.87E+3

Beam End Displacement Summary

Displacements shown in italic indicate the presence of an offset

	Beam	Node	L/C	X (mm)	Y (mm)	Z (mm)	Resultant (mm)
Max X	201	143	12:1.25DL+1.5I	215.677	-14.181	-205.773	298.430
Min X	537	332	11:1.25DL+1.5I	-218.021	-14.194	208.063	301.703
Max Y	380	215	5:WZ+	<i>-0.011</i>	1.170	1.792	2.140
Min Y	380	215	12:1.25DL+1.5I	<i>-0.016</i>	-20.765	-1.153	20.797
Max Z	696	393	11:1.25DL+1.5I	0.459	-7.835	2.82E+3	2.82E+3
Min Z	703	401	12:1.25DL+1.5I	0.397	-7.829	-2.87E+3	2.87E+3
Max Rst	703	401	12:1.25DL+1.5I	0.397	-7.829	-2.87E+3	2.87E+3

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Beam End Force Summary

The signs of the forces at end B of each beam have been reversed. For example: this means that the Min Fx entry gives the largest tension value for a beam.

	Beam	Node	L/C	Axial	Shear		Torsion	Bending	
				Fx (kN)	Fy (kN)	Fz (kN)	Mx (kNm)	My (kNm)	Mz (kNm)
Max Fx	136	77	9:1.25DL+1.5L	1.63E+3	7.581	0.127	0.000	-0.000	0.000
Min Fx	435	249	8:1.25DL+1.5L	-128.553	-0.028	-0.000	0.000	0.000	-0.027
Max Fy	763	363	10:1.25DL+1.5L	7.395	153.539	0.011	0.010	-0.032	232.472
Min Fy	101	98	9:1.25DL+1.5L	7.416	-153.502	-0.011	-0.010	-0.032	232.353
Max Fz	390	219	11:1.25DL+1.5L	495.746	-0.024	26.991	-0.000	-49.021	-0.047
Min Fz	392	221	12:1.25DL+1.5L	495.649	-0.032	-26.830	0.000	48.616	-0.057
Max Mx	835	437	12:1.25DL+1.5L	20.844	4.444	-0.559	3.628	3.050	17.610
Min Mx	43	27	12:1.25DL+1.5L	20.847	-4.441	-0.560	-3.607	3.060	-17.598
Max My	390	222	11:1.25DL+1.5L	495.746	-0.024	26.991	-0.000	58.945	0.049
Min My	392	224	12:1.25DL+1.5L	495.649	-0.032	-26.830	0.000	-58.703	0.070
Max Mz	734	348	10:1.25DL+1.5L	-7.261	153.131	0.011	-0.008	-0.034	243.587
Min Mz	814	433	9:1.25DL+1.5L	438.569	40.788	0.480	0.000	1.000	-84.117

Beam Force Detail Summary

Sign convention as diagrams:- positive above line, negative below line except Fx where positive is compression. Distance d is given from beam end A.

	Beam	L/C	d (m)	Axial	Shear		Torsion	Bending	
				Fx (kN)	Fy (kN)	Fz (kN)	Mx (kNm)	My (kNm)	Mz (kNm)
Max Fx	136	9:1.25DL+1.5L	0.000	1.63E+3	7.581	0.127	0.000	-0.000	0.000
Min Fx	435	8:1.25DL+1.5L	0.000	-128.553	-0.028	-0.000	0.000	0.000	-0.027
Max Fy	763	10:1.25DL+1.5L	0.000	7.395	153.539	0.011	0.010	-0.032	232.472
Min Fy	101	9:1.25DL+1.5L	7.000	7.416	-153.502	-0.011	-0.010	-0.032	232.353
Max Fz	390	11:1.25DL+1.5L	0.000	495.746	-0.024	26.991	-0.000	-49.021	-0.047
Min Fz	392	12:1.25DL+1.5L	0.000	495.649	-0.032	-26.830	0.000	48.616	-0.057
Max Mx	835	12:1.25DL+1.5L	0.000	20.844	4.444	-0.559	3.628	3.050	17.610
Min Mx	43	12:1.25DL+1.5L	0.000	20.847	-4.441	-0.560	-3.607	3.060	-17.598
Max My	390	11:1.25DL+1.5L	4.000	495.746	-0.024	26.991	-0.000	58.945	0.049
Min My	392	12:1.25DL+1.5L	4.000	495.649	-0.032	-26.830	0.000	-58.703	0.070
Max Mz	734	10:1.25DL+1.5L	0.000	-7.261	153.131	0.011	-0.008	-0.034	243.587
Min Mz	393	11:1.25DL+1.5L	3.750	13.598	-1.156	-0.000	0.000	0.000	-344.221

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Reaction Summary

	Node	L/C	Horizontal	Vertical	Horizontal	Moment		
			FX (kN)	FY (kN)	FZ (kN)	MX (kNm)	MY (kNm)	MZ (kNm)
Max FX	5	10:1.25DL+1.5	15.215	867.875	0.132	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min FX	415	9:1.25DL+1.5	-15.181	867.763	0.125	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max FY	77	9:1.25DL+1.5	-7.581	1.63E+3	0.127	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min FY	262	5:WZ+	0.034	-126.923	-88.508	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max FZ	150	12:1.25DL+1.5	-8.217	951.444	289.335	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min FZ	266	11:1.25DL+1.5	7.248	961.083	-291.419	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max MX	1	1:DL	3.721	285.173	1.937	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min MX	1	1:DL	3.721	285.173	1.937	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max MY	1	1:DL	3.721	285.173	1.937	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min MY	1	1:DL	3.721	285.173	1.937	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max MZ	1	1:DL	3.721	285.173	1.937	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min MZ	1	1:DL	3.721	285.173	1.937	0.000	0.000	0.000

Statics Check Results

L/C		FX (kN)	FY (kN)	FZ (kN)	MX (kNm)	MY (kNm)	MZ (kNm)
1:DL	Loads	0.000	-30.2E+3	0.000	770E+3	-0.000	-846E+3
1:DL	Reactions	-0.000	30.2E+3	-0.000	-770E+3	0.000	846E+3
	Difference	-0.000	-0.000	0.000	0.002	-0.000	-0.000
2:LL	Loads	-0.000	-14.2E+3	-0.000	363E+3	-0.000	-399E+3
2:LL	Reactions	0.000	14.2E+3	0.000	-363E+3	0.000	399E+3
	Difference	-0.000	-0.000	0.000	0.001	-0.000	0.001
3:WX+	Loads	412.455	0.000	0.000	0.000	10.5E+3	-2.96E+3
3:WX+	Reactions	-412.455	0.000	0.000	-0.000	-10.5E+3	2.96E+3
	Difference	0.000	0.000	0.000	-0.000	-0.000	-0.000
4:WX-	Loads	-412.455	0.000	0.000	0.000	-10.5E+3	2.96E+3
4:WX-	Reactions	412.455	-0.000	-0.000	-0.000	10.5E+3	-2.96E+3
	Difference	-0.000	-0.000	-0.000	-0.000	0.000	0.000
5:WZ+	Loads	0.000	0.000	429.155	2.98E+3	-12E+3	0.000
5:WZ+	Reactions	-0.000	-0.000	-429.155	-2.98E+3	12E+3	0.000
	Difference	-0.000	-0.000	0.000	0.002	-0.000	0.000
6:WZ-	Loads	0.000	0.000	-429.155	-2.98E+3	12E+3	0.000
6:WZ-	Reactions	0.000	0.000	429.155	2.98E+3	-12E+3	-0.000
	Difference	0.000	0.000	-0.000	-0.002	0.000	-0.000

Failed Members

There is no data of this type.

Project - Design of New Quarantine Hospital for Infectious Diseases (IDH) in Kotikawatta, Mulleriyawa, Sri Lanka.		
Reference	Calculations	Output
Unless stated otherwise all references are to BS EN 1991-1-1:2002 NA2.4 Table 6.1 Table 6.2 6.3.1.2(8)	<u>Characteristic actions – Floors above ground level</u>	
	<u>Permanent actions</u>	
	Self-weight of floor	3.58kN/m ²
	Self-weight of ceiling, raised floor & services	0.2 kN/m ²
	Total permanent action is, $g_k = 3.58 + 0.2 = 3.78 \text{ kN/m}^2$	
	Wall load along perimeter of the building	09KN/m
	<u>Variable actions</u>	
	Imposed floor load for offices (category C3)	3.0 kN/m ²
	Imposed floor load for moveable partitions of less than 2 kN/m run	0.8 kN/m ²
	Total variable action is, $q_k = 3.0 + 0.8 = 3.8 \text{ kN/m}^2$	
NA 2.10 Table NA.7	<u>Imposed roof actions</u>	
	<u>Permanent actions</u>	
	Self-weight of roof construction	0.40 kN/m ²
	Self-weight of ceiling and services	0.15 kN/m ²
	Total permanent action is $g_k = 0.40 + 0.15 = 0.55 \text{ kN/m}^2$	
	<u>Variable actions</u>	
	The roof is only accessible for normal maintenance and repair	Imposed roof load 0.6 kN/m ²

<p>BS EN 1991-1-4</p> <p>Unless stated otherwise all references are to BS EN 1993-1-1:2005</p> <p>See structural arrangement and loading</p> <p>BS EN 1990 NA.2.2.3.2 Table NA.A1.2(B)</p> <p>BS EN 1990 6.4.3.2</p> <p>BS EN 1990 Eq. (6.10b)</p>	<p><u>Wind action</u></p> <p>Wind force acting on the length of the building is:</p> $F_w = 0.75 \text{ kN/m}$ <p><u>Simply supported fully restrained beam</u></p> <p>Consider floor beam at Level 1 – Gridline 5 D-E</p> <p>Beam span, $L = 7.5 \text{ m}$ Bay width, $= 7 \text{ m}$</p> <p><u>Actions</u></p> <p>Permanent action</p> <p>Variable action</p> <p><u>Ultimate limit state (ULS)</u></p> <p>Partial factors for actions</p> <p>Partial factor for permanent actions $\gamma_G = 1.35$ Partial factor for variable actions $\gamma_Q = 1.5$ Reduction factor $\xi = 0.925$</p> <p>The combination factor (ψ_0) is not required as the only variable action is the imposed floor load. The wind has no impact on the design of this member.</p> <p><u>Combination of actions at ULS</u></p> <p>Design value of combined actions, $\xi \gamma_G g_k + \gamma_Q q_k$</p> $= (0.925 \times 1.35 \times 4.65) + (1.5 \times 3.8) = 11.5 \text{ kN/m}^2$ <p>UDL per meter length of beam accounting for bay width of 7.0 m,</p> $F_d = 11.5 \times 7.0 = 80.5 \text{ kN/m}$	<p>$F_w = 0.75 \text{ kN/m}$</p> <p>$g_k = 3.78 \text{ kN/m}^2$ $q_k = 3.8 \text{ kN/m}^2$</p> <p>ULS design load $F_d = 80.5 \text{ kN/m}$</p>
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<p>6.1(1) NA 2.15</p> <p>NA 2.4 BS EN 10025-2 Table 7</p> <p>3.2.6(1)</p> <p>5.5 & Table 5.2</p>	<p><u>Design moment and shear force</u></p> <p>Maximum design moment, $M_{y,Ed}$, occurs at mid-span, and for bending about the major (y-y) axis is:</p> $M_{y,Ed} = F_d L^2 / 8 = (80.5 \times 7.5^2) / 8 = 566 \text{ kNm}$ <p>Maximum design shear force, V_{Ed}, occurs at the end supports, and is:</p> $V_{Ed} = F_d L / 2 = (80.5 \times 7.5) / 2 = 301.875 \text{ kN}$ <p>Partial factors for resistance</p> $\gamma_{M0} = 1.0$ <p><u>Trial section</u></p> <p>An Advance UK Beam (UKB) S275 is to be used. Assuming the nominal thickness (t) of the flange and web is less than 40mm or more than 16 mm, the yield strength is:</p> $f_y = 265 \text{ N/mm}^2$ <p>From the tables of section properties try section 457 × 191 × 98 UKB, S265, which has $W_{pl,y} = 2010 \text{ cm}^3$</p> <p>Modulus of elasticity $E = 210000 \text{ N/mm}^2$</p> <p>For section classification the coefficient ϵ is:</p> $\epsilon = \sqrt{235/f_y} = \sqrt{235/265} = 0.94$ <p>Outstand flange: flange under uniform compression</p> $c = \frac{(b - t_w - 2r)}{2} = \frac{(191.9 - 10.5 - (2 \times 10.2))}{2}$ $= 80.5 \text{ mm}$ $\frac{c}{t_f} = \frac{80.5}{17.7} = 4.5$ <p>The limiting value for Class 1 is $c/t \leq 9\epsilon = 9 \times 0.94 = 8.46$ $4.5 < 8.46$, Therefore, the flange outstand in compression is Class 1.</p>	<p>$M_{y,Ed} = 566 \text{ kNm}$</p> <p>$V_{Ed} = 301.875 \text{ kN}$</p>
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	<p><u>Shear buckling</u></p> <p>6.2.6(6) Shear buckling of the unstiffened web need not be considered provided:</p> $\frac{h_w}{t_w} \leq \frac{72 \varepsilon}{\eta}$ $\frac{428}{10.5} \leq \frac{72 \times 0.94}{1}, \quad 40.76 < 66.68$ <p>Therefore, shear buckling check need not be considered.</p> <p><u>Moment Resistance</u></p> <p>6.2.5(1) The design requirement is:</p> $\frac{M_{Ed}}{M_{c,Rd}} \leq 1$ <p>6.2.5(2) $M_{c,Rd} = M_{pl,Rd} = \frac{W_{pl,y} \times f_y}{\gamma_{M0}}$ (For Class 1 sections)</p> <p>6.2.8(2) At the point of maximum bending moment, the shear force is zero. Therefore, the bending resistance does not need to be reduced due to the presence of shear.</p> <p>6.2.5(2) $M_{c,Rd} = M_{pl,Rd} = \frac{2230 \times 265}{I} \times 10^{-3} = 590.95 \text{ kNm}$</p> $\frac{M_{y,Ed}}{M_{c,Rd}} = \frac{566}{590.95} = 0.95 < 1$ <p>Therefore, the design bending resistance of the section is adequate.</p> <p><u>Serviceability Limit State (SLS)</u></p> <p>BS EN 1990 NA 2.2.6 Guidance on deflection limits and combinations of actions to be considered are given in the material Standards.</p> <p>BS EN 1993-1-1 NA 2.23 Vertical deflections should normally be calculated under the characteristic load combination due to variable loads. Permanent loads should not be included.</p>	<p>Design bending resistance is: $M_{c,Rd} = 532.65 \text{ kNm}$</p> <p>Bending resistance is adequate</p>
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<p>BS EN1990 6.5.3 (6.14b)</p>	<p>The characteristic load combination at SLS is: $\Sigma G_k + Q_{k,1} + \Sigma \psi_{\alpha,i} Q_{k,i}$ This is modified by NA 2.23 to EN 1993-1-1 which states that permanent loads should not be included. As there is only one variable action present, the term $\Sigma \psi_{\alpha,i} Q_{k,i} = 0$</p> <p>Vertical deflection of beam The vertical deflection at the mid-span is determined as:</p> $w = \frac{5L^4 q_k}{384EI_y}$ $q_k = 3.8 \times 7 = 26.6 \text{ kN/m}$ $w = \frac{5 \times 7500^4 \times 26.6}{384 \times 210000 \times 41000 \times 10^4} = 12.72 \text{ mm}$	<p>Vertical mid-span deflection $w = 12.72 \text{ mm}$</p>
<p>BS EN 1993-1-1 NA 2.23</p>	<p>Vertical deflection limit for this example is $\frac{\text{Span}}{360} = \frac{7500}{360} = 20.83 \text{ mm}$ $12.72 \text{ mm} < 20.83 \text{ mm}$ Therefore, the vertical deflection of the section is satisfactory. Vertical deflection is acceptable</p> <p>Adopt 457×191×98 UKB in S275</p>	<p>Vertical deflection is acceptable</p>

<p>Unless stated otherwise all references are to BS EN 1993-1-1:2005</p>	<p><u>Simply supported fully restrained beam</u> Consider floor beam at Level 1 – Gridline E 4-5</p> <p>Beam span, $L = 7$ m Bay width, $= 7.5$ m</p> <p><u>Actions</u></p>	
<p>See structural arrangement and loading</p>	<p>Permanent action</p> <p>Variable action</p>	<p>$g_k = 3.78$ kN/m² $q_k = 3.8$ kN/m²</p>
<p>BS EN 1990 NA.2.2.3.2 Table NA.A1.2(B)</p>	<p><u>Ultimate limit state (ULS)</u> Partial factors for actions</p> <p>Partial factor for permanent actions $\gamma_G = 1.35$ Partial factor for variable actions $\gamma_Q = 1.5$ Reduction factor $\xi = 0.925$</p> <p>The combination factor (ψ_0) is not required as the only variable action is the imposed floor load. The wind has no impact on the design of this member.</p>	
<p>BS EN 1990 6.4.3.2</p>	<p><u>Combination of actions at ULS</u> Design value of combined actions, $\xi \gamma_G g_k + \gamma_Q q_k$</p> <p>$= (0.925 \times 1.35 \times 3.78) + (1.5 \times 3.8) = 10.42 \text{ kN/m}^2$</p>	
<p>BS EN 1990 Eq. (6.10b)</p>	<p>UDL per meter length of beam accounting for bay width of 7.0 m,</p> <p>$F_d = 10.42 \times 7.5 = 78.15 \text{ kN/m}$</p>	<p>ULS design load $F_d = 78.15 \text{ kN/m}$</p>

Design moment and shear force

Maximum design moment, $M_{y,Ed}$, occurs at mid-span, and for bending about the major (y-y) axis is:

$$M_{y,Ed} = 612.54 \text{ kNm}$$

$$M_{y,Ed} = 612.54 \text{ kNm}$$

Maximum design shear force, V_{Ed} , occurs at the end supports, and is:

$$V_{Ed} = 311.775 \text{ kN}$$

$$V_{Ed} = 311.775 \text{ kN}$$

6.1(1) NA 2.15	<p>Partial factors for resistance</p> $\gamma_{M0} = 1.0$	
NA 2.4 BS EN 10025- 2 Table 7	<p><u>Trial section</u></p> <p>An Advance UK Beam (UKB) S275 is to be used. Assuming the nominal thickness (t) of the flange and web is less than 40mm or more than 16 mm, the yield strength is: $f_y = 265 \text{ N/mm}^2$</p>	
3.2.6(1)	<p>From the tables of section properties try section $457 \times 191 \times 133$ UKB, S265, which has $W_{pl,y} = 3080 \text{ cm}^3$</p> <p>Modulus of elasticity $E = 210000 \text{ N/mm}^2$</p>	
5.5 & Table 5.2	<p>For section classification the coefficient ϵ is:</p> $\epsilon = \sqrt{235/f_y} = \sqrt{235/265} = 0.94$ <p>Outstand flange: flange under uniform compression</p> $c = \frac{(b - t_w - 2r)}{2} = \frac{(196.7 - 15.3 - (2 \times 12.7))}{2}$ $= 78 \text{ mm}$ $\frac{c}{t_f} = \frac{78}{26.3} = 2.96$	
	<p>The limiting value for Class 1 is $c/t \leq 9\epsilon = 9 \times 0.94 = 8.46$ $2.96 < 8.46$, Therefore, the flange outstand in compression is Class 1.</p> <p>Internal compression part: web under pure bending $c = d = 480.6 \text{ mm}$ $c/t_w = 480.6/15.3 = 31.4$</p> <p>The limiting value for Class 1 is $c/t_w \leq 72\epsilon = 72 \times 0.94 = 67.68$ $31.4 < 67.68$ Therefore, the web in pure bending is Class 1. Therefore the section is Class 1 under pure bending.</p>	
		Section is Class 1

	<p><u>Member resistance verification</u></p> <p><u>Shear resistance</u></p> <p>6.2.6 6.2.6(1) The basic design requirement is:</p> $\frac{V_{Ed}}{V_{c,Rd}} \leq 1$ <p>6.2.6(2) $V_{c,Rd} = V_{pl,Rd} = \frac{A_v (F_y / \sqrt{3})}{\gamma_{M0}}$ (for Class 1 sections)</p> <p>6.2.6(3) For a rolled I-section with shear parallel to the web the shear area is</p> $A_v = A - 2bt_f + (t_w + 2r) t_f, \text{ but not less than } \eta h_w t_w$ $A_v = (170 \times 10^2) - (2 \times 196.7 \times 26.3) + 26.3(15.3 + (2 \times 12.7))$ $A_v = 7723.99 \text{ mm}^2$ <p>$\eta = 1.0$ (conservative)</p> $h_w = D - 2 t_f = 480.6 - (2 \times 26.3) = 428 \text{ mm}$ $\eta h_w t_w = 1 \times 428 \times 15.3 = 6548.4 \text{ mm}^2$ $7723.99 \text{ mm}^2 > 6548.4 \text{ mm}^2$ <p>Therefore, $A_v = 7723.99 \text{ mm}^2$</p> <p>The design shear resistance is therefore</p> <p>6.2.6(2) $V_{c,Rd} = V_{pl,Rd} = \frac{7723.99 (265 / 1.732)}{I} \times 10^{-3} = 1181.78 \text{ kN}$</p> $\frac{V_{Ed}}{V_{c,Rd}} = \frac{311.775}{1181.78} = 0.263 \leq 1$ <p>Therefore, the shear resistance of the section is adequate.</p> <p><u>Shear buckling</u></p> <p>6.2.6(6) Shear buckling of the unstiffened web need not be considered provided:</p> $\frac{h_w}{t_w} \leq \frac{72 \epsilon}{\eta}$ $\frac{428}{15.3} \leq \frac{72 \times 0.94}{1}, \quad 27.97 < 66.68$ <p>Therefore, shear buckling check need not be considered.</p>	<p>Design shear resistance is: $V_{c,Rd} = 1181.78 \text{ kN}$</p> <p>Shear resistance is adequate</p>
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	<p><u>Moment Resistance</u></p> <p>The design requirement is:</p> <p>6.2.5(1) $\frac{M_{Ed}}{M_{c,Rd}} \leq 1$</p> <p>6.2.5(2) $M_{c,Rd} = M_{pl,Rd} = \frac{W_{pl,y} \times f_y}{\gamma_{M0}}$ (For Class 1 sections)</p> <p>6.2.8(2) At the point of maximum bending moment, the shear force is zero. Therefore, the bending resistance does not need to be reduced due to the presence of shear.</p> <p>6.2.5(2) $M_{c,Rd} = M_{pl,Rd} = \frac{3080 \times 265}{I} \times 10^{-3} = 816.2 \text{ kNm}$</p> <p>$\frac{M_{y,Ed}}{M_{c,Rd}} = \frac{612.54}{816.2} = 0.75 < 1$</p> <p>Therefore, the design bending resistance of the section is adequate.</p> <p><u>Serviceability Limit State (SLS)</u> Guidance on deflection limits and combinations of actions to be considered are given in the material Standards.</p> <p>BS EN 1990 NA 2.2.6</p> <p>BS EN 1993-1-1 NA 2.23</p> <p>BS EN 1990 6.5.3 (6.14b)</p> <p>The characteristic load combination at SLS is: $\Sigma G_k + Q_{k,1} + \Sigma \psi_{0,i} Q_{k,i}$ This is modified by NA 2.23 to EN 1993-1-1 which states that permanent loads should not be included. As there is only one variable action present, the term $\Sigma \psi_{0,i} Q_{k,i} = 0$</p> <p>Vertical deflection of beam The vertical deflection at the mid-span is determined as:</p>	<p>Design bending resistance is: $M_{c,Rd} = 816.2 \text{ kNm}$</p> <p>Bending resistance is adequate</p>
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<p>BS EN 1993-1-1 NA 2.23</p>	$w = \frac{5L^4 q_k}{384EI_y}$ $q_k = 3.8 \times 7.5 = 28.5 \text{ kN/m}$ $w = \frac{5 \times 7000^4 \times 28.5}{384 \times 210000 \times 64058 \times 10^4} = 6.62 \text{ mm}$ <p>Vertical deflection limit for this example is</p> $\frac{\text{Span}}{360} = \frac{7000}{360} = 19.44 \text{ mm}$ $6.62 \text{ mm} < 19.44 \text{ mm}$ <p>Therefore, the vertical deflection of the section is satisfactory. Vertical deflections acceptable</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Adopt 457×191×133 UKB in S275</p>	<p>Vertical mid-span deflection w=12.72m m</p> <p>Vertical deflection is acceptable</p>
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<p>Unless stated otherwise all references are to BS EN 1994-1-1</p>	<p><u>Simply supported composite secondary beam</u></p> <p>7.5m long beam between 4-5 and DE</p> <p><u>Design data</u></p> <p>Beam span $L = 7.5$ m Beam spacing $s = 3.5$ m Total slab depth $h = 130$ mm Depth of concrete above profile $h_c = 70$ mm Deck profile height $h_p = 60$ mm Width of the bottom of the trough $b_{bot} = 120$ mm Width of the top of the trough $b_{top} = 170$ mm approx</p> <p><u>Shear connectors</u></p> <p>Diameter $d = 19$ mm Overall height before welding $h_{sc} = 100$ mm Height after welding 95mm</p> <p><u>Materials</u></p> <p>Structural Steel: For grade S275 and maximum thickness (t) less than 16 mm Yield strength $f_y = 275$ N/mm² Ultimate strength $f_u = 410$ N/mm²</p>	
<p>BS EN 1993-1-1 NA 2.4 BS EN 10025-2 Table 7</p>	<p>Steel reinforcement: Yield strength $f_{yk} = 500$ N/mm²</p>	
<p>BS EN 1992-1-1 Table C.1 BS 4449</p>	<p>Concrete: Normal weight concrete strength class C25/30 Density 26 kN/m³ (wet) 25 kN/m³ (dry) Cylinder strength $f_{ck} = 25$ N/mm² Secant modulus of elasticity $E_{cm} = 31$ kN/mm²</p>	
<p>BS EN 1992-1-1 Table 3.1</p>	<p><u>Actions</u></p> <p><u>Concrete weight</u></p> <p>Self-weight of the concrete slab (volume from manufacturer's data) $0.097 \times 26 \times 10^{-6} = 2.52$ kN/m² (wet) $0.097 \times 25 \times 10^{-6} = 2.43$ kN/m² (dry)</p>	

<p>BS EN 1991-1-6 NA 2.13</p>	<p><u>Permanent Actions</u></p> <p>Construction stage kN/m²</p> <p>Steel deck 0.11</p> <p>Steel beam <u>0.20</u></p> <p>Total <u>0.31</u></p> <p>Composite stage kN/m²</p> <p>Concrete slab 2.43</p> <p>Steel deck 0.11</p> <p>Steel beam 0.20</p> <p>Ceiling and services <u>0.15</u></p> <p>Total <u>2.89</u></p> <p><u>Variable actions</u></p> <p>Construction stage kN/m²</p> <p>Construction loading Inside and outside the working area 0.75</p> <p>Concrete slab <u>2.52</u></p> <p>Total <u>3.27</u></p> <p>Composite stage kN/m²</p> <p>Imposed floor load 3.30 (See structural arrangement and loading)</p>	<p>Construction stage: g_k= 0.31 kN/m²</p> <p>Composite stage: g_k= 2.89 kN/m²</p> <p>Construction stage: q_k= 3.27 kN/m²</p> <p>Composite stage: q_k = 3.30 kN/m²</p>
<p>BS EN 1990 NA.2.2.3.2 Table NA.A1.2(B)</p>	<p><u>Ultimate limit state (ULS)</u></p> <p>Partial factors for actions</p> <p>Partial factor for permanent actions $\gamma_G = 1.35$</p> <p>Partial factor for variable actions $\gamma_Q = 1.5$</p> <p>Reduction factor $\xi = 0.925$</p> <p>Design value of combined actions, $\xi \gamma_G g_k + \gamma_Q q_k$</p> <p><u>Construction stage</u></p> <p>= (0.925 × 1.35 × 0.31) + (1.5 × 3.27) = 5.29 kN/m²</p> <p>Total load F_d = 5.29 × 7.5 × 3.5 = 138.86 kN</p>	<p>Construction stage F_d = 138.86 kN</p>
<p>BS EN 1990 Eqn 6.10b NA 2.2.3.2 Table NA A1.2(B)</p>		

<p>BS EN 1993-1-1 NA 2.15 BS EN 1992-1-1 NA 2 Table NA.1 NA 2.3 NA 2.4</p> <p>BS EN 1993-1-1 NA 2.4 BS EN 1993-1-1 3.2.6(1)</p>	<p><u>Composite stage:</u></p> $= (0.925 \times 1.35 \times 2.89) + (1.5 \times 3.3) = 8.56 \text{ kN/m}^2$ <p>Total load $F_d = 8.56 \times 7.5 \times 3.5 = 224.7 \text{ kN}$</p> <p><u>Design values of moment and shear force at ULS</u></p> <p><u>Construction stage</u> Maximum design moment (at mid span) $M_{y,Ed} = F_d L/8 = (138.86 \times 7.5) / 8 = 130.18 \text{ kNm}$</p> <p><u>Composite stage</u> Maximum design moment (at mid span) $M_{y,Ed} = F_d L/8 = (224.7 \times 7.5) / 8 = 210.65 \text{ kNm}$</p> <p>Maximum design shear force (at supports) $V_{Ed} = F_d / 2 = 153/2 = 76.5 \text{ kN}$</p> <p><u>Partial factors for resistance</u></p> <table data-bbox="491 1093 925 1310"> <tr> <td>Structural steel</td> <td>$\gamma_{M0} = 1.0$</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Concrete</td> <td>$\gamma_C = 1.5$</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Reinforcement</td> <td>$\gamma_S = 1.15$</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Shear connectors</td> <td>$\gamma_V = 1.25$</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Longitudinal shear</td> <td>$\gamma_{VS} = 1.25$</td> </tr> </table> <p>The plastic modulus that is required to resist the construction stage maximum design bending moment is determined as:</p> $W_{pl,y} = M_{y,Ed} \gamma_{M0} / f_y = (130.28 \times 10^3 \times 1) / 275 = 473.75 \text{ cm}^3$ <p>From the tables of section properties try section 254 × 146 × 43 UKB, S275, which has $W_{pl,y} = 566 \text{ cm}^3$</p> <p>$t_f < 16 \text{ mm}$, therefore $f_y = 275 \text{ N/mm}^2$</p> <p>Modulus of elasticity $E = 210000 \text{ N/mm}^2$</p>	Structural steel	$\gamma_{M0} = 1.0$	Concrete	$\gamma_C = 1.5$	Reinforcement	$\gamma_S = 1.15$	Shear connectors	$\gamma_V = 1.25$	Longitudinal shear	$\gamma_{VS} = 1.25$	<p>Composite stage $F_d = 224.7 \text{ kN}$</p> <p>$M_{y,Ed} = 130.18 \text{ kNm}$</p> <p>$M_{y,Ed} = 210.65 \text{ kNm}$ $V_{Ed} = 76.5 \text{ kN}$</p>
Structural steel	$\gamma_{M0} = 1.0$											
Concrete	$\gamma_C = 1.5$											
Reinforcement	$\gamma_S = 1.15$											
Shear connectors	$\gamma_V = 1.25$											
Longitudinal shear	$\gamma_{VS} = 1.25$											

<p>BS EN 1992-1-1 3.1.6 NA 2 Table NA 1</p> <p>5.4.1.2</p>	<p>For section classification the coefficient ϵ is:</p> $\epsilon = \sqrt{235/f_y} = \sqrt{235/275} = 0.92$ <p>Outstand flange: flange under uniform compression</p> $c = \frac{(b - t_w - 2r)}{2} = \frac{(147.3 - 7.2 - (2 \times 7.6))}{2}$ $= 62.45 \text{ mm}$ $\frac{c}{t_f} = \frac{62.45}{12.7} = 4.91$ <p>The limiting value for Class 1 is $c/t \leq 9\epsilon = 9 \times 0.92 = 8.28$ $4.91 < 8.28$, Therefore, the flange outstand in compression is Class 1.</p> <p>Internal compression part: web under pure bending $c = d = 219 \text{ mm}$ $c/t_w = 219/7.2 = 30.4$</p> <p>The limiting value for Class 1 is $c/t_w \leq 72\epsilon = 72 \times 0.92 = 66.24$ $30.4 < 66.24$ Therefore, the web in pure bending is Class 1. Therefore, the section is Class 1 under pure bending.</p> <p><u>Composite stage member resistance checks</u> <u>Concrete</u> Design value of concrete compressive strength $f_{cd} = \alpha_{cc} \times f_{ck} / \gamma_C$ $\alpha_{cc} = 0.85$ $f_{cd} = 0.85 \times 25 / 1.5 = 14.2 \text{ N/mm}^2$</p> <p><u>Compression resistance of concrete slab</u> At mid-span the effective width of the compression flange of the composite beam is determined from: $b_{eff} = b_0 + \Sigma b_{ei}$ $b_{ei} = L_e/8 = L/8 = 7.5/8 = 0.93 \text{ m}$ ($L_e = L$ for simply supported beams)</p> <p>Assume a single line of shear studs, therefore, $b_0 = 0$ $b_{eff} = 0 + 2 \times 0.93 = 1.86 < 3.5 \text{ m}$ (beam spacing)</p>	<p>Section is Class 1</p> <p>$f_{cd} = 14.2$ N/mm^2</p> <p>Effective width $b_{eff} = 1.85 \text{ m}$</p>
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<p>6.2.1.2</p>	<p>Compression resistance of concrete slab is determined from: $N_{c,slab} = f_{cd} b_{eff} h_c$ where h_c is the depth of the solid concrete above the decking $N_{c,slab} = 14.2 \times 1850 \times 70 \times 10^{-3} = 1838.9 \text{ kN}$</p> <p><u>Tensile resistance of steel section</u></p> $N_{pl,a} = F_d A_a = \frac{F_y A_a}{\gamma_{M0}}$ $N_{pl,a} = \frac{275 \times 54.8 \times 10^2}{1} \times 10^{-3} = 1507 \text{ kN}$ <p>Location of neutral axis Since $N_{pl,a} < N_{c,slab}$ the plastic neutral axis lies in the concrete flange.</p> <p><u>Design bending resistance with full shear connection</u></p>	<p>Design compressive resistance of slab $N_{c,slab} = 1838.9 \text{ kN}$</p> <p>Design tensile resistance of steel section $N_{pl,a} = 1507 \text{ kN}$</p>
<p>6.2.1</p>	<p>As the plastic neutral axis lies in the concrete flange, the plastic resistance moment of the composite beam with full shear connection is: $M_{pl,Rd} = N_{pl,a} (h_a/2 + h - N_{pl,a} / N_{c,slab} \times h_c/2)$</p> $M_{pl,Rd} = 1507 (259.6/2 + 130 - (1507 / 1838.9 \times 70/2)) \times 10^{-3}$ $M_{pl,Rd} = 348.3 \text{ kNm}$ <p>Bending moment at mid span $M_{y,Ed} = 210.65 \text{ kNm}$</p> $M_{y,Ed} / M_{pl,Rd} = 210.65 / 348.3 = 0.69 < 1$ <p>Therefore, the design bending resistance of the composite beam is adequate, assuming full shear connection.</p> <p><u>Shear connector resistance</u> The design shear resistance of a single shear connector in a solid slab is the smaller of:</p> $P_{Rd} = \frac{0.29 \alpha d^2 \sqrt{f_{ck} E_{cm}}}{\gamma_V}$	<p>Design plastic resistance moment of composite beam $M_{pl,Rd} = 348.3 \text{ kNm}$</p> <p>Design bending resistance is adequate</p>
<p>6.6.3.1</p>	<p><u>Shear connector resistance</u> The design shear resistance of a single shear connector in a solid slab is the smaller of:</p> $P_{Rd} = \frac{0.29 \alpha d^2 \sqrt{f_{ck} E_{cm}}}{\gamma_V}$	

<p>NA 2.3</p> <p>6.6.4.2</p> <p>Eqn 6.23</p>	<p>And</p> $P_{Rd} = \frac{0.8f_u (\pi d^2 / 4)}{\gamma_v}$ <p>$\gamma_v = 1.25$ for a single stud $\alpha = 1$</p> $P_{Rd} = \frac{0.29 \times 1 \times 19^2 \sqrt{25 \times 31 \times 10^3}}{1.25} \times 10^{-3} = 73.7 \text{ kN}$ $P_{Rd} = \frac{0.8 \times 450 (\pi 19^2 / 4)}{1.25} \times 10^{-3} = 81.7 \text{ kN}$ <p>shear resistance of a single shear connector is 73.7 kN</p> <p><u>Influence of deck shape</u></p> <p>Deck crosses the beam (i.e. ribs transverse to the beam) One stud per trough, $n_r = 1.0$</p> <p>Reduction factor</p> $k_t = (0.7/n_r^{1/2})(b_0 h_p)(h_{sc}/h_p - 1) \leq 1$ <p>For trapezoidal profiles, b_0 is the average width of a trough, taken here as $(120 + 170) \div 2 = 145 \text{ mm}$</p> $k_t = (0.7/1^{1/2})(145 \times 60)(100/60 - 1) = 1.13 \text{ but not more than } 1.0$ <p>Therefore, as $k_t = 1.0$ no reduction in shear connector resistance is required. Therefore, $P_{Rd} = 73.7 \text{ kN}$</p> <p><u>Number of shear studs in half span</u></p> <p>Use one shear connector per trough, therefore, Stud spacing along beam = 300 mm Centre line to centre line span of 3.5 m should be reduced to allow for the primary beam width or the column width (assume 305 mm). $n = \frac{3500 - (254/2)}{300} = 12$ stud shear connectors per half span</p>	<p>Design shear resistance of a single shear stud $P_{Rd} = 73.7 \text{ kN}$</p>
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<p>6.6.1.2</p> <p>6.2.1.3</p>	<p><u>Degree of shear connection</u></p> <p>Total resistance of 12 shear connectors</p> $R_q = 12P_{Rd} = 12 \times 73.7 = 884.4 \text{ kN}$ $\frac{R_q}{N_{pl,a}} = \frac{884.4}{1298} = 0.68 < 1.0$ <p>As this is less than 1.0, this beam has partial shear connection. Therefore, the minimum shear connection requirements must be checked, and the moment resistance reassessed.</p> <p><u>Minimum shear connection requirements</u></p> <p>The minimum shear connection requirement is calculated from: (for $L_e < 25\text{m}$):</p> $\eta \geq 1 - (355/f_y)(0.75 - 0.03L_e), \eta \geq 0.4$ <p>For a simply supported beam, L_e is equal to the span.</p> $\eta \geq 1 - (355/275)(0.75 - 0.03 \times 7.5) = 0.32, \eta \geq 0.4$ <p>Therefore the degree of shear connection must be at least 0.4. As shown above, there are a sufficient number of shear connectors to achieve this.</p> <p><u>Design bending moment resistance with partial shear connection</u></p> <p>The design bending moment can conservatively be calculated using:</p> $M_{Rd} = M_{pl,a,Rd} + (M_{pl,Rd} - M_{pl,a,Rd}) \eta$ <p>$M_{pl,a,Rd}$ is the plastic moment resistance of the steel section:</p> $M_{pl,a,Rd} = f_{yd} W_{ply} = 275 \times 566 \times 10^{-3} = 155.65 \text{ kNm}$ <p>So the design bending moment resistance is:</p> $M_{Rd} = 155.65 + (348.3 - 155.65) 0.4 = 232.71 \text{ kNm}$ <p>Bending moment at mid span $M_{y,Ed} = 210.65 \text{ kNm}$</p> $\frac{M_{y,Ed}}{M_{Rd}} = \frac{210.65}{232.71} = 0.9 < 1$	<p>$\eta = 0.68$</p>
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	<p>Therefore, $A_v = 2023.06 \text{mm}^2$</p> $V_{pl,Rd} = V_{pl,a,Rd} = \frac{2023.06 (275 / 1.73)}{1} \times 10^{-3} = 321.58 \text{kN}$ $\frac{V_{Ed}}{V_{pl,Rd}} = \frac{76.5}{321.58} = 0.24 < 1$ <p>Therefore the design resistance to vertical shear is adequate.</p> <p>6.2.2.4 As there is no shear force at the point of maximum bending moment (mid span) no reduction (due to shear) in bending resistance is required.</p> <p><u>Design of the transverse reinforcement</u></p> <p>neglect the contribution of the decking and check the resistance of the reinforced concrete flange to splitting.</p> <p>BS EN 1992-1-1 6.2.4 (4) The area of reinforcement (A_{sf}) can be determined using the following equation:</p> $\frac{A_{sf} F_{yd}}{S_f} > \frac{V_{Ed} h_f}{\text{Cot} \theta_f} \text{ therefore,}$ $\frac{A_{sf}}{S_f} > \frac{V_{Ed} h_f}{F_{yd} \text{Cot} \theta_f}$ <p>where: h_f is the depth of concrete above the metal decking, therefore,</p> <p>6.6.6.4 (1) $h_f = h_c = 70 \text{ mm}$ S_f is the spacing of the transverse reinforcement</p> $f_{yd} = \frac{f_y}{\gamma_s} = \frac{500}{1.15} = 435 \text{N/mm}^2$ <p>For compression flanges $26.5^\circ \leq \theta_f \leq 45^\circ$</p> <p>6.6.6.1 The longitudinal shear stress is the stress transferred from the steel beam to the concrete. This is determined from the minimum resistance of the steel, concrete and shear connectors. with partial shear connection, that maximum force that can be transferred is limited by the</p>	<p>Design vertical shear resistance $V_{pl,Rd} = 321.58 \text{kN}$</p> <p>Design resistance for vertical shear is adequate</p>
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<p>Figure 6.16</p> <p>BS EN 1992-1-1 6.2.4 (4)</p> <p>BS EN 1992-1-1 6.2.4 (4)</p> <p>BS EN 1992-1-1 NA 2 Table NA.1</p>	<p>resistance of the shear connectors over half of the span, and is given by $R_q = 884.4\text{kN}$</p> <p>This force must be transferred over each half-span. As there are two shear planes (one on either side of the beam, running parallel to it), the longitudinal shear stress is:</p> $V_{Ed} = \frac{R_q}{h_f \Delta x} = \frac{884.4 \times 1000}{2 \times 70 \times 3500} = 1.8\text{N/mm}^2$ <p>For minimum area of transverse reinforcement assume $\Theta = 26.5^\circ$</p> $\frac{A_{sf}}{S_f} > \frac{V_{Ed} h_f}{F_{yd} \cot \Theta_f} = \frac{1.8 \times 70}{435 \times \cot 26.5} \times 10^3 = 144.4\text{mm}^2/\text{m}$ <p>Therefore, provide A193 mesh reinforcement ($193\text{mm}^2/\text{m}$) in the slab.</p> <p>contribution of decking is included so the transverse reinforcement provided can be reduced.</p> <p><u>Crushing of the concrete compression strut</u></p> <p>The model for resisting the longitudinal shear assumes compression struts form in the concrete slab</p> <p>Verify that:</p> $V_{Ed} \leq v f_{cd} \sin \Theta_f \cos \Theta_f$ <p>where:</p> $v = 0.6(1 - f_{ck}/250)$ $v = 0.6(1 - 25/250) = 0.54$ $v f_{cd} \sin \Theta_f \cos \Theta_f = 0.54 \times 14.2 \times \sin 26.5 \cos 26.5 = 3.06\text{N/mm}^2$ $V_{Ed} = 1.8\text{N/mm}^2 < 3.06\text{N/mm}^2$ <p>Therefore the crushing resistance of the compression strut is adequate.</p>	<p>Use A193 mesh reinforcement</p>
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<p>BS EN 1992-1-1 Table 3.1 BS EN 1991-1-1 Table A.1</p>	<p><u>Composite slab</u></p> <p>Slab panel – D-E - 4-5</p> <p><u>Floor slab and material properties -</u> Total depth of slab $h = 130$ mm</p> <p><u>Corus profiled steel sheeting CF60 -</u> Thickness of profile $t = 1.0$ mm Depth of profile $h_p = 60$ mm Span $L = 3$ m Effective cross-sectional area of the profile $A_{pe} = 1424$ mm²/m Second moment of area of the profile $I_p = 106.15$ cm⁴/m Yield strength of the profiled deck $f_{yp} = 350$ N/mm² Design value of bending resistance (sagging) $MR_d = 11.27$ KNm/m Height of neutral axis above soffit: $= 30.5$ mm</p> <p><u>Concrete</u> Normal concrete strength class C25/30 Density (normal weight, reinforced) 26 kN/m³ (wet) 25 kN/m³ (dry) Cylinder strength $f_{ck} = 25$ N/mm² Modulus of elasticity $E_{cm} = 31$ kN/mm²</p> <p><u>Actions</u> <u>Concrete weight</u> Self-weight of the concrete slab (volume from decking manufacturer's data) $0.097 \times 26 \times 10^{-6} = 2.52$ kN/m² (wet) $0.097 \times 25 \times 10^{-6} = 2.43$ kN/m² (dry)</p> <p><u>Permanent Actions</u></p> <table border="0"> <tr> <td>Construction stage</td> <td>kN/m²</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Steel deck</td> <td><u>0.11</u></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Total</td> <td><u>0.11</u></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Composite stage</td> <td>kN/m²</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Concrete slab</td> <td>2.43</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Steel deck</td> <td>0.11</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Ceiling and services</td> <td><u>0.15</u></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Total</td> <td><u>2.69</u></td> </tr> </table>	Construction stage	kN/m ²	Steel deck	<u>0.11</u>	Total	<u>0.11</u>	Composite stage	kN/m ²	Concrete slab	2.43	Steel deck	0.11	Ceiling and services	<u>0.15</u>	Total	<u>2.69</u>	<p>Construction stage: $g_k = 0.11$ kN/m² Composite stage: $g_k = 2.69$ kN/m²</p>
Construction stage	kN/m ²																	
Steel deck	<u>0.11</u>																	
Total	<u>0.11</u>																	
Composite stage	kN/m ²																	
Concrete slab	2.43																	
Steel deck	0.11																	
Ceiling and services	<u>0.15</u>																	
Total	<u>2.69</u>																	

<p>BS EN 1991-1-6 NA 2.13</p>	<p><u>Variable actions</u></p> <p>Construction stage kN/m²</p> <p>Construction loading (1) Outside the working area 0.75 (2) Inside the working area (additional) 0.75 (3) Concrete slab <u>2.52</u> Total <u>4.02</u></p> <p>Composite stage kN/m²</p> <p>Imposed floor load 3.30 (See structural arrangement and loading)</p> <p><u>Ultimate limit state (ULS)</u></p>	<p>Construction stage: $q_k = 4.02 \text{ kN/m}^2$ Composite stage: $q_k = 3.30 \text{ kN/m}^2$</p>
<p>BS EN 1990 NA.2.2.3.2 Table NA.A1.2(B)</p>	<p>Partial factors for actions</p> <p>Partial factor for permanent actions $\gamma_G = 1.35$ Partial factor for variable actions $\gamma_Q = 1.5$ Reduction factor $\xi = 0.925$</p>	
<p>BS EN 1990 Eq. (6.10b)</p>	<p>Design value of combined actions, $\xi \gamma_G g_k + \gamma_Q q_k$</p> <p><u>Construction stage</u> $= (0.925 \times 1.35 \times 0.11) + (1.5 \times 4.02) = 6.17 \text{ kN/m}^2$</p> <p><u>Composite stage:</u> $= (0.925 \times 1.35 \times 2.69) + (1.5 \times 3.3) = 8.31 \text{ kN/m}^2$</p> <p>UDL per meter length of beam accounting for bay width of 7.0 m, $F_d = 10.42 \times 7.0 = 72.94 \text{ kN/m}$</p> <p><u>Design moment and shear force</u> <u>Construction Stage</u> The design bending moment per metre width of the steel deck is: $M_{y,Ed} = F_d L^2 / 8 = (6.17 \times 3^2) / 8 = 6.94 \text{ kNm width}$</p>	<p>Construction stage $F_d = 6.17 \text{ kN/m}^2$ Composite stage $F_d = 8.13 \text{ kN/m}^2$</p> <p>$M_{Ed} = 6.94 \text{ kNm/m}$</p>

<p>BS EN 1993- 1-1 NA 2.15 BS EN 1992-1-1 NA 2 Table NA.1</p>	<p>The design shear force per metre width of the steel deck is: $V_{Ed} = F_d L / 2 = (6.17 \times 3) / 2 = 9.26 \text{ kN}$</p> <p><u>Normal Stage</u> The design bending moment per metre width of the steel deck is: $M_{y,Ed} = F_d L^2 / 8 = (8.31 \times 3^2) / 8 = 9.35 \text{ kNm width}$</p> <p>The design shear force per metre width of the steel deck is: $V_{Ed} = F_d L / 2 = (8.31 \times 3) / 2 = 13.07 \text{ kN}$</p> <p><u>Partial factors for resistance</u></p> <p>Structural steel $\gamma_{M0} = 1.0$</p> <p>Concrete $\gamma_C = 1.5$</p> <p>Reinforcement $\gamma_S = 1.15$</p> <p>Longitudinal shear $\gamma_{VS} = 1.25$</p>	<p>$V_{Ed} = 9.26 \text{ kN/m}$</p> <p>$M_{y,Ed} = 9.35 \text{ kNm}$</p> <p>$V_{Ed} = 13.07 \text{ kN}$</p>
<p>BS EN 1992-1-1 NA 2 Table NA.1</p>	<p><u>Design values of material strengths</u> <u>Steel deck</u> Design yield strength</p> $f_{yp,d} = \frac{f_{yp}}{\gamma_{M0}} = \frac{350}{1} = 350 \text{ N/mm}^2$ <p>Concrete Design value of concrete compressive strength</p> $f_{cd} = \alpha_{cc} \times f_{ck} / \gamma_C$ $\alpha_{cc} = 0.85$ $f_{cd} = 0.85 \times 25 / 1.5 = 14.2 \text{ N/mm}^2$	<p>$f_{cd} = 14.2 \text{ N/mm}^2$</p>
<p>BS EN 1993-1-3 6.1.1</p>	<p><u>Verification at the construction stage</u> <u>Bending resistance</u></p> $\frac{M_{y,Ed}}{M_{Rd}} = \frac{6.94}{11.27} = 0.62 < 1$ <p>Therefore the bending moment resistance at the construction stage is adequate</p>	

<p>9.3.2(2)</p> <p>NA 2.15</p> <p>6.2.1.2</p> <p>9.7.2(5)</p>	<p><u>Serviceability Limit State (SLS)</u> <u>Construction Stage Deflections</u> <u>Deflection without ponding</u> At serviceability, loading = 0.11 + 2.52 = 2.63 kN/m</p> $\delta_s = \frac{5F_d L^4}{384EI} = \frac{5 \times 2.63 \times 3^4}{384 \times 210 \times 106.15 \times 10^6} \times 10^6 = 12.4 \text{ mm}$ <p>As this is less than 10% of the slab depth (13 mm), the effects of the additional concrete may be ignored in the design of the steel sheeting.</p> <p>$\delta_{s,max} = L/180$ but 20mm max where the loads from ponding are ignored. $\delta_{s,max} = 3000/180 = 16.6 \text{ mm}$, OK</p> <p><u>Verification of the composite slab</u> <u>Ultimate Limit State (ULS)</u> <u>Bending resistance – location of plastic neutral axis(pna)</u></p> <p>Maximum compressive design force per metre in the concrete above the sheeting assuming the pna is below the solid part of the slab is determined as:</p> $N_c = f_{cd} A_c = 14.2 \times 70 \times 1000 \times 10^{-3} = 994 \text{ kN/m}$ <p>Maximum tensile resistance per metre of the profiled steel sheet is determined as:</p> $N_p = f_{yp,d} A_p = 350 \times 1424 \times 10^{-3} = 498.4 \text{ kN/m}$ <p>As $N_p < N_c$ the neutral axis lies above the profiled sheeting.</p> <p>Therefore, the sagging bending moment resistance should be determined</p> <p>The depth of concrete in compression is:</p> $x_{pl} = \frac{A_{pe} f_{yp,d}}{b f_{cd}}$ <p>where: b is the width of the floor slab being considered, here; b = 1000 mm $x_{pl} = \frac{1424 \times 350}{1000 \times 14.2} = 35.1 \text{ mm}$</p> <p><u>Bending resistance – full shear connection</u> For full shear connection, the design moment resistance is:</p>	
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	<p>$M_{pl,Rd} = A_p f_{yd} (d_p - x_{pl}/2)$</p> <p>$d_p = h$ - depth from soffit to centroidal axis of sheeting $d_p = 130 - 30.5 = 99.5$ mm</p> <p>The plastic bending resistance per metre width of the slab is: $= 1424 \times 350 \times (99.5 - 35.1/2) \times 10^{-6} = 40.84$ kNm/m</p> <p>$\frac{M_E}{M_{pl,Rd}} = \frac{9.35}{40.84} = 0.23 < 1$</p> <p>Therefore, the bending moment resistance for full shear connection is adequate.</p> <p><u>Longitudinal shear resistance: m-k method</u></p> <p>9.7.3 The method given in 9.7.3 may be used to determine the design resistance to longitudinal shear ($V_{l,Rd}$). The benefits of end anchorage have been ignored.</p> <p>9.7.3(4) $V_{l,Rd} = \frac{bd_p}{\gamma_{VS}} \frac{(mA_p + k)}{bL_s}$</p> <p>m and k are design values obtained from the manufacturer. $m = 157.2$ N/mm² $k = 0.1232$ N/mm²</p> <p>9.7.3(5) For a uniform load applied to the whole span length; $L_s = L/4 = 3000/4 = 750$mm</p> <p>9.7.3(4) $V_{l,Rd} = \left(\frac{1000 \times 99.5}{1.25} \times \frac{(157.2 \times 1424 + 0.1232)}{1000 \times 750} \right) \times 10^{-3}$ $= 33.56$ kN/m</p> <p>$V_{Ed} = 13.07$ kN/m</p> <p>$\frac{V_{Ed}}{V_{l,Rd}} = \frac{13.07}{33.56} = 0.39 < 1$</p> <p>Therefore, the design resistance to longitudinal shear is adequate.</p>	<p>$M_{pl,Rd} = 40.84$ kNm/m</p>
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<p>BS EN 1992- 1-1 NA 2 Table NA.1</p>	<p><u>Design vertical shear resistance</u></p> $V_{v,Rd} = V_{min} b_s d_p$ <p>The recommended value of v_{min} is,</p> $V_{min} = 0.035 k^{3/2} f_{ck}^{1/2}$ <p>Where, $k = 1 + \sqrt{200/d_p} \leq 2$</p> $k = 1 + \sqrt{200/99.5} = 2.42 \text{ so } k=2$ $V_{min} = 0.035 \times 2^{3/2} \times 25^{1/2} = 0.49 \text{ N/mm}^2$ $V_{v,Rd} = 0.49 \times 99.5 = 48.8 \text{ kN/m, } > 13.19 \text{ kN/m, OK}$ <p>Therefore, the vertical shear resistance is satisfactory. All design checks of the composite slab in the ultimate limit state are satisfied.</p>	
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<p>Unless stated Column in Simple Construction otherwise all references are to BS EN 1993-1-1:2005</p>	<p>Column Design</p> <p>Internal column at ground level – Gridline E5 Column height = 4.0 m</p> <p><u>Actions</u> Reactions at each of the two floor levels from 7.5m span beams: Permanent = $0.5 \times 7.5 \times 7 \times 3.78 = 99.22$ kN Variable = $0.5 \times 7.5 \times 7 \times 3.8 = 99.75$ kN Reactions at each of the two floor levels from 7 m span beams: Permanent = $0.5 \times 7 \times 7.5 \times 3.78 = 99.22$ kN Variable = $0.5 \times 7 \times 7.5 \times 3.8 = 99.75$ kN</p> <p>The total load acting on the column due to two floors is given by: Permanent $G_k = 2 \times (99.22 + 99.22) = 396.88$ kN Variable $Q_k = 2 \times (99.75 + 99.75) = 399$ kN</p>	<p>$G_k = 396.88$ kN $Q_k = 399$ kN</p>
<p>BS EN 1990 Table A1(2)B NA 2.2.3.2 Table NA.A1.2(B)</p>	<p><u>Ultimate Limit State (ULS)</u> Partial factors for actions Partial factor for permanent actions $\gamma_G = 1.35$ Partial factor for variable actions $\gamma_Q = 1.5$ Reduction factor $\xi = 0.925$</p>	
<p>BS EN 1990 6.4.3.2</p>	<p>Design value of combined actions, $\xi \gamma_G g_k + \gamma_Q q_k$ $= (0.925 \times 1.35 \times 396.88) + (1.5 \times 399) = 1094.1$ kN</p>	<p>The ULS axial load, $N_{Ed} = 1094.1$ kN</p>
<p>6.1(1) NA 2.15</p>	<p>At level 1, The reaction from an 7.5 m beam is $0.925 \times 1.35 \times 99.22 + 1.5 \times 99.75 = 273.53$ kN The reaction from an 7 m beam is $0.925 \times 1.35 \times 99.22 + 1.5 \times 99.75 = 273.53$ kN</p> <p>Partial factors for resistance $\gamma_{M0} = 1.0$ $\gamma_{M1} = 1.0$</p>	

<p>NA 2.4 BS EN 10025-2 Table 7</p>	<p><u>Trial section</u> Try 254 × 254 × 73 UKC, S275</p> <p><u>Yield Strength, f_y</u> Steel grade = S275 Nominal thickness of the element, $t < 16$ mm then $f_y = 275$ N/mm²</p>	
<p>Access Steel document SN008a- ENEU</p>	<p><u>Section classification</u> Cross-section is assumed to be at Class 1 or 2.</p> <p><u>Buckling lengths</u> Buckling length about y-y axis $L_{cr,y} = 5.0$ m Buckling length about z-z axis $L_{cr,z} = 5.0$ m</p>	
	<p><u>Design moments on column due to beam reactions</u></p> <p>$M_{y,Ed} \text{ \& } M_{z,Ed} = 0$</p> <p>zero because the beam reactions are equal on either side of the column in this direction as the bay widths and loads are identical.</p>	<p>$M_{y,Ed} = 0$ $M_{z,Ed} = 0$</p>
<p>6.3.1.3</p>	<p><u>Flexural buckling resistance</u></p> <p>$\lambda_1 = 93.9\epsilon = 93.9 \times (235/275)^{0.5} = 86.8$</p> <p>$\bar{\lambda}_z = \frac{L_{cr}/i_z}{\lambda_1} = \frac{5000/64.8}{86.8} = 0.89$</p>	
<p>Table 6.2</p>	<p>$h/b < 1.2$ and $t_f < 100$ mm, so use buckling curve ‘c’ for the z-axis for flexural buckling.</p>	
<p>Figure 6.4</p>	<p>From graph, $\chi_z = 0.61$</p>	
<p>Eq. (6.47)</p>	<p>$N_{b,z,Rd} = \chi_z A f_y / \gamma_{M1} = 0.61 \times 9310 \times 275 \times 10^{-3} / 1.0 = 1562$ kN</p>	<p>$N_{b,z,Rd} = 1562$ kN</p>
<p>6.3.2</p>	<p><u>Lateral torsional buckling resistance moment</u></p> <p>Conservatively the slenderness for lateral torsional buckling may be determined as:</p>	

<p>Access Steel document SN002a-ENEU</p>	$\bar{\lambda}_{LT} = 0.9 \bar{\lambda}_z = 0.9 \times 0.89 = 0.80$	
<p>6.3.2.3</p>	<p>For rolled and equivalent welded sections</p>	
	$X_{LT} = \frac{1}{\Phi_{LT} \pm \sqrt{\Phi_{LT}^2 - \beta \bar{\lambda}_{LT}^2}}$	
	<p>Where,</p> $\Phi_{LT} = 0.5(1 + \alpha_{LT}(\bar{\lambda}_{LT} - \bar{\lambda}_{LT,0}) + \beta \bar{\lambda}_{LT}^2)$	
<p>6.3.2.3 NA 2.17</p>	$\bar{\lambda}_{LT,0} = 0.4$ $\beta = 0.75$	
<p>Table 6.5</p>	<p>For rolled bi-symmetric I-sections with $h/b \leq 2$: use buckling curve 'b'.</p>	
<p>Table 6.3</p>	<p>For buckling curve 'b', $\alpha_{LT} = 0.34$</p>	
	$\Phi_{LT} = 0.5(1 + 0.34(0.80 - 0.40) + 0.75 \times 0.80^2) = 0.81$	
	$X_{LT} = \frac{1}{0.81 \pm \sqrt{0.81^2 - 0.75 \times 0.8^2}} = 0.81$	
<p>6.3.2.3</p>	<p>But the following restrictions apply:</p> $X_{LT} \leq 1$ $X_{LT} \leq 1 / \bar{\lambda}_{LT}^2 = 1 / 0.8^2 = 1.56$ $X_{LT} = 0.81$	
<p>6.3.2.1(3)</p>	<p>$M_{b,Rd} = \frac{X_{LT} W_{pl,y} f_y}{\gamma_{M1}}$ for Class 1 or 2 cross-sections</p>	
	$= \frac{0.81 \times 992 \times 275 \times 10^{-3}}{1} = 221 \text{ kNm}$	
		<p>$M_{b,Rd} = 221 \text{ kNm}$</p>

<p>SN048a- EN- GB Access Steel document</p>	<p><u>Combined bending and axial compression buckling</u></p> <p>Instead of equation 6.61 and 6.62, the simplified expression given below is used:</p> $\frac{N_{Ed}}{N_{b,z,Rd}} + \frac{M_{y,Ed}}{M_{b,Rd}} + 1.5 \frac{M_{z,Ed}}{M_{z,Rd}} \leq 1$ $\frac{1094.1}{1562} + 0 + 0 = 0.7 \leq 1$ <p>Therefore a 254 × 254 × 73 UKC is adequate</p>	<p>Section used is 254×254×73 UKC, S275</p>
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<p>Unless stated otherwise all references are to BS EN 1993-1-1 and its National Annex</p>	<p><u>Column base connection</u></p> <p>Gridline E5</p> <p>Characteristic force due to permanent action, $F_{G,k} = 396.88$ kN</p> <p>Characteristic force due to variable action, $F_{Q,k} = 399$ kN</p>	
<p>BS EN 1990-1-1 NA 2.2.3.2 Table NA A1.2(B)</p>	<p><u>Ultimate Limit State (ULS)</u></p> <p>Partial factors for actions</p> <p>Partial factor for permanent actions $\gamma_G = 1.35$</p> <p>Partial factor for variable actions $\gamma_Q = 1.5$</p> <p>Reduction factor $\xi = 0.925$</p>	
<p>BS EN 1990 6.4.3.2</p>	<p>Design value of combined actions,</p> $\xi \gamma_G g_k + \gamma_Q q_k$ $= (0.925 \times 1.35 \times 396.88) + (1.5 \times 399) = 1142 \text{ kN}$	<p>Axial force $N_{Ed} = 1142$ kN</p>
<p>6.1(1) NA 2.15</p>	<p>Partial factors for resistance</p> $\gamma_{M0} = 1.0$ $\gamma_{M2} = 1.25$	
<p></p>	<p><u>Base plate details</u></p>	
<p>BS EN 1992-1-1 Table 3.1</p>	<p>Strength of foundation concrete to be C25/30</p> $f_{ck} = 30$ N/mm ²	
<p>BS EN 1992-1-1 NA 2 Table NA 1 BS EN 1992-1-1 NA 2 Table NA 1</p>	$f_{cd} = \frac{\alpha_{cc} f_{ck}}{\gamma_c}$ <p>α_{cc} to be taken as 0.85 for axial loading</p> $\gamma_c = 1.5$	
	$f_{cd} = \frac{\alpha_{cc} f_{ck}}{\gamma_c} = \frac{0.85 \times 30}{1.5} = 17 \text{ N/mm}^2$	<p>$f_{cd} = 17 \text{ N/mm}^2$</p>

<p>BS EN 1993-1-8 6.2.5(4)</p>	<p>Area required = $\frac{1094.1 \times 10^3}{17} = 64358.8 \text{ mm}^2$</p> <p>Effective area $\approx 4c^2 + \text{Section perimeter} \times c + \text{section area}$ where c is the cantilever outstand of the effective area,</p> <p>$64358.8 = 4c^2 + 1490c + 9310$ $c = 33.86 \text{ mm}$</p> <p>$\frac{h-2t_f}{2} = \frac{254.1 - 2 \times 14.2}{2} = 112.9 \text{ mm} > 33.86 \text{ mm}$</p> <p>Therefore there is no overlap between the flanges</p> <p><u>Thickness of base plate (t_p)</u></p> <p>$t_p = c (3f_{cd} / f_y \gamma_{M0})^{0.5}$</p> <p>$t_p = 33.86 (3 \times 17 / 275 \times 1)^{0.5} = 14.58 \text{ mm}$</p> <p>$t_p < 40$, therefore nominal design strength = 275 N/mm^2. Adopt 20mm thick base plate in S275 material</p> <p><u>Connection of base plate to column</u></p> <p>It is assumed that the axial force is transferred by direct bearing, which is achieved by normal fabrication processes. Only nominal welds are required to connect the baseplate to the column, though in practice full profile 6mm fillet welds are often used.</p> <p>The column is assumed to be pin-ended. However it is crucial the column is stable during the erection phase therefore 4 bolts outside the column profile should be used.</p>	<p>$t_p = 20 \text{ mm}$</p>
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(BS 8110-97)

Foundation - Isolated Footing

Size of the column shaft = 300 x300mm
Safe bearing capacity of the soil (SBC) = 250 kN/m²

Axial force N_{Ed} = 1142 kN

Serviceability limit

Total load = serviceability load + 8 % of serviceability load

$$\begin{aligned} &= 1142 + 91.36 \\ &= 1233 \text{ kN} \end{aligned}$$

Size of the footing

So, the required area of the footing, $A = \text{Total load} / \text{SBC}$
 $= 1233 / 250$
 $= 4.93 \text{ m}^2$

Now for square footing, $B^2 = A$
 $B = (4.93)^{1/2}$
 $= 2.22 \text{ m}$

Provide a square footing of size = 2.4 x 2.4

Self-weight of footing

Assume the overall depth of footing (h) = 450 mm
Self-weight of the footing = area x h x density of concrete
 $= 2.4 \times 2.4 \times .45 \times 24$
 $= 55.29 \text{ kN}$

Actual total load (w) = Serviceability load + Self-weight of footing
 $= 1233 + 55.29 \text{ kN}$
 $= 1288.3 \text{ kN}$

Actual earth pressure (P_s) = w / (plan area of the base)
 $= 1288.3 / (2.4 \times 2.4)$
 $= 223 \text{ kN}$

$P_s < \text{bearing capacity of soil}$
 $223 < 250$

<p>CI 3.4.4.4</p>	<p><u>Design moment</u></p> <p>Max. design moment (M) = resultant force x length (Occurs at face of column)</p> $= 223 \times 1 \times \frac{1}{2} \times 2.4$ $= 267.6 \text{ kNm}$ <p><u>Ultimate moment</u></p> <p>Assume bar diameter 10 mm and cover 50mm</p> <p>Hence average effective depth of reinforcement is</p> $d_{\text{avg}} = h - \text{cover} - \text{diameter}$ $= 450 - 50 - 10 = 390 \text{ mm}$ <p>Ultimate design moment (M_u) = $0.156 f_{cu} b d^2$</p> $= 0.156 \times 30 \times 2400 \times 390^2 / 10^6$ $= 1708.38 \text{ kNm}$ <p>Since $M < M_u$ no compression r/f not required</p> <p><u>Main steel</u></p> $K = M / b d^2 f_{cu}$ $= 1708.38 \times 10^6 / (2400 \times 390^2 \times 30)$ $= 0.156$ $K \leq 0.156$ <p>Hence, no required compression r/f</p> $Z = d(0.5 + \sqrt{(0.25 - K/0.9)})$ $= d(0.5 + \sqrt{(0.25 - 0.156/0.9)})$ $= 0.78d$ $= 0.78d < 0.95d$ <p>Hence $Z = 0.78 \times 390 = 304.2 \text{ mm}$</p> $A_{s \text{ req}} = M / 0.95 f_y Z$ $= 267.6 \times 10^6 / (0.95 \times 460 \times 172.9)$ $= 3541.68 \text{ mm}^2$ <p><u>Check for minimum steel</u></p> $A_{s \text{ min}} \leq 0.24 \% A_c$ $= 0.24 / 100 \times (2400 \times 450) = 2592 \text{ mm}^2$ <p>Hence $A_s = 3541.68 \text{ mm}^2$</p>	
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<p>Cl 3.11.4.5</p>	<p>No of bars = $3541.68/78.54=45$</p> <p>Spacing = $2400/45=103.37$ Hence spacing 100mm</p> <p>(T10 area =78.54)</p> <p><u>Punching shear</u></p> <p>Critical perimeter P_{cr} , is P_{cr} =(column perimeter + 8 x 1.5 d) or P_{cr} = 4 (225+3 d)</p> <p>P_{cr} = 4 x 300 + 8 x 1.5 x 390=5880</p> <p>Area within perimeter = $(300+3d)^2=(300+3x390)^2$ =2160900mm²</p> <p>Ultimate punching force v is</p> <p>V= load on the shaded area = $107.58 \times (2.0 \times 2.0 - 2.16)$ = $107.58 \times (4 - 2.16)$ = 197.95 kN</p> <p>Design punching shear stress v is</p> <p>$v = V / (P_{cr} \times d)$ = $197.95 \times 1000 / (5880 \times 390)$ = 0.08</p> <p>$0.8 (f_{cu})^{1/2}$ or 5 = $4.8 > 0.08$</p>	
<p>Table 3.8</p>	<p>Design concrete shear stress V_c</p> <p>$V_c = 0.79 \{ 100A_s / (bvd) \}^{1/3} (400/d)^{1/4} / \gamma_m$</p> <p>$\{ 100A_s / (bvd) \}^{1/3} = \{ 100 \times 1423.82 / (2000 \times 390) \}^{1/3} = 0.56$</p> <p>$(400/d)^{1/4} = (400/390)^{1/4} = 1.0$ γ_m</p> <p>$V_c = 0.79 \{ 100A_s / (bvd) \}^{1/3} (400/d)^{1/4} / \gamma_m$ = $0.79 (0.56 \times 1) / 1.25$ = 0.35 0.35 > 0.08</p>	

	<p>Since $V_c > v$ Punching failure is unlikely and a 450 mm depth of footing is acceptable.</p>	
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Unless stated otherwise all references are to BS EN 1993-1-1

Roof Truss

The truss uses hollow sections for its tension chord, rafters, and internal members. The truss is fully welded. Truss analysis is carried out by placing concentrated loads at the joints of the truss. All of the joints are assumed to be pinned in the analysis and therefore only axial forces are carried by members.

NA 2.2.3.2
Table
NA.A1.2(B)

Ultimate limit state (ULS)

Partial factors for actions

Partial factor for permanent actions $\gamma_G = 1.35$

Partial factor for variable actions $\gamma_Q = 1.5$

Reduction factor $\xi = 0.925$

Design value of combined actions, using equation 6.10b

$$= 0.925 \times 1.35 \times 0.9 + 1.5 \times 0.6 = 2.02 \text{ kN/m}^2$$

Design values of combined actions on purlins supported by truss For the distance of 3.5 m between purlins centre to centre

$$\text{Design value} = 2.02 \times 3.5 / \cos 15^\circ = 7.32 \text{ kN/m}$$

Design value of combined actions on truss

For a purlin span of 6 m

$$F_d = 7.32 \times 6 = 43.92 \text{ kN}$$

$F_d = 43.92$
kN

<p>6.1(1) NA 2.15</p> <p>NA 2.4 BS EN 10210-1</p> <p>Table A3</p> <p>Table 5.2</p>	<p><u>Truss analysis (due to forces F_d)</u> Reaction force at support A $R_A = 2 \times F_d = 87.8 \text{ kN}$</p> <p>At joint A $F_{AB} \times \sin 15^\circ + (R_A - W/2) = 0$ $F_{AB} \times \cos 15^\circ + F_{AC} = 0$</p> <p>At joint B $F_{BC} + W \times \cos 15^\circ = 0$ $F_{BD} - F_{AB} - W \times \sin 15^\circ = 0$</p> <p>At joint C $F_{BC} \times \sin 75^\circ + F_{CD} \times \sin 30^\circ = 0$ $F_{CE} - F_{AC} - F_{BC} \times \cos 75^\circ + F_{CD} \times \cos 30^\circ = 0$</p> <p>Partial factors for resistance $\gamma_{M0} = 1.0$ $\gamma_{M1} = 1.0$ $\gamma_{M2} = 1.25$</p> <p>Design of Top Chords (members AB, BD, DG, GH) Maximum design force (member AB and GH) = 255 kN (compression) Try 100 × 100 × 6.3 square hollow section in S355 steel</p> <p>Material properties: modulus of elasticity $E = 210000 \text{ N/mm}^2$ steel grade S355 and thickness × 16 mm Yield strength $f_y = 355 \text{ N/mm}^2$</p> <p>$\varepsilon = \sqrt{235/f_y} = \sqrt{235/355} = 0.81$</p> <p>Classification of the cross-section: $c = 100 - 3 \times 5 = 85 \text{ mm}$ $\frac{c}{t} = \frac{85}{5} = 17$ Class 3 limit = $42e = 42 \times 0.81 = 34$. $17 < 34$, so the section is at least class 3</p>	<p>$F_{AB} = -255 \text{ kN}$ $F_{AC} = 246 \text{ kN}$</p> <p>$F_{BC} = -42 \text{ kN}$ $F_{BD} = -243 \text{ kN}$</p> <p>$F_{CD} = 82 \text{ kN}$ $F_{CE} = 164 \text{ kN}$</p> <p>$N_{Ed} = 255 \text{ kN}$</p> <p>The section is at least Class 3</p>
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<p>Eq.(6.10) for Class 3 sections</p>	<p>Compression resistance of the cross-section:</p> $N_{c,Rd} = \frac{A_{fy}}{\gamma_{M0}} = \frac{1870 \times 355 \times 10^3}{1} = 633 \text{ kN}$ $\frac{N_{Ed}}{N_{c,Rd}} = \frac{255}{633} = 0.4 < 1.0$ <p>Therefore, the compressive design resistance is adequate.</p>	<p>$N_{c,Rd} > N_{Ed}$</p>
<p>Eq.(6.50) for Class 1,2 and 3 crosssections</p>	<p><u>Flexural buckling resistance:</u></p> <p>Determine the non-dimensional slenderness for flexural buckling:</p> $\bar{\lambda}_z = \frac{\sqrt{A_{fy}}}{\sqrt{N_{cr}}} = \frac{L_{cr}}{I_z} \frac{1}{\lambda_1}$ <p>where $L_{cr} = 1.0 \times L_{AB} = \frac{3500}{\cos 15^\circ} = 3623 \text{ mm}$</p> $\lambda_1 = \pi \sqrt{\frac{E}{f_y}} = \pi \sqrt{\frac{210000}{355}} = 76.4$ $\bar{\lambda} = \frac{\sqrt{A_{fy}}}{\sqrt{N_{cr}}} = \frac{3623}{38.6} \frac{1}{76.4} = 1.23$	
<p>Eq.(6.49) and Tables 6.1 and 6.2</p>	<p>Determine the reduction factor due to buckling</p> $X = \frac{1}{\Theta + \sqrt{\Theta^2 - \bar{\lambda}^2}}$ <p>where:</p> $\Theta = 0.5(1 + \alpha(\bar{\lambda} - 0.2) + \bar{\lambda}^2)$ <p>$\alpha = 0.21$ (use buckling curve 'a' for a SHS)</p> $\Theta = 0.5(1 + 0.21(1.23 - 0.2) + 1.23^2) = 1.36$ $X = \frac{1}{\Theta + \sqrt{\Theta^2 - \bar{\lambda}^2}}$ $X = \frac{1}{1.36 + \sqrt{1.36^2 - 1.23^2}} = 0.52$	

	<p> $N_{b,Rd} = \frac{\chi_z A_{fy}}{\gamma_{M1}} = \frac{0.52 \times 1870 \times 355 \times 10^{-3}}{1} = 345 \text{ kN}$ </p> <p> $\frac{N_{Ed}}{N_{b,Rd}} = \frac{255}{345} = 0.71 < 1.0, \text{ OK}$ </p> <p>Therefore, the design flexural buckling resistance of the selected $100 \times 100 \times 6.3$ SHS is satisfactory.</p> <p>Design of bottom chords (members AC, CE, EH) Maximum design force (member AC and EH) = 246 kN (in tension) The bottom chord will also be a $100 \times 100 \times 6.3$ SHS, S355. By inspection, the design tension resistance is equal to the design plastic resistance of the cross section.</p> <p>Eq.(6.6) $N_{pl,Rd} = \frac{A f_y}{\gamma_{M0}} = \frac{1870 \times 355 \times 10^{-3}}{1} = 663 \text{ kN}$ $663 \text{ kN} > 246 \text{ kN}, \text{ OK}$ </p> <p><u>Design of internal members (members BC, EG, CD, DE)</u></p> <p>Maximum design compression force (BC and EG) = 42 kN Maximum design tension force (CD and DE) = 82 kN Maximum length in compression is BC and EG = 970 mm Try a $70 \times 70 \times 5$ SHS, in S355 steel.</p> <p>Material properties:</p> <p>modulus of elasticity $E = 210000 \text{ N/mm}^2$ steel grade S355 and thickness $\times 16 \text{ mm}$ Yield strength $f_y = 355 \text{ N/mm}^2$</p> <p>Table 5.2 $\varepsilon = \sqrt{235/f_y} = \sqrt{235/355} = 0.81$ </p> <p>Classification of the cross-section: $c = 100 - 3 \times 5 = 85 \text{ mm}$ $\frac{c}{t} = \frac{85}{5} = 17$</p>	<p>$N_{b,Rd} > N_{Ed}$</p> <p>$N_{Ed} = 246 \text{ kN}$</p> <p>$N_{pl,Rd} > N_{Ed}$</p> <p>$N_{Ed} = 42 \text{ kN}$</p>
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<p>Eq.(6.10) for Class 3 sections</p>	<p>Class 3 limit = $42e = 42 \times 0.81 = 34$. $17 < 34$, so the section is at least class 3</p> <p>Compression resistance of the cross-section:</p> $N_{c,Rd} = \frac{A_{fy}}{\gamma_{M0}} = \frac{1870 \times 355 \times 10^3}{1} = 633 \text{ kN}$ $\frac{N_{Ed}}{N_{c,Rd}} = \frac{255}{633} = 0.4 < 1.0$ <p>Therefore, the compressive design resistance is adequate.</p>	<p>The section is at least Class 3</p>
<p>Eq.(6.50) for Class 1,2 and 3 crosssections</p>	<p><u>Flexural buckling resistance:</u></p> <p>Determine the non-dimensional slenderness for flexural buckling:</p> $\bar{\lambda}_z = \sqrt{\frac{A_{fy}}{N_{cr}}} = \frac{L_{cr}}{I_z} \frac{1}{\lambda_1}$ <p>where $L_{cr} = 1.0 \times L_{AB} = \frac{3500}{\cos 15^\circ} = 3623 \text{ mm}$</p> $\lambda_1 = \pi \sqrt{\frac{E}{f_y}} = \pi \sqrt{\frac{210000}{355}} = 76.4$ $\bar{\lambda} = \sqrt{\frac{A_{fy}}{N_{cr}}} = \frac{3623}{38.6} \frac{1}{76.4} = 1.23$	<p>$N_{c,Rd} > N_{Ed}$</p>
<p>Eq.(6.49) and Tables 6.1 and 6.2</p>	<p>Determine the reduction factor due to buckling</p> $X = \frac{1}{\Theta + \sqrt{\Theta^2 - \bar{\lambda}^2}}$ <p>where:</p> $\Theta = 0.5(1 + \alpha(\bar{\lambda} - 0.2) + \bar{\lambda}^2)$ <p>$\alpha = 0.21$ (use buckling curve 'a' for a SHS)</p> $\Theta = 0.5(1 + 0.21(1.23 - 0.2) + 1.23^2) = 1.36$ $X = \frac{1}{\Theta + \sqrt{\Theta^2 - \bar{\lambda}^2}}$	

<p>BS EN 1993- 1-1 NA 2.23</p>	<p> $X = \frac{1}{1.36 + \sqrt{1.36^2 - 1.23^2}} = 0.52$ </p> <p> $N_{b,Rd} = \frac{\chi_z A_{fy}}{\gamma_{M1}} = \frac{0.52 \times 1870 \times 355 \times 10^{-3}}{1} = 345 \text{ kN}$ </p> <p> $\frac{N_{Ed}}{N_{b,Rd}} = \frac{255}{345} = 0.71 < 1.0, \text{ OK}$ </p> <p>Therefore, the design flexural buckling resistance of the selected 70 × 70 × 5 SHS is satisfactory.</p> <p><u>Serviceability limit state (SLS)</u> The UK National Annex provides suggested limits for vertical and horizontal deflections. The National Annex also states that the deflections should be checked under unfactored variable loads and that permanent loads should not be included. Partial factors for actions</p> <p><u>Partial factor for variable actions</u></p> <p>$\gamma_c = 1.0$ Design value of combined actions = 1.0 × 0.6 = 0.6 kN/m² Design value of combined actions on truss = 6 × 0.6 × 3.5 / Cos 15° = 13.0 kN</p> <p><u>Deflection</u> The maximum allowable deflection is assumed to be</p> <p>Span/300 = 14000/300 = 46.67 mm. The maximum deflection of the truss is obtained for the SLS value of combined actions (i.e. F_d = 13.4 kN). The deflection at the apex was found to 6.4 mm when all of the joints are assumed to be pinned. Deflection is therefore satisfactory.</p>	<p>F_d = 13.0 kN</p>
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<p>PUntless stated otherwise all references are to BS EN 1993-1-1</p> <p>BS EN 1991-1-4</p> <p>BS EN 1990 NA 2.2.3.2 Table NA.A1.2(B)</p> <p>BS EN 1990 NA 2.2.2 Table NA.A1.1</p>	<p><u>Bracing</u></p> <p><u>Forces in the bracing system</u></p> <p>Total overall unfactored wind load $F_w = 925$ kN With two braced bays, total unfactored load to be resisted by each braced bay = $0.5 \times 925 = 463$ kN</p> <p><u>Actions</u></p> <p><u>Roof</u> Permanent action = 0.9 kN/m² Variable action = 0.6 kN/m²</p> <p><u>Floor</u> Permanent action = 3.7 kN/m² Variable action = 3.3 kN/m²</p> <p><u>Ultimate limit state (ULS)</u></p> <p><u>Partial factors for actions</u></p> <p>Partial factor for permanent actions $\gamma_G = 1.35$ Partial factor for variable actions $\gamma_Q = 1.5$ Reduction factor $\xi = 0.925$</p> <p>ω_0 factors For imposed floor loads (office areas) $\omega_0 = 0.7$ For snow loads on roofs ($H \leq 1000$m a.s.l) $\omega_0 = 0.5$</p> <p><u>Design wind load at ULS</u> Using Equation 6.10b with wind as the leading variable action, the design wind load per braced bay is: $F_{Ed} = 1.5 \times 463 = 695$ kN Distributing this total horizontal load as point loads at roof and floor levels, in proportion to the storey heights:</p> <p>Roof level $\frac{2.25}{18.5} \times 695 = 85$ kN</p>	
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	<p>2nd floor level $\frac{4.45}{18.5} \times 695 = 169\text{kN}$</p> <p>1st floor level $\frac{4.75}{18.5} \times 695 = 178\text{kN}$</p> <p>Ground at column base level $\frac{2.5}{18.5} \times 695 = 94\text{kN}$</p> <p>Assume that this load is taken out in shear through the ground slab and is therefore not carried by the frame.</p> <p><u>Equivalent horizontal forces</u> With wind as the leading variable action, the design values of the combined floor and roof actions are: Design value for combined roof actions $= 0.925 \times 1.35 \times 0.9 + 1.5 \times 0.5 \times 0.6 = 1.57 \text{ kN/m}^2$</p> <p>Design value for combined floor actions $= 0.925 \times 1.35 \times 3.7 + 1.5 \times 0.7 \times 3.3 = 8.09 \text{ kN/m}^2$ Total roof load $= 1.57 \times 14 \times 48 = 1055 \text{ kN}$ Total floor load $= 8.09 \times 14 \times 48 = 5437 \text{ kN}$ Equivalent horizontal forces for each bracing system are:</p> <p>roof level $= \frac{1055}{200} \times 0.5 = 2.64 \text{ kN}$</p> <p>floor level $= \frac{5437}{200} \times 0.5 = 13.6 \text{ kN}$</p> <p><u>Horizontal forces at ground level</u></p> <p>Horizontal design force due to wind $= (85 + 169 + 169 + 178) = 601 \text{ kN}$ Horizontal design force due to equivalent horizontal loads $= 2.64 + 3 \times 13.6 = 43.4 \text{ kN}$ Total horizontal design force per bracing system $= 601 + 43.4 = 644.4 \text{ kN}$</p> <p>Horizontal component of force in bracing member = 644.4 kN Vertical component of force in bracing member = $\frac{644.4}{6} \times 5 = 537.0 \text{ kN}$ Axial force in bracing = $\sqrt{644.4^2 + 537.0^2} = 839 \text{ kN}$</p>	
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<p>NA 2.15 BS EN 1993- 1-8 NA 2.3 Table NA.1</p>	<p>Partial factors for resistance $\gamma_{M0} = 1.0$ $\gamma_{M1} = 1.0$</p>	
<p>NA 2.4 BS EN 10210-1 Table A3 3.2.6 (1)</p>	<p><u>Trial section</u> Try: 219.1 × 10.0 mm thick Circular Hollow Section (CHS), grade S355</p> <p><u>Material properties</u> As $t \leq 16$ mm, for S355 steel</p> <p>Yield strength $f_y = 355$ N/mm²</p> <p>modulus of elasticity $E = 210$ kN/mm²</p>	
<p>5.5 Table 5.2</p>	<p><u>Section classification</u></p> <p>Class 1 limit for section in compression, $d/t \leq 50 \epsilon^2$</p> <p>$\epsilon = (235/f_y)^{0.5}$, $f_y = 355$ N/mm², $\epsilon = 0.82$</p> <p>$d/t \leq 50\epsilon^2 = 50 \times 0.822 = 33.6$</p> <p>Since $21.9 < 33.6$, the section is Class 1 for axial compression</p>	
<p>6.2.4(1) Eq. 6.9</p>	<p><u>Design of member in compression</u> <u>Cross sectional resistance to axial compression</u></p> <p>Basic requirement $\frac{N_{Ed}}{N_{cRd}} \leq 1$</p> <p>$N_{Ed}$ is the design value of the applied axial force $N_{Ed} = 839$ kN $N_{c,Rd}$ is the design resistance of the cross-section for uniform compression</p>	
<p>6.2.4(2) Eq. 6.10</p>	<p>$N_{c,Rd} = \frac{A f_y}{\gamma_{M0}}$ (For Class 1, 2 and 3 cross-sections)</p> <p>$N_{c,Rd} = \frac{6570 \times 355}{1} \times 10^3 = 2332 \text{ kN}$</p>	

	<p> $\frac{N_{Ed}}{N_{c,Rd}} = \frac{839}{2332} = 0.36 < 1$ </p> <p>Therefore, the resistance of the cross section is adequate.</p> <p><u>Flexural buckling resistance</u></p> <p>6.3.1.1(1) Eq. 6.46 For a uniform member under axial compression the basic requirement is:</p> <p> $\frac{N_{Ed}}{N_{b,Rd}} \leq 1$ </p> <p>N_{b,Rd} is the design buckling resistance and is determined from:</p> <p>6.3.1.1(3) Eq. 6.47 $N_{b,Rd} = \frac{\chi A f_y}{\gamma_{M1}}$ = (For Class 1, 2 and 3 cross-sections)</p> <p>6.3.1.2(1) χ is the reduction factor for buckling and may be determined from Figure 6.4.</p> <p>Table 6.2 For hot finished CHS in grade S355 steel use buckling curve 'a' For flexural buckling the slenderness is determined from:</p> <p>6.3.1.3(1) Eq. 6.50 For flexural buckling the slenderness is determined from:</p> <p> $\bar{\lambda}_z = \frac{\sqrt{A f_y}}{\sqrt{N_{cr}}} = \frac{L_{cr}}{i} \frac{1}{\lambda_1}$ </p> <p>where: L_{cr} is the buckling length As the bracing member is pinned at both ends, conservatively take: where $L_{cr} = L = \sqrt{5000^2 + 6000^2} = 7810\text{mm}$</p> <p>Table 5.2 $\lambda_1 = 93.9\varepsilon$</p> <p> $\varepsilon = \frac{\sqrt{235}}{\sqrt{f_y}} = \frac{\sqrt{235}}{\sqrt{355}} = 0.81$ </p> <p>$\lambda_1 = 93.9 \times 0.81 = 76.1$</p>	<p>Use buckling curve 'a'</p> <p>L_{cr} = 7810 mm</p> <p>$\lambda_1 = 76.1$</p>
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<p>6.3.1.3(1) Eq. 6.50</p>	$\bar{\lambda} = \frac{7810}{74} \frac{1}{76.1} = 1.39$	$\bar{\lambda} = 1.39$
<p>Figure 6.4</p>	<p>for $\bar{\lambda} = 1.39$ and buckling curve 'a'</p> <p>$\chi = 0.42$</p> <p>Therefore,</p>	<p>$\chi = 0.42$</p>
<p>6.3.1.1(3) Eq. 6.47</p>	$N_{b,Rd} = \frac{0.42 \times 65.7 \times 10 \times 355 \times 10^3}{1} = 980 \text{ kN}$	<p>Flexural buckling resistance $N_{b,Rd} = 980 \text{ kN}$</p>
<p>6.3.1.1(1) Eq. 6.46</p>	$\frac{N_{Ed}}{N_{b,Rd}} = \frac{839}{980} = 0.86 < 1$ <p>Therefore, the flexural buckling resistance of the section is adequate.</p>	

<p>Unless stated otherwise all references are to BS EN 1993-1-8:2005</p> <p>BS EN 1993-1-1 NA 2.4 BS EN 10025-2 Table 7</p> <p>BS EN 1993-1-1 NA 2.15</p> <p>Access steel document SN013a-ENEU</p>	<p><u>Beam-to-column flexible end plate connection</u></p> <p>Design the beam-to-column connection at level 1 between gridlines E and 5.</p> <p>Initial sizing of the components of the connection Column 254 × 254 × 73 UKC in S275 steel Beam 457 × 191 × 98 UKB in S275 steel</p> <p>For the beam, $f_y = 275 \text{ N/mm}^2$; $f_u = 410 \text{ N/mm}^2$; $h_b = 460 \text{ mm}$; $t_w = 9.9 \text{ mm}$; $t_f = 16 \text{ mm}$</p> <p>For the plate, $f_u = 410 \text{ N/mm}^2$</p> $V_{cRd} \approx \frac{h_b \times t_w \times f_y / \sqrt{3}}{\gamma_{M0}} = \frac{460 \times 9.9 \times 275 / \sqrt{3}}{1} = 723 \text{ kN}$ <p>design shear force at ULS, $V_{Ed} = 230 \text{ kN}$</p> <p>Because $230 < 0.75 V_{cRd}$, a partial depth endplate is proposed. $h_b < 500 \text{ mm}$, so 8 or 10 mm endplate is proposed. End plate depth is minimum $0.6 h_b = 276 \text{ mm}$; propose 280 mm. Assuming M20 bolts, number of bolts = $239/74 = 3.2$ 6 M20 bolts are proposed.</p>	<p>$V_{Ed} = 230 \text{ kN}$</p>
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Bolt details

The bolts are fully threaded, non-preloaded, M20 8.8, 60 mm long,

Tensile stress area of bolt	$A_s = 245 \text{ mm}^2$
Diameter of the holes	$d_o = 22 \text{ mm}$
Diameter of the washer	$d_w = 37 \text{ mm}$
Yield strength	$f_{yb} = 640 \text{ N/mm}^2$
Ultimate tensile strength	$f_{ub} = 800 \text{ N/mm}^2$

3.5, Table 3.3

Limits for locations and spacings of bolts

End distance $e_1 = 55 \text{ mm}$

Minimum = $1.2d_o = 1.2 \times 22 = 26.4 \text{ mm} < 55 \text{ mm}$, OK

Edge distance $e_2 = 50 \text{ mm}$

Limits are the same as those for end distance.

Minimum = $1.2d_o = 1.2 \times 22 = 26.4 \text{ mm} < 50 \text{ mm}$, OK

Spacing (vertical pitch) $p_1 = 85 \text{ mm}$

Minimum = $2.2d_o$

$2.2d_o = 2.2 \times 22 = 48.4 \text{ mm} < 85 \text{ mm}$, OK

$14t_p = 14 \times 10 = 140 \text{ mm} > 85 \text{ mm}$

Spacing (horizontal gauge) $p_3 = 100 \text{ mm}$

Minimum = $2.4d_o$

$2.4d_o = 2.4 \times 22 = 52.8 \text{ mm} < 100 \text{ mm}$, OK

<p>4.7.3 Access Steel document SN014a- EN-EU</p>	<p><u>Weld design</u> For full strength “side” welds Throat (a) $\geq 0.39 \times t_w$ $a \geq 0.39 \times 9.9 = 3.86$ mm; adopt throat (a) of 4mm, leg = 6 mm</p>	<p>Weld throat thickness, a = 4 mm Leg = 6 mm</p>
<p>BS EN 1993-1-1 6.1(1) Table 2.1 BS EN 1993-1-8 NA 2.3 Table NA.1</p>	<p>Partial factors for resistance $\gamma_{M0} = 1.0$ $\gamma_{M2} = 1.25$ (for shear) $\gamma_{M2} = 1.1$ (for bolts in tension)</p>	
<p>SN014a- EN-EU</p>	<p>$t_p \leq d/2.8\sqrt{f_{ub}/f_{yp}}$ or $t_{fc} \leq d/2.8\sqrt{f_{ub}/f_{yc}}$ $t_p \leq 20/2.8\sqrt{800/275} = 12$mm Since $t_p = 10$ mm < 12 mm, ductility is ensured.</p>	
<p>3.6.1 & Table 3.4</p>	<p><u>Joint shear resistance</u> <u>Bolts in shear</u> the shear resistance $F_{v,Rd}$ of a single bolt is given by: $F_{v,Rd} = \frac{\alpha_v f_{ub} A}{\gamma_{M2}}$ For bolt class 8.8, $\alpha_v = 0.6$, therefore, $F_{v,Rd} = \frac{0.6 \times 800 \times 245 \times 10^{-3}}{1.25} = 75.2 \text{ kN}$ For 6 bolts, $V_{Rd,1} = 6 \times 75.2 = 451$ kN</p>	<p>$V_{Rd,1} = 451$ kN</p>
<p>3.6.1 & Table 3.4</p>	<p><u>End plate in bearing</u> The bearing resistance of a single bolt, $F_{b,Rd}$ is given by: $F_{b,Rd} = \frac{k_1 \alpha_b f_{up} d t_p}{\gamma_{M2}}$</p>	

<p>BS EN 1993-1-1 6.2.6(2)</p>	<p>Where:</p> $\alpha_b = \min \left(\alpha_d ; \frac{f_{ub}}{f_{up}} ; 1 \right)$ $\alpha_d = \frac{e_1}{3d_0} \text{ for end bolts and } \frac{p_1}{3d_0} - 1/4 \text{ for inner bolts}$ <p>For end bolts,</p> $\alpha_b = \min \left(\frac{55}{3 \times 22} ; \frac{800}{410} ; 1 \right) \min (0.83; 1.95; 1.0) = 0.83$ <p>For inner bolts,</p> $\alpha_b = \min \left(\frac{85}{3 \times 22} - \frac{1}{4} ; \frac{800}{410} ; 1 \right) \min (1.04; 1.95; 1.0) = 1$ $k_1 = \min(2.8 e_2/d_0 - 1.7; 2.5) = \min((2.8 \times 50/22 - 1.7); 2.5)$ <p>Therefore, $k_1 = \text{minimum} (4.66; 2.5) = 2.5$</p> <p>Therefore, for the end bolts,</p> $F_{bRd} = \frac{2.5 \times 0.83 \times 410 \times 20 \times 10}{1.25} \times 10^{-3} = 136.1 \text{ kN}$ <p>And for the inner bolts,</p> $F_{bRd} = \frac{2.5 \times 1 \times 410 \times 20 \times 10}{1.25} \times 10^{-3} = 164 \text{ kN}$ <p>The bearing resistance of the bolts</p> $= 2 \times 136.1 + 4 \times 164 = 928 \text{ kN}$ <p><u>Beam web in shear</u></p> <p>Shear resistance is checked only for the area of the beam web connected to the end plate. The design plastic shear resistance is given by:</p> $V_{plRd} = V_{Rd8} = \frac{A_v (f_{yb}/\sqrt{3})}{\gamma_{M0}}$ $V_{Rd8} = \frac{280 \times 9.9 (275/\sqrt{3})}{I} \times 10^{-3} = 396 \text{ kN}$ <p>The design shear resistance of the connection is 396 kN, > 230 kN, OK</p>	<p>$V_{Rd,2} = 928$ kN</p> <p>$V_{Rd,8} = 396$ kN</p>
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Annexure 11 - Trial Pit Report

CECB Laboratory Services					Site Mulleriyawa IDH		Trial Pit Number TP01	
Machine : JCB JCX Method : Trial Pit		Dimensions 2.50m X 0.70m X 2.00m				Client MOH		Job Number 7757-05-18
		Location 725947.4 E 720584.4 N		Dates 26/06/2022		Project Contractor Ground Investigations Ireland		Sheet 1/1
Depth (m)	Sample / Tests	Water Depth (m)	Field Records	Level (mOD)	Depth (m) (Thickness)	Description	Legend	Water
						Brown slightly sandy slightly gravelly TOPSOIL with rootlets.		
				21.31	0.40	Brown slightly sandy clayey subangular to rounded fine to coarse GRAVEL with some subrounded cobbles.		
				20.71	1.00	gravelly sand		
				19.71	2.00	Trial pit terminated at scheduled depth. Complete at 2.00m		
						Remarks -No Groundwater encountered. -Trial pit stable. -Trial pit backfilled on completion.		
						Scale (approx) 1:25		

Annexure 12 - Structural drawings

- Column Footing Layout
- Column Layout – Ground Floor
- Column & Beam Layout – First Floor
- Column & Beam Layout – Second Floor
- Roof Plan
- Connection Details
- Roof Truss Details

FOOTING SIZES

TAG	SIZE (L x W x H)	TAG	SIZE (L x W x H)
F1	1350 X 1350 X 305	F36	1900 X 1900 X 405
F2	1650 X 1650 X 305	F37	1350 X 1350 X 305
F3	1500 X 1500 X 305	F38	1650 X 1650 X 305
F4	1650 X 1650 X 305	F39	1950 X 1950 X 355
F5	1800 X 1800 X 355	F40	1900 X 1900 X 405
F6	1650 X 1650 X 305	F41	2300 X 2300 X 455
F7	1500 X 1500 X 305	F42	1900 X 1900 X 405
F8	1650 X 1650 X 305	F43	2050 X 2050 X 455
F9	1350 X 1350 X 305	F44	1650 X 1650 X 305
F10	1900 X 1900 X 405	F45	1350 X 1350 X 305
F11	2250 X 2250 X 455	F46	1900 X 1900 X 405
F12	2100 X 2100 X 405	F47	2250 X 2250 X 455
F13	2200 X 2200 X 455	F48	2100 X 2100 X 405
F14	2450 X 2450 X 505	F49	2200 X 2200 X 455
F15	2200 X 2200 X 455	F50	2450 X 2450 X 505
F16	2100 X 2100 X 405	F51	2200 X 2200 X 455
F17	2250 X 2250 X 455	F52	2100 X 2100 X 405
F18	1900 X 1900 X 405	F53	2250 X 2250 X 455
F19	1350 X 1350 X 305	F54	1900 X 1900 X 405
F20	1650 X 1650 X 305	F55	1350 X 1350 X 305
F21	1950 X 1950 X 355	F56	1650 X 1650 X 305
F22	1900 X 1900 X 405	F57	1500 X 1500 X 305
F23	2300 X 2300 X 455	F58	1650 X 1650 X 305
F24	1900 X 1900 X 405	F59	2050 X 2050 X 455
F25	2050 X 2050 X 455	F60	1650 X 1650 X 305
F26	1650 X 1650 X 305	F61	1500 X 1500 X 305
F27	1350 X 1350 X 305	F62	1650 X 1650 X 305
F28	1900 X 1900 X 405	F63	1350 X 1350 X 305
F29	2300 X 2300 X 455		
F30	1900 X 1900 X 405		
F31	1900 X 1900 X 405		
F32	2300 X 2300 X 455		
F33	1900 X 1900 X 405		
F34	1900 X 1900 X 405		
F35	2300 X 2300 X 455		

COLUMN FOOTING LAYOUT

SCALE 1:250

Client - Ministry Of Health
Design of New Quarantine Hospital for Infectious diseases(IDH) at Kotikawatta, Mulleriyawa, Sri Lanka.
Design & Drawn Team - Group J
Drawn Title : COLUMN FOOTING LAYOUT

COLUMN SIZES

TAG	SIZE (L x W x H)
C1	254x254x73 Kg/m

COLUMN LAYOUT - GROUND FLOOR

SCALE 1:250

Client - Ministry Of Health
Design of New Quarantine Hospital for Infectious diseases(IDH) at Kotikawatta, Mulleriyawa, Sri Lanka.
Design & Drawn Team - Group J

Drawn Title : COLUMN LAYOUT- GROUND FLOOR
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COLUMN & BEAM LAYOUT - FIRST FLOOR

SCALE 1:250

COLUMN SIZES

TAG	SIZE (L x W x H)
C1	254x254x73 Kg/m

BEAM SIZES

TAG	SIZE (L x W x H)	LENGTH (mm)
UB1	457x191x98 Kg/m	6965.0
UB2	356x127x39 Kg/m	5965.0
UB3	356x127x39 Kg/m	4965.0
UB4	457x191x98 Kg/m	7485.0
UB5	457x191x98 Kg/m	6746.0
UB6	254x146x43 Kg/m	6980.0
UB7	254x146x43 Kg/m	5980.0
UB8	254x146x43 Kg/m	4980.0
UB9	254x146x43 Kg/m	7480.0

SLAB DETAIL

SCALE 1:20

Client - Ministry Of Health
Design of New Quarantine Hospital for Infectious diseases(IDH) at Kotikawatta, Mulleriyawa, Sri Lanka.
Design & Drawn Team - Group J
Drawn Title : COLUMN & BEAM LAYOUT- FIRST FLOOR

COLUMN & BEAM LAYOUT - SECOND FLOOR

SCALE 1:250

COLUMN SIZES

TAG	SIZE (L x W x H)
C2	203x203x60 Kg/m

BEAM SIZES

TAG	SIZE (L x W x H)	LENGTH (mm)
UB1	457x191x98 Kg/m	6965.0
UB2	356x127x39 Kg/m	5965.0
UB3	356x127x39 Kg/m	4965.0
UB4	457x191x98 Kg/m	7485.0
UB5	457x191x98 Kg/m	6746.0
UB6	254x146x43 Kg/m	6980.0
UB7	254x146x43 Kg/m	5980.0
UB8	254x146x43 Kg/m	4980.0
UB9	254x146x43 Kg/m	7480.0

SLAB DETAIL

SCALE 1:20

Client - Ministry Of Health
Design of New Quarantine Hospital for Infectious diseases(IDH) at Kotikawatta, Mulleriyawa, Sri Lanka.
Design & Drawn Team - Group J
Drawn Title : COLUMN & BEAM LAYOUT- SECOND FLOOR

BEAM SIZES

TAG	SIZE (L x W x H)	LENGTH (mm)
RB1	178X102X19 Kg/m	6875.0
RB2	178X102X19 Kg/m	5875.0
RB3	178X102X19 Kg/m	4875.0
RB4	178X102X19 Kg/m	7475.0

ROOF PLAN
SCALE 1:250

Client - Ministry Of Health
Design of New Quarantine Hospital for Infectious diseases(IDH) at Kotikawatta, Mulleriyawa, Sri Lanka.
Design & Drawn Team - Group J
Drawn Title: ROOF PLAN

PLAN VIEW

SCALE 1:10

TYPICAL BASE PLATE DETAILS

SCALE 1:10

PLAN VIEW

SCALE 1:10

DETAIL - A

SCALE 1:10

PLAN VIEW

SCALE 1:10

DETAIL - B

SCALE 1:10

PLAN VIEW

SCALE 1:10

DETAIL - C

SCALE 1:10

Client - Ministry Of Health
Design of New Quarantine Hospital for Infectious diseases(IDH) at Kotikawatta, Mulleriyawa, Sri Lanka.
Design & Drawn Team - Group J
Drawn Title : CONNECTION DETAILS

ROOF TRUSS DETAILS- RT01
SCALE 1:30

ROOF TRUSS DETAILS- RT02
SCALE 1:30

Client - Ministry Of Health
Design of New Quarantine Hospital for Infectious diseases(IDH) at Kotikawatta, Mulleriyawa, Sri Lanka.
Design & Drawn Team - Group J
Drawn Title : TRUSS DETAILS

Design Calculation for Plumbing Work

➤ Pump size calculation for Sump,

$$\begin{aligned} Ph(kW) &= q \rho g h / (3.6 \ 106) \\ &= q p / (3.6 \ 106) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where

$Ph(kW)$ = hydraulic power (kW)

q = flow (m³/h)

ρ = density of fluid (kg/m³)

g = acceleration of gravity (9.81 m/s²)

h = differential head (m)

p = differential pressure (N/m², Pa)

theo. Valve -

Hydraulic Power: 0.33 (kW) 0.44 (hp)

Shaft Power: 0.55 (kW) 0.73 (hp)

There for we use 2 hp pump for each tank which is available in market.

➤ *Drainage Design Calculation*

Total Discharge - Gray water – 5.4 L/s

Black Water – 5.1 L/s

So we do design calculation for large blocks where maximum discharge is high.

K valve – Frequency of use is 0.7 for hospital buildings.

And there are two parallel toilet blocks at first floor and second floor. so we connect drainage and waste water lines as same path line but separately as black water and gray water.

$$Q_{ww} = \text{Waste water flow rate} = k \sqrt{(\sum du)}$$

Gray water – 10.8 L/s (for both floors)

$$Q = 2.3 \text{ L/s}$$

Assume *head loss in meters per meter run* as 0.02 for higher accuracy.

Max. Flow rate of gray water pipe= 2.3 liters per second

According to the *Graph 04 Pipe sizing chart – plastic*,

Required minimum diameter of pipe is 75mm OD.

But form usual recommendations, we provided 110mm OD pipe are ok for gray water drainage.

Then, For Bath room internal drainage line

$D_u(\text{max}) = 3.9 \text{ L/s}$

$Q = 1.38$

Here minimum pipe size is 50mm

So we provide 50mm pipes for all gray water outlet individually and connect to 63mm line , then it connect to main drain line (110mm) which carry it to disposal pits

Black water – 10.2 L/s

$Q = 2.2 \text{ L/s}$

Assume *head loss in meters per meter run* as 0.02 for higher accuracy.

Max. Flow rate of gray water pipe= 2.2 liters per second

According to the *Graph 04 Pipe sizing chart – plastic*,

Required minimum diameter of pipe is 75mm OD.

Required minimum diameter of pipe is 75mm OD for Black water.

However usual, we provided 110mm OD pipes for black water drainage commonly

For Washing area Block

$D_u = 1.2$

For 3 machines, total $DU = 3.6$

So, $Q = 1.3 \text{ L/s}$

According to the *Graph 04 Pipe sizing chart – plastic*,

Required minimum diameter of pipe is 50mm OD.

But Usually We provide 63mm pipe for Waste water line, so 63mm pipe is good enough for that.

Annexure 14 - Design Calculations of Septic Tank and Soakage Pit

➤ Septic tank, soakage pit design calculations

(From Quantity of sewage produced = population X per capita)

Assuming usage = 415 persons

Total water demand = 72000L

Sewage/day = 24000 litres

- Assuming detention period = 24 hr = 1 days.

Therefore, quantity of sewage = 24000 X 24/24

During detention period

= 24000 litres

- Assuming rate of sludge deposited = 30lit/capita/day & sludge periods = 1 year.

Therefore, volume of sludge

= rate of sludge deposited X population X sludge period

= 30 X 415 X 1 = 12450 litres.

Therefore, required capacity of tank = 24000 + 12450 = 36450 litres = 37 m³

Assuming depth of tank = 2.7m

Therefore, surface area available = 37/2.7 = 13.7 m²

Assuming length & width ratio i.e. (L: B = 4:1)

Therefore, surface area of tank = L X B

13.7 = 4B X B

B = 1.85 m

Therefore, L = 4B

L = 4X1.85

L = 7.4m

Area of cross-section = L X B = 7.4X1.85

- Therefore surface area of tank calculated above or equal to the 13.77 m² which is satisfy by length width ratio.
- Assuming free board surface 0.3m.

Therefore, depth (d) = 3m

Therefore, a septic tank of size **7.4mX1.85mX3m**

For Hospital - Bed	: 220 lpcd (Litres/bed/day) x 255 = 56100L
For Hospital – staff	: 45 lpcd (Litres/head/day) x 160 = 7200L
Other	: 8500L
Total	: 71800 L = 72000 Leters

By general practice and previous report about health relative projects we assumed here,
 24000L for black water (1/3 of total)
 48000L for Gray water (2/3 of total)

Black water generation = 24000L /day = 24 m³/day

Grey water generation = 48000 /day = 48 m³/day

One soakage pit used just for the black water conveyed through the septic tank (24 m³/day). And used two soakage pits for the grey water generation of 48 m³/day.

Annexure 15 - Design Calculations Electrical

Design calculation - Electrical

➤ Lighting Design

$$\text{No of light fittings} = \frac{\text{Area x Illumination Level (Lux)}}{\text{Lumen per fitting x Utilization Factor x Maintenance Factor}}$$

(See the calculation table)

➤ Demand Calculation

Total lighting fittings capacity for the building (12W and 18W LED)	= 75057W = 75.06 kW
Total 13A Schocket Outlet capacity for the building	= 738 x 200 = 147.6 kW Power
Total industrial Schocket Outlet capacity for the building	= 77 x 500 (avg) = 38.5 kW Power
Fan Points	= 117 x 75 = 8.77 Kw
Requirement for Air Conditioning	
24000 BTU	= 42 x 2000 = 84 kW
36000 BTU	= 4 x 3000 = 12 kW
Pump	= 3 x 2000 = 6KW
Passenger lift	= 20KW
Total Electrical Medical Equipment/services Demand	= 240 KW
Total electrical demand of building (P)	= 631.93 KW = 632Kw

$$\text{Current (A) – 3 phase} = \frac{P \times \text{Diversity factor}}{\sqrt{3} \times \text{Voltage} \times \text{Power factor}}$$

$$\text{Current (A) – 3 phase} = \frac{632 \times 1000 \times 0.60}{\sqrt{3} \times 400 \times 0.80} = 684.9 \text{ A}$$

Where,

Voltage – 400

Diversity factor -60%

Power factor – 0.8

Lighting calculations

Floor Level	Location	Area (ft2)	Area (m2)	Illumination Level (Lux)	Lumen per fitting	Watt	Utilization Factor (η)	Maintanent Factor (mf)	No. of Light Fittings		Total Watts
Ground Floor	Patient admision corridor	1200	111.52	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	38.30	39	468
	Patient waiting area	1723	160.13	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	54.99	55	660
	Disinfection area	1480	137.55	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	47.23	48	576
	Patient admin & guidance area	210	19.52	500.00	1,400.00	18.00	0.80	0.65	13.40	14	252
	Patient Supporting staff restroom	130	12.08	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	4.15	5	60
	Admission Staff Dining area	97	9.01	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	3.10	4	48
	Disabled Toilet	57	5.30	200.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	2.43	3	36
	Staff toilet & Bath area	84	7.81	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	2.68	3	36
	clean. Equi. Area	193	17.94	500.00	1,400.00	18.00	0.80	0.65	12.32	13	234
	cle. Staff manage.	79	7.34	500.00	1,400.00	18.00	0.80	0.65	5.04	6	108
	Toilet	42	3.90	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	1.34	2	24
	chang. Room	49	4.55	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80				-
	saniti. Area	71	6.60	500.00	1,400.00	18.00	0.80	0.65	4.53	5	90
	clen.staff area	153	14.22	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	4.88	5	60
	laundry	318	29.55	500.00	1,400.00	18.00	0.80	0.65	20.30	21	378
	Disinfection Lobby	500	46.47	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	15.96	16	192
	waste disp. Corridor	1200	111.52	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	38.30	39	468
	PTU & ETU	480	44.61	1,000.00	1,400.00	18.00	0.80	0.65	61.28	62	1,116
	Server Room	105	9.76	500.00	1,400.00	18.00	0.80	0.65	6.70	7	126
	Network Room	65	6.04	500.00	1,400.00	18.00	0.80	0.65	4.15	5	90
	Intercom Room	75	6.97	500.00	1,400.00	18.00	0.80	0.65	4.79	5	90
	ICT Room	93	8.64	500.00	1,400.00	18.00	0.80	0.65	5.94	6	108
	CCTV Room	86	7.99	500.00	1,400.00	18.00	0.80	0.65	5.49	6	108
	Pharmacy	60	5.58	500.00	1,400.00	18.00	0.80	0.65	3.83	4	72
Laboratory	260	24.16	500.00	1,400.00	18.00	0.80	0.65	16.60	17	306	
Sampling Room	57	5.30	200.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	2.43	3	36	

	Pharmaceutical Store	377	35.04	200.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	16.04	17	204
	Medical equipment store	435	40.43	200.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	18.51	19	228
	Supply services corridor	1190	110.59	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80				-
	Fire recommeded center	120	11.15	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	3.83	4	48
	dec. clean. Rest area	450	41.82	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	14.36	15	180
	services Toi. Wash area	230	21.38	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	7.34	8	96
	loundry	138	12.83	500.00	1,400.00	18.00	0.80	0.65	8.81	9	162
	Staff Toilet & Bath area1	77	7.16	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	2.46	3	36
	Changing room & locker 1	91	8.46	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	2.90	3	36
	Nurse rest area 1	665	61.80	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	1.65	8.36	9	108
	Nurse rest area 2	1225	113.85	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	39.10	40	480
	Staff Toilet & Bath area2	42	3.90	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	1.34	2	24
	Changing room & locker 2	108	10.04	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	3.45	4	48
	Doc. Rest area	1135	105.48	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	36.22	37	444
	Staff Toilet & Bath area3	42	3.90	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	1.34	2	24
	Changing room & locker 3	98	9.11	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	3.13	4	48
	Medical Staff cooridor	1200	111.52	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	38.30	39	468
First Floor	staff rest area A	500	46.47	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	15.96	16	192
	Staff Toilet A	42	3.90	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	1.34	2	24
	Dis. Passgae	1150	106.88	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	36.70	37	444
	saniti.area A	63	5.86	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	2.01	3	36
	ICU	2347	218.12	1,000.00	1,400.00	18.00	0.80	0.65	299.62	300	5,400
	Theater	945	87.83	1,000.00	1,400.00	18.00	0.80	0.65	120.64	121	2,178
	radiolo. Unit	485	45.07	1,000.00	1,400.00	18.00	0.80	0.65	61.92	62	1,116
	ICU rest area	700	65.06	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	22.34	23	276
	Staff Toilet B	68	6.32	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	2.17	3	36
	saniti.area B	88	8.18	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	2.81	3	36
	saniti.area C	115	10.69	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	3.67	4	48
	staff rest area B	195	18.12	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	6.22	7	84
	Staff Toilet C	36	3.35	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	1.15	2	24

	Wast. Dispo. Equip. store	90	8.36	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	2.87	3	36
	Ward 1	4145	385.22	1,000.00	1,400.00	18.00	0.80	0.65	529.15	530	9,540
	Ward 2	5215	484.67	1,000.00	1,400.00	18.00	0.80	0.65	665.75	666	11,988
	Medicine store	145	13.48	500.00	1,400.00	18.00	0.80	0.65	9.26	10	180
	Dis. Lobby	414	38.48	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	13.21	14	168
	Med.staff pass	520	48.33	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	16.60	17	204
	paitent pass.	550	51.12	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	17.55	18	216
	Doc. Wait area	570	52.97	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	18.19	19	228
	Nurse wait area	795	73.88	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	25.37	26	312
	Doc. Toi.	42	3.90	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	1.34	2	24
	Nur.toi	42	3.90	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	1.34	2	24
	Sani.area	105	9.76	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	3.35	4	48
	Buffer room	154	14.31	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	4.91	5	60
	paitent Toi.M	283	26.30	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	9.03	10	120
	Pait. Toi.F	240	22.30	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	7.66	8	96
Second Floor	staff rest area A	500	46.47	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	15.96	16	192
	Staff Toilet A	42	3.90	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	1.34	2	24
	Dis. Passgae	1150	106.88	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	36.70	37	444
	saniti.area A	63	5.86	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	2.01	3	36
	ICU	2347	218.12	1,000.00	1,400.00	18.00	0.80	0.65	299.62	300	5,400
	Theater	945	87.83	1,000.00	1,400.00	18.00	0.80	0.65	120.64	121	2,178
	radiolo. Unit	485	45.07	1,000.00	1,400.00	18.00	0.80	0.65	61.92	62	1,116
	ICU rest area	700	65.06	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	22.34	23	276
	Staff Toilet B	68	6.32	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	2.17	3	36
	saniti.area B	88	8.18	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	2.81	3	36
	saniti.area C	115	10.69	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	3.67	4	48
	staff rest area B	195	18.12	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	6.22	7	84
	Staff Toilet C	36	3.35	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	1.15	2	24
	Wast. Dispo. Equip. store	90	8.36	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	2.87	3	36
	Ward 1	4145	385.22	1,000.00	1,400.00	18.00	0.80	0.65	529.15	530	9,540

Ward 2	5215	484.67	1,000.00	1,400.00	18.00	0.80	0.65	665.75	666	11,988
Medicine store	145	13.48	500.00	1,400.00	18.00	0.80	0.65	9.26	10	180
Dis. Lobby	414	38.48	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	13.21	14	168
Med.staff pass	520	48.33	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	16.60	17	204
paitent pass.	550	51.12	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	17.55	18	216
Doc. Wait area	570	52.97	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	18.19	19	228
Nurse wait area	795	73.88	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	25.37	26	312
Doc. Toi.	42	3.90	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	1.34	2	24
Nur.toi	42	3.90	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	1.34	2	24
Sani.area	105	9.76	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	3.35	4	48
Buffer room	154	14.31	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	4.91	5	60
paitent Toi.M	283	26.30	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	9.03	10	120
Pait. Toi.F	240	22.30	150.00	840.00	12.00	0.80	0.65	7.66	8	96
									4,442	74,652

Power Demand calculation Items

Floor Level	Location	13A Socket outlet	Industrial Socket outlet	AC	Fan
Ground Floor	Patient admision corridoor	2.00			
	Patient waiting area	12.00	2.00		5.00
	Disinfection area				3.00
	Patient admin & guidance area	3.00	1.00		4.00
	Patient Supporting staff restroom	3.00			1.00
	Admission Staff Dining area	2.00			1.00
	Disabled Toilet	1.00			
	Staff toilet & Bath area	1.00			
	clean. Equi. Area	2.00			1.00
	cle. Staff manage.	1.00			1.00
	Toilet	1.00			
	chang. Room	1.00			
	saniti. Area				
	clen.staff area	2.00			1.00
	laundry	1.00	3.00		1.00
	Disinfection Lobby	2.00			1.00
	waste disp. Corridor	2.00			
	PTU & ETU	6.00	3.00		2.00
	Server Room	6.00			2.00
	Network Room	5.00			2.00
	Intercom Room	4.00			2.00
	ICT Room	6.00			2.00
	CCTV Room	4.00			2.00
	Pharmacy	4.00			2.00
	Laboratory	5.00	2.00		3.00
	Sampling Room	2.00			1.00
	Pharmaceutical Store	3.00			3.00
	Medical equipment store	3.00			3.00
	Supply services corridoor	2.00			
	Fire recommeded center	2.00	1.00		1.00
	dec. clean. Rest area	4.00			2.00
	services Toi. Wash area	2.00			
	loundry	2.00	1.00		1.00
	Staff Toilet & Bath area1	1.00			
	Changing room & locker 1	2.00			1.00
	Nurse rest area 1	6.00			2.00
	Nurse rest area 2	6.00			3.00
	Staff Toilet & Bath area2	1.00			
	Changing room & locker 2	2.00			1.00
	Doc. Rest area	5.00			3.00
	Staff Toilet & Bath area3	1.00			
	Changing room & locker 3	2.00			1.00
	Medical Staff cooridoor	2.00			

First Floor				
	staff rest area A	4.00		2.00
	Staff Toilet A	1.00		
	Dis. Passgae	6.00		
	saniti.area A			
	ICU	12.00	6.00	12.00
	Theater	6.00	3.00	6.00
	radiolo. Unit	5.00	3.00	4.00
	ICU rest area	4.00		2.00
	Staff Toilet B	1.00		
	saniti.area B			
	saniti.area C			
	staff rest area B	3.00		1.00
	Staff Toilet C	1.00		
	Wast. Dispo. Equip. store	2.00		
	Ward 1	120.00	10.00	12.00
	Ward 2	120.00	10.00	14.00
	Medicine store	2.00		2.00
	Dis. Lobby	2.00		
	Med.staff pass			
	paitent pass.			
	Doc. Wait area	5.00		2.00
	Nurse wait area	5.00		2.00
	Doc. Toi.	1.00		
	Nur.toi	1.00		
	Sani.area			
	Buffer room	2.00		
	paitent Toi.M	2.00		
	Pait. Toi.F	2.00		
Second Floor				
	staff rest area A	4.00		2.00
	Staff Toilet A	1.00		
	Dis. Passgae	6.00		
	saniti.area A			
	ICU	12.00	6.00	12.00
	Theater	6.00	3.00	6.00
	radiolo. Unit	5.00	3.00	4.00
	ICU rest area	4.00		2.00
	Staff Toilet B	1.00		
	saniti.area B			
	saniti.area C			
	staff rest area B	3.00		1.00
	Staff Toilet C	1.00		
	Wast. Dispo. Equip. store	2.00		
	Ward 1	120.00	10.00	12.00
	Ward 2	120.00	10.00	14.00
	Medicine store	2.00		2.00
	Dis. Lobby	2.00		
	Med.staff pass			

paitent pass.				
Doc. Wait area	5.00			2.00
Nurse wait area	5.00			2.00
Doc. Toi.	1.00			
Nur.toi	1.00			
Sani.area				
Buffer room	2.00			
paitent Toi.M	2.00			
Pait. Toi.F	2.00			
	738.00	77	69	117

Annexure 16 - Design Calculations - Elevator

Design calculation - Lift

$$\text{The round-trip time (RTT)} = 2H (d_f/v) + [S + 1] [t_c + t_f + t_o - d_f/v] + 2Pt_p$$

Where,

H – Average highest reversal floor – from previous project assumption

d_f – Average inter floor height (m)

v – Rated Speed (m/s)

S – Average probable number of stops (BS Code, Table F.1) [$t_c + t_f + t_o$] - Performance time

P – Average number of passengers in the car (BS Code, Table F.1)

t_p - Average passenger transfer time

$$\begin{aligned} \text{The round-trip time} &= [2 \times 8.4 \times 3.9/1.6] + [2 + 1] \times [8.4 - (3.9/1.6)] + [2 \times 8 \times 2] \\ &= 81.91 \text{ s} \end{aligned}$$

The up-peak interval (INT), in seconds (s), of a number of (L) lifts can be calculated using this equation: [INT = RTT / L]

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Here we propose . Waiting Interval} &= 81.9 / 8 \\ &= 10.23 \text{ s} \end{aligned}$$

Checking 01 - Assume no of lifts is 5.

We assume 4 persons can use lift with one stretcher

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Capacity of group} &= [5 \text{ mins} \times \text{Travel Height} \times \text{No. of Lifts} \times \text{Lift Capacity} \times 80\%] / \text{RTT} \\ &= [5 \times 8 \times 5 \times 4 \times 0.8] / 81.91 \\ &= 7.8\text{s} \end{aligned}$$

interval is lower than required time intervals. Therefore, this is satisfied.

5 nos lifts satisfied with the building requirement.

Annexure 17 - Design Calculations of fire fighting system

➤ Fire Pump Calculation

Here we do sum assumption from expert who already done this type of works.

No. Of people in the building	= 415	capita
demand	= 72 m ³ litres per day	
Ground sump size	= 54 m ³	
For firefighting 54 m ³ / 3	= 18 m ³	

Assuming ,

45min have to operate until fire brigade comes.

Rate - 0.5 L/s

Capacity need = 60 x 60 x 5 x 0.5 = 9000 L

So storage is good enough.

$$P_{h(kW)} = q \rho g h / (3.6 \cdot 10^6)$$

$$= q p / (3.6 \cdot 10^6)$$

where

$P_{h(kW)}$ = hydraulic power (kW)

q = flow (m³/h)

ρ = density of fluid (kg/m³)

g = acceleration of gravity (9.81 m/s²)

h = differential head (m)

p = differential pressure (N/m², Pa)

The theoretical pump power can be calculated as

- Hydraulic Power: 0.04 (kW) 0.5 (hp)
- Shaft Power: 0.07 (kW) 0.9 (hp)

But practically here we can use 1.5 hp pumps for this work.

Annexure 18 - Design calculations of Air Conditioning System

Rules of Thumb for Cooling Load Estimates		
Room Design Conditions		
	Temperature	72F +/- 1F
	Humidity	50% +/- 1% RH
Sensible Heat Ratio		
	Sensible Heat Gain	0.90 to 0.95
	Total Heat Gain	
Load Density		
	sq ft/Ton (Total heat gain / 12000)	50 to 100
Preferred Air Distribution		
	Underfloor/overhead	Underfloor
Ventilation Rate		
	CFM/person	10-15 Maximum
Humidificaiton		
	Lbs Moisture/100 CFM of outside air	3

Catogery 01

outside design tem.
When outside tem. Is
95F

1 Windows Exposed to sun (Use only one exposure: Select the one that gives the largest result)	South	0 sq ft		70			
	East, West, Southeast	0 sq ft		92			
	Northwest	0 sq ft	X	72	=	0	
	Northeast	0 sq ft		75			
	North	0 sq ft		10			
	2 All windows not included in item 1		0 sq ft	X	26	=	0
3 Wall Exposed to sun	Light construction	0 linear ft		75			
	Heavy construction	0 linear ft	X	55	=	0	
4 Shade walls not included in item 3		0 linear ft	X	40	=	0	
5 Partitions	All interior walls adjacent to an unconditioned space	10 linear ft	X	35	=	35	
6 Ceiling or roof	Ceiling with unconditioned, occupied space above	100 sq ft		5		500	
	Ceiling w/attic above						
		No Insulation	sq ft	X	12	=	
		2" or more insulation	sq ft		5		
Flat roof w/ceiling below	No Insulation	sq ft		10			
	2" or more insulation	sq ft		5			
7 Floor	Over unconditioned space (on ground or over unheated basement)	sq ft	X	5	=		
8 People (includes allowance for ventilation)	Number of people	4	X	750	=	3000	
9 Lights/ Equipment (use 5 watts/sq ft of floor area as general rule)		100 sq ft	X	5	=	500	
10 Computer Load Total BTU/Hr (if not available in BTU, mult total watts x 3.4)		12800		3.4	=	43520	
Total BTU Cooling Load:						47555	

Catogery 02

outside design tem.
When outside tem. Is
95F

1 Windows Exposed to sun (Use only one exposure: Select the one that gives the largest result)	South	0 sq ft		70		
	East, West, Southeast	36 sq ft		92		3312
	Northwest	0 sq ft	X	72	=	0
	Northeast	0 sq ft		75		
	North	0 sq ft		10		
2 All windows not included in item 1		0 sq ft	X	26	=	0
3 Wall Exposed to sun	Light construction	0 linear ft		75		
	Heavy construction	74 linear ft	X	55	=	0
4 Shade walls not included in item 3		0 linear ft	X	40	=	0
5 Partitions	All interior walls adjacent to an unconditioned space	linear ft	X	35	=	35
6 Ceiling or roof	Ceiling with unconditioned, occupied space above	420 sq ft		5		2100
	Ceiling w/attic above	<i>No Insulation</i>		12	=	
		<i>2" or more insulation</i>		5		
	Flat roof w/ceiling below	<i>No Insulation</i>		10		
	<i>2" or more insulation</i>		5			
7 Floor	Over unconditioned space (on ground or over unheated basement)	420 sq ft	X	5	=	2100
8 People (includes allowance for ventilation)	Number of people	6	X	750	=	4500
9 Lights/ Equipment (use 5 watts/sq ft of floor area as general rule)		420 sq ft	X	5	=	2100
10 Computer Load Total BTU/Hr (if not available in BTU, mult total watts x 3.4)		19200		3.4	=	65280
Total BTU Cooling Load:						79427

Catogery 03

outside design tem.
When outside tem. Is
95F

1 Windows Exposed to sun (Use only one exposure: Select the one that gives the largest result)	South	0 sq ft		70		
	East, West, Southeast	180 sq ft		92		16560
	Northwest	0 sq ft	X	72	=	0
	Northeast	0 sq ft		75		
	North	0 sq ft		10		
2 All windows not included in item 1		0 sq ft	X	26	=	0
3 Wall Exposed to sun	Light construction	110 linear ft		75		8250
	Heavy construction	80 linear ft	X	55	=	0
4 Shade walls not included in item 3		0 linear ft	X	40	=	0
5 Partitions	All interior walls adjacent to an unconditioned space	linear ft	X	35	=	35
6 Ceiling or roof	Ceiling with unconditioned, occupied space above	2347 sq ft		5		11735
	Ceiling w/attic above	<i>No Insulation</i>		12		
		<i>2" or more insulation</i>	X	5	=	
	Flat roof w/ceiling below	<i>No Insulation</i>		10		
	<i>2" or more insulation</i>	sq ft		5		
7 Floor	Over unconditioned space (on ground or over unheated basement)	2347 sq ft	X	5	=	11735
8 People (includes allowance for ventilation)	Number of people	25	X	750	=	18750
9 Lights/ Equipment (use 5 watts/sq ft of floor area as general rule)		2347 sq ft	X	5	=	11735
10 Computer Load Total BTU/Hr (if not available in BTU, mult total watts x 3.4)		64000		3.4	=	217600
Total BTU Cooling Load:						296400

Annexure 19 - Services Drawings

Client - Ministry Of Health
Design of New Quarantine Hospital for Infectious diseases(IDH) at Kotikawatta, Mulleriyawa, Sri Lanka.
Design & Drawn Team - Group J
Drawn Title:

— Waste water line
— sewerage line

FRIST & SECOND FLOOR WASTE WATER LINE DIAGRAM

SCALE - 1:250

Client - Ministry Of Health
Design of New Quarantine Hospital for Infectious diseases(IDH) at Kotikawatta, Mulleriyawa, Sri Lanka.
Design & Drawn Team - Group J
Drawn Title :

- Fire detectors
- Fire alarm
- Hose reel
- Fire extinguishers

GROUND FLOOR FIRE LAYOUT

SCALE - 1:250

Client - Ministry Of Health
Design of New Quarantine Hospital for Infectious diseases(IDH) at Kotikawatta, Mulleriyawa, Sri Lanka.
Design & Drawn Team - Group J
Drawn Title :

- Fire detectors
- Fire alarm
- Hose reel
- Fire extinguishers

FRIST & SECOND FLOOR FIRE LAYOUT
SCALE - 1:250

Client - Ministry Of Health
Design of New Quarantine Hospital for Infectious diseases(IDH) at Kotikawatta, Mulleriyawa, Sri Lanka.
Design & Drawn Team - Group J
Drawn Title :

- ▶ 13A Socket outlet
- ⊠ LED Panel Light
- ▬ A/C Units
- ⌞ Fan

GROUND FLOOR - ELECTRICAL LAYOUT
SCALE - 1:250

Client - Ministry Of Health
Design of New Quarantine Hospital for Infectious diseases(IDH) at Kotikawatta, Mulleriyawa, Sri Lanka.
Design & Drawn Team - Group J
Drawn Title :

- ▶ 13A Socket outlet
- ⊠ LED Panel Light
- ▣ A/C Units
- ⌞ Fan

FRIST & SECOND FLOOR - ELECTRICAL LAYOUT

SCALE - 1:250

Client - Ministry Of Health
Design of New Quarantine Hospital for Infectious diseases(IDH) at Kotikawatta, Mulleriyawa, Sri Lanka.
Design & Drawn Team - Group J
Drawn Title :

1. MANAGEMENT

Prerequisite 1 - Green Building Accredited Professional

Intent: - To encourage and recognize the engagement of professionals who can assist the project team with the integration of Green Building aims and processes throughout design and construction phases.

Hospital Building Approach: - The design team GBCSL accredited professional attending at 50% of all design meetings and at least 75% of all building services meetings throughout the project. They are tasked with monitoring the implementation of all green activities and participate site visits and site meetings per once a month throughout the project completion.

Prerequisite 2 - Commissioning Clauses

Intent: - To encourage and recognize commissioning and handover initiatives those ensure that all building services can operate to optimum design potential.

Hospital Building Approach: - The final consist of a commissioning report, as-built drawings, commissioning data sheets and operation and maintenance manuals. Commissioning is done prior to handover as per commissioning clauses and building tuning plan. A commissioning plan format was developed to implement the commissioning clauses.

Prerequisite 3 - Building Users' Guide

Intent: - Encourage and recognize information management that enables building users to optimize the building's environmental performance.

Hospital Building Approach: - This guide is a comprehensive document that includes information for the safe and efficient operation of the building which depends on the interactions of occupants and buildings. This helps the users of the building to get a better understanding of the building and get efficient provision of required services from the building.

The building user guide includes the following information,

1. Energy and environmental strategies for optimum building performance.
2. Targets for the reduction of energy, water and waste.
3. Optimum performance criteria for ventilation, cooling, lighting, electrical, water management system, sewerage etc.
4. Monitoring provisions for energy, water and indoor environment quality.
5. Transport facilities including car parking provisions, location of cyclist facilities and public transport information.
6. Emergency contact information.
7. References and further information.
8. As built drawings.

Credit 1.1 - Integrated Design Process

Intent: - To address and negotiate between the various needs of all stakeholders involved in a building project to achieve common targets in order to have a balanced and optimized sustainable design outcome.

Hospital Building approach: - Beginning in pre-design and continuing throughout the design phases, identify and use opportunities to achieve synergies across disciplines and building systems and Building Information Modeling used for coordination and design integration, enabling optimization of resources and downstream building performance.

Point can obtain = 1

Credit 1.2 - Green Facility Manager

Intent: - To ensure the sustainability practices are maintained throughout the operations stage.

Hospital Building approach: - Hiring a Facility manager who is an Associate Professional of GREEN SL to monitor the performance of building whether sustainable practices are well maintained in the building as per designed data and submitting a progress report to the GBCSL.

Point can obtain = 1

Credit 1.3 - Responsible Construction Practices

Intent: - Encourage and recognize the adoption of a formal environmental management system in line with established guidelines during construction.

Hospital Building Approach: -

Credit 1.3.1: Involvement of an expert in Ecology

Consultant Ecologist involving in the design stage and obtaining a report of survey ecosystem and asses the diversity.

Point can be obtain = 1

1.3.2: Environmental Management Plan

Due to the Hospital building IEE conduct to identify the environmental impacts. It contains dust control system, sound control system, water pollution controlling system and waste management system.

Point can obtain = 1

2. SUSTAINABLE SITES

Prerequisite 1 - Erosion and Sedimentation Control

Intent - Control/reduce soil erosion and minimize negative impacts of waterway sedimentation and airborne dust generation.

Hospital Building Approach: - During the entire construction period soil erosion and sedimentation of site eliminating according to the environment management plan which is prepares in the IEE.

Credit 2.1 - Site Selection

Intent: - Avoid the development of inappropriate sites and reduce the environmental impact from the location of a building on a site.

Hospital Building Approach: - Selected land situated at Kotikawatta, Mulleriyawa which existing IDH hospital situated land not be affected natural disasters and with necessary services.

Thus the selected land has following features,

- ❖ The selected land was not designated as a sensitive area.
- ❖ It is not a prime agricultural land or conserved land.
- ❖ It is not identified as a wetland.
- ❖ It is not in close proximity to any sensitive natural habitat as defined by the Central Environmental Authority (CEA).
- ❖ It is not identified as a threat to habitat for any species and does not come under the purview of Department of Wildlife Conservation and Ministry of Environment.
- ❖ The selected land doesn't affect the flood hazardous.

Flood Hazard Map Published by Irrigation Department, With the Assistance from Disaster Management Center Sri Lanka 2019

Points can be obtain = 4

Credit 2.2 - Site Assessment and Development

Intent: - To assess site condition before design to evaluate sustainable options and to conserve existing natural areas and restore damaged areas.

Hospital Building Approach: -Complete and document site assessment including the following,

- ❖ Topography – Flat land with firm soil
- ❖ Hydrology - Alluvium aquifer region under layer
- ❖ Climate – Average temperature 30-32 Celsius, located in wet zone
- ❖ Vegetation – Wet zone trees and bushes
- ❖ Soils – Existing firm soil and free from natural disasters (landslides)
- ❖ Human use – Due to urbanization, infrastructure facilities also developed in the area
- ❖ Human health effects – Strictly considering safety precaution methods within the premises

Topographic Map of the Selected Land in Kotikawatta, Mulleriyawa

Ground Water Potential Map

N
1:2500000

Surface Water Potential Map

Average Annual Rainfall Map

Climatic Zone Map

ශ්‍රී ලංකාවේ මහා පාංශුගණ හා උපගණ පැතිරී ඇති ආකාරය

Soil Group Map

DISTRIBUTION OF LANDSLIDE HAZARD ZONES IN THE CENTRAL HIGHLANDS OF SRI LANKA

Revised on - 29.03.2016

NATIONAL BUILDING RESEARCH ORGANISATION
99/1, Jawatta Road, Colombo 05, SRI LANKA

Landslide Vulnerability Map in Western Province

Colombo District Vegetation Map

Human Use Map around Kotikawatta, Mulleriyawa

Human Health Effects Population Map

Points can obtain = 1

Credit 2.3 - Development Density and Community Connectivity

Intent: - Channel development into urban areas with existing infrastructure, protect green fields and preserve habitat and natural resources.

Hospital Building approach: - The site is situated in front of Mandawila road. In addition to that land is situated at the existing IDH Hospital land in Mulleriyawa. So, the surrounding area has already prepared for the hospital situation and people are well aware of the behavior of the Hospital. Not harm to any green field or habitat and natural resources.

Facilities of close proximity of selected land

Points can be obtain = 2

Credit 2.4- Reuse of Previously Developed sites and Allowance for Connectivity of Green Lands

Intent: - To rehabilitate damaged sites/previously developed sites reducing pressure on undeveloped land and improving a percentage of land as reservation to support biodiversity.

Hospital Building Approach: - Selected land for proposed infectious diseases hospital situated in the same land in existing IDH hospital. This land area is already developed for hospital purposes and the proposed land has four numbers of small-scale single-story buildings. When the construction work execution these four buildings are demolishing. Also, more than 30% of the area of selected land planting trees and turfing for ground with a proper landscaping plan by consulting a GBCSL Accredited professional landscape architecture; it also includes an herbal plant garden.

Point can obtain = 2

Credit 2.5 - Alternative Transportation

Intent: - Reduce pollution and land development impacts from automobile use.

Hospital Building approach: -

Credit 2.5.1 - Public Transportation Access

The proposed Hospital building located in front of Mandawila road where public transport is readily available. 10m for the bus stop for both sides. 650m for Gothatuwa New town.

Point can obtain = 1

Credit 2.5.2 Parking Capacity

According to the TIA conducted for the project, implement the parking spaces and traffic mitigate measures to overcome the impacts. Vehicle parking lots reserved in the design,

Area	No of Parking slots provided
Ambulance parking	22
Staff drivers area	25(Bikes)
Public area	22
	03(Disabled)
	17(Bikes)
Medical and Admin staff area	38
	50(Bikes)
Supply and Services area	03
	02
Waste Management area	04
	03(Lorries)

Point can obtain = 1

Credit 2.5.3 – Encourage use of green vehicle

Hospital Building Approach: - This project is for a hospital building where emergency services are always operational. Therefore, using alternative vehicles other than fuel vehicles that provide the easiest and fastest service may cause problems.

Points can be obtain = 0

Credit 2.6 - Reduced Site Disturbance

Intent: - To conserve existing natural areas and restore damaged areas, to provide habitat and promote biodiversity.

Hospital Building approach: -

Credit 2.6.1 Protect or Restore Habitat, Credit 2.6.2 Greenery Provisions, Credit 2.6.3 Development Footprint

According to GREENSL Rating System for New Construction encourage developers to restore a 50% of the site area (excluding the building footprint) by replacing impervious surface with native or adapted vegetation. In this building project there going to be vegetated more than 50% green areas; it also include herbal plant garden which usable for patient.

Point can be obtain = 6

Credit 2.7 - Storm water Design, Quantity and Quality Control

Intent: - To limit disruption of natural hydrology by reducing impervious cover, increasing on site infiltration, and reducing or eliminating pollution from storm water run-off.

Hospital Building Approach: - Paving is designed to allow water to soak through the gaps between pavings and seep into the ground. Only used less amount of pavings for marked the parking area outlines. Green more than 50% of the open space to reduce surface runoff.

Maximize the infiltration by reducing impervious cover. Improve the drainage system in the land and connected it to the road main drain.

Points can be obtain = 2

Credit 2.8 - Heat Island Effect, Non-Roof

Intent: - Reduce heat islands (thermal gradient differences between developed and undeveloped areas), minimize the impact on microclimate and human and wildlife habitat.

Hospital Building approach: - The open area around the building has been landscaped with native planting and extensive garden and grassed areas, which will directly reduce the heat island effect. Native trees provide shade to the land and reduce the heat island effect. Hard landscaping methods are reduced for the design, hollow ground pavers reduced the impact of heat.

Point can obtain = 1

Credit 2.9 - Heat Island effect, Roof

Intent: - Reduce heat islands (thermal gradient differences between developed and undeveloped areas) to minimize the impact on microclimate and human and wildlife habitat.

Hospital Building approach: - proposed sandwich panel roof sheets for reduce heat transfer into the building and also installing a solar panel for total roof area for generating electricity, this also helps to reduce transferring heat to the building area.

Point can be obtain = 0

Credit 2.10 - Light Pollution Reduction

Intent: - Minimize light trespass from the building and site, reduce sky-glow to increase night sky access, improve nighttime visibility through glare reduction, and reduce development impact on nocturnal environments.

Hospital Building approach: - The building has been designed to maximize natural light penetration via windows. Therefore, only the night time needed the electrical lighting system for the most areas of the building. Manually switch off lights in unoccupied areas reducing light pollution. Introduce LED lighting theme for the entire premises. Shading cover/funnel lights to prevent night sky pollution. Using BMS controlled light system for the common areas (lift lobbies, staircases).

Night sky pollution reduction

Point can obtain = 1

3. WATER EFFICIENCY

Prerequisite 1 - Water Efficient Landscaping

Intent: - To eliminate the use of portable water (from NWSDB) for landscape irrigation.

Hospital Building Approach: - Use only ground water through tube well for the landscape irrigation. This is planned to achieve by following activities.

- ❖ Plant water efficient native plants.
- ❖ Design landscape to maximize the exposure of plants to effective rainfall.

Plants and trees for outside,

Cristina Tree

Rathmal

Acacia

Magul Karanda

Mango

Kottamba

Prerequisite 2 - Indoor Water Use Reduction

Intent: - To reduce indoor water consumption.

Hospital Building Approach: - Use of water efficient water closet. 100% of toilet flushing can be used by harvested rain water and tube well water.

Category	No of occupants	Usage	Frequency of use/day	Base line		Proposed System	
				Water Capacity (L)	Water Capacity (L/day)	Water Capacity (L)	Water Capacity (L/day)
Fully occupied	355	100%	3	6	6390	3.6	3834
Daily transient	60	75%	1	6	270	3.6	162
Total	415				6660		3996

Monthly toilet flushing water capacity (ltr/month) = 199,800.00 ltr/month

Total water requirement for the users = 2,241,000.00 ltr/month

Total water requirement if toilet flushing used

From water efficient water closet = 119,880.00 ltr/month

Total water reduction percentage = 3.56%

Prerequisite 3 - Building Level Water Metering

Intent: - To support water management and identify opportunities for additional saving by tracking water consumption.

Hospital building Approach: -

Installing permanent water meters in various divisions for measure the portable water consumption of various divisions and maintaining proper database in manual and electronic formats. Identify the consumption patterns and finding the potential saving strategies.

Credit 3.1 - Water Efficient Construction

Intent: - To limit or eliminate the use of potable water (from NWSDB) for construction activities.

Hospital Building Approach: - Proposed project building land is situated in wet zone. So there has more water in ground level. So before the construction work implement installing a tube well for supply water for constructions work. It helps to reduce more than 50% potable water consumption.

Point can be obtain = 1

Credit 3.2 - Cooling Tower Water Efficiency in Air-conditioning System

Intent: - Limit or eliminate the use of potable water for Air-conditioning make-up by 50%.

Hospital Building Approach: - This project execute for a hospital building foe infectious diseases patients. So there is not installing an air conditioning for most areas. Because viruses can spread rapidly by air conditioning system. Split type air conditioners use only for Medicine stores, labs, ICU, Sever room, CCTV camera room, Intercom panel room. Therefore, no need to supply water to operate air conditioners.

Point can be obtain = 1

Credit 3.3 - Indoor Water Use Reduction

Intent: - Optimize the water use efficiency within building to reduce the burden on potable water supply and wastewater system.

Hospital Building Approach: -

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Total fully occupied} &= (\text{Patients} - 255) + (\text{Doctors} - 15) + (\text{Nurses} - 45) + \\ &(\text{Minor staff} - 30) + (\text{Services} - 10) = 415 \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Occupant water usage} = 180\text{L/per person per day}$$

$$\text{Daily transient persons} = 10\text{L/per person per day}$$

$$\text{Vehicle washing} = 500\text{L/per day}$$

$$\text{Landscaping \& Irrigation} = 2000\text{L/day}$$

$$\text{Total water usage} = (220\text{L} \times 255) + (160 \times 45) = 65800 \text{ L/day}$$

Usage water for vehicle washing and for gardening can be fulfill with tube well water resource; it can reduce portable water consumption of the building.

It can be reduce 75m³ of portable water consumption by installing tube well in the premises. It saves 3.79% portable water usage.

Point can be obtain = 0

Credit 3.4 - Innovation Waste Water Technologies

Intent: - Reduce the generation of wastewater and potable water demand, while increasing the local aquifer recharge.

Hospital Building Approach: -

Credit 3.4.1 – Reduce Portable Water Use

Total water requirement for sewage conveyance fulfilled by portable water.

Point can be obtain = 0

Credit 3.4.2 – Treat Wastewater

Total sewerage and wastewater transfer through the underground pipelines to the main sewerage transfer line of the NWS&DB treatment plant.

Points can be obtain = 0

Credit 3.4.3 Harvested Rainwater

. This project is designed to construct within a short time period to face unexpected pandemics. So there not include more complex features; projects only do with basic requirements.

Points can be obtain = 0

Credit 3.4.4 Aquifer Recharge

This project it has not including waste water treatments plant and rain water harvested tanks.

Points can be obtain = 0

Credit 3.5 - Innovative Water transmission

Intent: - Limit the use of non-renewable energy for water transmission.

Hospital Building Approach: - Net Metering solar system installing on the 50% roof area. It reduce more than 50% of non-renewable energy consumption for transmission water.

Point can obtain = 1

Credit 3.6 - Water Sub-metering

Intent: - To support water management and identify opportunities for additional water savings by tracking water consumption.

Hospital Building Approach: - Installing water meters at a few locations covering the whole project and monitor the water consumption patterns and maintaining record of each water meter and analyze date and identify potential water saving opportunities.

Point can obtain = 1

4. ENERGY & ATMOSPHERE

Prerequisite 1 - Fundamental Building Systems Commissioning and Verification

Intent: - Verify and ensure that fundamental building elements and systems are designed, installed and calibrated to operate to meet the owner's project requirements for energy, water, indoor environmental quality, and durability.

Hospital Building Approach: - Preparing the building commissioning plan to verify and ensure the fundamental building elements and systems operate as intended. The commissioning plan included the followings,

- ❖ Hiring the commissioning agent does not directly responsible for project or construction management.
- ❖ Prepare the design brief and implement it.
- ❖ Included commissioning requirements into the contract documents.
- ❖ Verify installation, functional performance, training, and operation & maintenance procedures by commissioning documentation.
- ❖ Completed a commissioning report.
- ❖ Commissioning document includes; heating, ventilation, lighting and day lighting system, renewable energy system.

Prerequisite 2 - Minimum Energy Performance

Intent: - Establish the minimum level of energy efficiency for the base building and systems to reduce the environmental and economic impacts of excess energy usage.

Hospital Building Approach: - The building project is complied with,

- ❖ The mandatory provisions (Section 5.4, 6.4, 7.4, 8.4, 9.4 and 10.4) of ASHRAE/IESNA standard 90.1-2010. (without amendments)
- ❖ The prescriptive requirements (Section 5.5, 6.5, 7.5 and 9.5) or performance requirements (Section 11) of ASHRAE/IESNA standard 90.1-2010 (without amendments)
- ❖ The project comply with the final version of Code of practices of energy efficient buildings of the Sri Lanka, published by Sustainable Energy Authority (SEA), 2008.

Prerequisite 3 - CFC Reduction in HVAC&R Equipment

Intent: - Reduce ozone layer depletion.

Hospital Building Approach: - This hospital building project execute for infectious diseases. Mainly these diseases spreading one person to another person by the aspiratory system. So there has risk for installing air condition for this hospital. Split type air conditioners use only for Medicine stores, labs, ICU, Sever room, CCTV camera room, Intercom panel room. R400a refrigerant use for these air conditioning machines. (Zero use of CFC base refrigerant)

Prerequisite 4 - Energy Metering

Intent: - To support energy management and identify opportunities for additional energy savings by tracking building-level energy use.

Hospital Building Approach: - Installing permanent energy meters (Electricity, Chilled water, Steam) in various divisions for measure the energy consumption of various divisions and maintaining proper database in manual and electronic formats. Identify the consumption patterns and finding the potential energy saving strategies.

Credit 4.1 - Optimize Energy Performance

Intent: -Achieve increasing levels of energy performance above the prerequisite standard to reduce environmental impact associate with excessive energy use.

Hospital Building Approach: - the building design complies with the prescriptive measures of the ASHRAE Advance Energy Design Guide for Hospital Buildings.

Typically, the building services designed for minimize the energy consumption.

- ❖ LED lamps proposed for all light fittings.
- ❖ Solar lights proposed for outdoor lights.
- ❖ Building orientation is designed for maximum penetration of natural day light to the building.
- ❖ Sun control films pasting to windows for make the thermal comfort inside the building.

According to above proposed methods it can be reduced 25% to 30 % energy cost saving.

Points can obtain = 5

Credit 4.2 - Onsite Renewable Energy

Intent: - Encourage and recognize increasing levels of self-supply through renewable technologies to reduce environmental impacts associated with fossil fuel energy use.

Hospital Building Approach: - Hospital building roof installing 1000m² solar panel system and gardening lights operate with solar panel system individually. Roof solar panel system operate as a Net- Metering system.

Size of solar panel = 1.65m x 0,992m

One solar panel coverage area = 1.636 m²

500 solar panel coverage area = 818m²

Total Load of Proposed Building (kWh) per year = 543653.07

Energy saving (kWh) per year from solar system = 170128.42

Energy Saving Percentage (Per year) = 31.29%

Point can be obtain = 4

Credit 4.3 - Enhanced Commissioning

Intent: - Verify and ensure that the entire building is designed, constructed, and calibrated to operate as intended.

Hospital Building Approach: - Well qualified experienced consultant team member conducts the following tasks to achieve its optimized usage,

- ❖ Conduct a focused review of the design prior to the construction document phase.
- ❖ Conduct a focused review the construction documents when close to completion.
- ❖ Conduct a selective review of consultant submittals of commissioned equipment.
- ❖ Develop a re-commissioning management manual.
- ❖ Have a contract in place for a near warranty end or post occupancy review.

Points can obtain = 1

Credit 4.4 - Enhanced Refrigerant Management

Intent: - Reduce ozone depletion and support early compliance with the Montreal Protocol while minimizing the direct contribution to climate change.

Hospital Building Approach: - This hospital building project execute for infectious diseases. Mainly these diseases spreading one person to another person by the aspiratory system. So there has risk for installing air condition for this hospital building not only patients areas but also staff areas. Split type air conditioners use only for Medicine stores, labs, ICU, Sever room, CCTV camera room, Intercom panel room. R400a refrigerant use for these air conditioning machines. (Zero use of CFC base refrigerant).

Point can obtain = 1

Credit 4.5 - Measurement and Verification

Intent: - Provide the building energy consumption over time, for the ongoing accountability.

Hospital Building Approach: - Whole building simulation program will be used to simulate the building energy use. The building Management System (BMS) has been designed so that install the meeting system to measure the energy use of the respective areas/services. BMS system is installed for tracking the proposed system. The implemented system is as per the guidance given in the International Performance Measurement & Verification Protocol (IPMVP). Energy used in the baseline model and the calibrated as built model is used for calculating the energy savings.

Points can obtain = 2

Credit 4.6 - Off-site Renewable Energy

Intent: - Encourage investments in off-site renewable energy technologies for export purposes to the National Grid.

Hospital Building Approach: - In this Hospital Building project installing Net-metering solar system of roof area. So generate solar power use for building usage in day time and excess power export to the national grid.

Points can obtain = 1

Credit 4.7 - Certified Energy Auditor

Intent: - Ensure that a qualified person on staff manage the building energy system and seek to optimize performance over time.

Hospital Building Approach: - Consultant need to hired a person as the energy auditor, a person who have the “Energy Manager” certificate from the Sustainable Energy Authority of Sri Lanka with a valid contract for a 1 year, with a commitment to extend up to 3 years. The auditor needs to present the annual report on the building energy consumption and energy management to the client.

Points can obtain = 1

Credit 4.8 - Greenhouse Gas Emission Management

Intent: - To reduce the impact on the environment due to the GHG emission during the operations stage of the building.

Hospital Building Approach: - Fixing common area CO₂ level monitoring equipment to monitoring the Co₂ levels of the various areas of building and maintain a report about 1 year period in accordance with Greenhouse Gas Protocol and ISO 14064-part1 standard. Submitting Carbon management plan along with the calculations and take necessary actions to reduce GHG emission gradually.

Points can be obtain = 1

5. MATERIAL & RESOURCES AND WASTE MANAGEMENT

5.1 Material and Resources

Prerequisite 1 - Operational Solid Waste Management

Intent: - Ensure effective operational solid waste management, to avoid operational (domestic and industrial) wastes being sent to the landfills and to improve sanitation, health and reduce environmental pollution.

Hospital Building Approach: - Sri Lanka government introduced the new solid waste management design of separation, collection and storage of waste materials for recycling. Therefore, separation of the solid waste done by at the site. Coloured and labeled bins using to collect separated waste. Handover those separated waste to municipal waste collection daily.

Waste Hierarchy

Credit 5.1.1 - Building Reuse

Intent: - Extend the life cycle of the existing building stock, conserve resources, retain cultural resources, reduce waste, and reduce environmental impacts of new buildings as they relate to materials manufacturing and transport.

Hospital Building Approach: - There have 4 single story buildings in proposed land, those 4 buildings should demolished and removing debris for construct proposed building.

Points can be obtain = 0

Credit 5.1.2 - Reused and Recycled Materials/Products

Intent: - To reduce the demand for virgin materials and to reduce solid wastes to landfills through the usage of recycled materials and/or resource reuse.

Hospital Building Approach: - Due to the new building and following rapid construction methods cannot handle with old materials, it's used new materials to construction works.

Point can be obtain = 0

Credit 5.1.3 - Local/Regional Materials

Intent: - Increase demand for building materials and products that are extracted and manufactured within the region, thereby supporting the regional economy and reducing the environmental impacts resulting from transportation.

Hospital Building Approach: - Use of the local or regional material is a greener concept as well as a cost-effective method. Majority of the materials selected are local or regional materials. Cement, sand, metal, rubble, aluminium, soil and certified timber are local and readily available. All the sanitary appliances and relevant accessories, ceramic tiles, plumbing items, electrical components, including cables and paints are purchased from local manufacturers. A limited number of imported materials is used for the project such as waterproofing materials, electrical items and solar power system which are not locally manufactured.

Therefore, more than 50% of the materials that have been used for the building are manufactured locally. They include:

- ❖ Portland Lime Stone Cement – Galle/Puttalam
- ❖ Fly ash bricks - Puttalam
- ❖ Reinforcements – Oruwala (Lanwa)
- ❖ Locally manufactured aluminium doors/windows - Ja-Ela
- ❖ Lanka Tiles - Biyagama
- ❖ Local timber used for doors and door frames - Moratuwa

Points can be obtain = 1

Credit 5.1.4 - Rapidly Renewable Materials

Intent: - Reduce the use and depletion of finite raw, and long-cycle renewable materials by replacing them with rapidly renewable materials.

Hospital Building Approval: - For this Hospital building project does not used bamboo, cotton.agri-fiber and strawboards, therefore, not consider to gain this point.

Points can be obtain = 0

Credit 5.1.5 - Green Labelled Products

Intent: - To use green labelled materials and products, certified as environmentally friendly products and equipment, to reduce dependence on materials that have associated negative environmental impacts.

Hospital Building Approach: - More than 10% of materials using in the project are certified materials by GBCSL under the Green product labeling preprogram.

Cement – Tokyo super

Pints – Low VOC emitting Nippon Paint

Tiles – Lanka tiles

Interlock pavings – SMS Holdings

Sanitary ware – Rocell

Aggregate – Sri Lanka land development cooperation

Points can be obtain = 1

Credit 5.1.6 - Certified Wood

Intent: - To encourage environmentally responsible forest management.

Hospital Building Approach: - 100% of the timber used in the building is certified timber in accordance with the Department of Forest Conservation and State Timber Cooperation of Environment Ministry for wood building components. Aluminium doors and windows used in the exterior and timber doors and windows used for the internal.

Points can be obtain = 1

Credit 5.1.7 - Upfront Carbon Emissions

Intent: - To quantify the environmental impact of the building due to carbon emissions during the building material production stage and construction stages. Carbon emission refer to all emissions of greenhouse gases.

Hospital Building Approach: - Well maintained landscaping, herbal plant garden, flower tuffs will reduce the global warming potential of the building. It will reduce the emission of CO₂. But this project doing in short construction period with rapid construction methods. So, does not obtain this point.

Points cab be obtain = 0

Credit 5.1.8 - Sustainable Building Systems

Intent: - To encourage the adoption of building designs, building structures and construction practices that are environmentally friendly and sustainable.

Hospital Building Approach: -All design features, structural designs and construction methodologies executing according to the GBCSL Rating System for New Construction.

Followings are the adopt sustainable building systems following in construction stage.

- ❖ Light weight concrete elements – Fly ash blocks for partition walls
- ❖ Structural steel elements for columns and beams
- ❖ Precast concrete elements for slab

It is more than 50% of the constructed floor area consist of sustainable building system.

Points can be obtain = 2

5.2 Waste Management

Credit 5.2.1 - Construction and Demolition Waste Reuse

Intent: - Divert construction, demolition, and land-clearing debris from landfill disposal, redirect recyclable recovered resources back to the manufacturing process. Redirect reusable materials to appropriate uses in construction.

Hospital Building Approach: - According to the implemented waste management plan of the IEE contractor should consider the measures to prevent the environment impact.

Majority of the building components was manufactured off site, thus construction waste on site was reduced. The management of all non-recyclable construction waste was handled by contractor an environmentally sensitive manner.

- ❖ Reinforcement Off cuts are sold back to the collectors
- ❖ Demolishing, construction waste items and other hazardous materials used for backfilling purposes.
- ❖ PVC pipes, aluminium off cuts sold back to the collectors and usable item stored for other construction project by the contractors` yard.
- ❖ Formwork timber used for other project constructions. Fly
- ❖ Cardboard, cement bags sold out to the collectors.
- ❖ Ready-mix concrete excess used to make eco concrete paving blocks and floor concreting.

Therefore, most of the generated waste recycled or reused in the project. (Near to 90%)

Construction waste generation in the project

Points can be obtain = 2

Credit 5.2.2 - Waste Materials to Construction Materials

Intent: - To reduce the demand for virgin materials by diverting different industry wastes to construction practices while avoiding wastes being sent to the landfills.

Hospital Building Approach: - To encourage use of materials or products which are up-cycled or down- cycled using waste materials, which results in a reduction of solid waste to landfills.

Hospital Building approach: - Bricks made out of fly ash used to construct walls.

Replacing ordinary bricks and cement blocks. Fly ash brick saves the material cost for bricks shows in following table.

Cost for fly ash blocks = 2,537,170.00

BOQ Value = 581,040,000.00

Fly ash block usage from BOQ value = 4.36%

Point can be obtain = 1

Credit 5.2.3 - Storage, Collection & Safe disposal of Hazardous Wastes

Intent: - Facilitate the safe disposal of hazardous waste generated by building occupants which cannot be released to the environment.

Hospital Building Approach: - As per the IEE waste management measures e- wastes, flammable liquids, chemicals and other hazardous waste collected safely and submit to the municipal waste collectors to dispose properly. Specially this hospital operate as infectious diseases hospital, so the viruses can spread if not following necessary safety guidelines and regulations.

Point can be obtain = 1

1.0 INDOOR ENVIRONMENTAL QUALITY

Prerequisite 1 – Minimum IAQ Performance

Intent: - Establish minimum indoor air quality (IAQ) performance to prevent the development of indoor air quality problems in buildings, thus contributing to the comfort and well-being of the occupants.

Hospital Building approach: - The building complies with the minimum requirement of voluntary consensus standard ASHRAE 62.1-2010 Ventilation for acceptable indoor sections 04 through 07 of air quality. Naturally ventilated spaces requirements shall comply with ASHRAE 62.1-2010 and Urban Development Authority. (Window area more than 30% from the 1/7 from the floor area.)

Prerequisite 2 – Smoke (ETS) Control

Intent: - Minimize exposure of building occupants, indoor surface and ventilation air distribution systems to Environmental Tobacco Smoke (ETS)

Hospital Building Approach: - According to the National Authority on Tobacco Act no 27 of 2006, is the law of governing tobacco control in Sri Lanka. The comprehensive law includes measures relating to restrictions on smoking in public places. According to the option three, prohibit smoking in all common areas of the building.

Prerequisite 3 – Minimum Acoustic Performance

Intent: - Minimize noise and vibration from mechanical and electrical equipment can ensure a basic level of acoustic comfort for occupant health and wellbeing.

Hospital Building Approach: -

Internal noises - fly ash walls and separated roof slab act as noise barriers to the building. So that the designed hospital building elements acoustic levels are comply with the CIBSE guide A.

External noises; There is no sever impact of noise in exterior if the land situated road frontage. 4m guard-wall used for the project design to cover the building. Therefore, it will reduce the noise incoming towards the hospital building. The selected land does not affect from the other significant noise sources in the handbook (aircraft over flights, trains, industry)

Credit 6.1 – Outdoor Air Delivery Monitoring

Intent: - Provide capacity for ventilation system monitoring to help sustain occupant comfort and well-being.

Hospital Building Approach: - Installing permanent Co2 monitoring system for take feedback about ventilation performance to ensure that ventilation system maintain design minimum. Following CIBSE AM 10, Section 4, Design Calculation and monitoring airflows of all individual areas and designing all openings to satisfactory the minimum requirement of ventilation mentioned in the UDA building regulations.

Points can be obtain = 1

Credit 6.2 – Increased Ventilation

Intent: - Provide additional outdoor air ventilation to improve indoor air quality for improved occupant comfort, well-being and productivity.

Hospital Building Approach: - Installing permanent Co2 monitoring system for take feedback about ventilation performance to ensure that ventilation system maintain design minimum. Following CIBSE AM 10, Section 4, Design Calculation and monitoring airflows of all individual areas and designing all openings to satisfactory the minimum requirement of ventilation.

Point can be obtain = 1

Credit 6.3 – Construction IAQ Management Plan

Intent: - Prevent indoor air quality problems resulting from the construction/renovation process in order to help sustain the comfort and well-being of construction workers and building occupants.

Hospital Building Approach: - According to the IEE, Environmental Management Plan proposed migratory measures followed by the contractor and it will monitor by the consultant throughout the project duration. During the construction:

- ❖ Properly follows the procedure for loading and unloading the material such as Sand, Soil, and Cement.
- ❖ Proper storage places allocated for the materials to prevent the contamination, odor.
- ❖ Implement a water spreading system for controlling the dust.
- ❖ Vehicle speed limits are establishing, vehicle emission report (less than one year old) were considered.

After the construction:

After construction ends, prior to occupancy and after all interior finishes installing, a building flush-out was performed.

Points can be obtain = 1

Credit 6.4 – Low Emitting Materials

Intent: - Reduce the quantity of indoor air contaminants that are odorous or potentially irritating harmful to the comfort and well-being of installers and building occupants.

Hospital Building Approach: -

Credit 6.4.1 Adhesive and Sealant – Swisstek tile adhesive and grout use for fixing tiles which is certified company in ISO 9001:2015.

Points can be obtain = 1

Credit 6.4.2 Paints and Coatings - Nippolac low VOC limits paints used for the building.

Nippolac paints are lower the specified VOC limits.

VOC Limits; Non-Flat 150 (g/l)

Mat 50 (g/l)

Anti-Corrosive / Anti Rust 250 (g/l)

Points can be obtain = 1

Credit 6.4.3 Carpet Systems and Composite wood and Agri-fiber products - Do not used carpet in the building

Points can be obtain = 1

Credit 6.5 – Indoor chemical & Pollutant Source control

Intent: - Minimize exposure of building occupants to potentially hazardous particulates and chemical pollutants.

Hospital Building Approach: - Proposed land area situated in residential area. There is no any industries surrounding area and also due to hospital building totally ventilation by outdoor fresh air. All chemical related work doing in well managed labs under well managed safety precautions and regulations.

Point can obtain = 1

Credit 6.6 – Lighting and Comfort Controls

Provide a high level of lighting system control by individual occupants or by specific groups in multi-occupant spaces to promote the productivity, comfort and well-being of building occupants.

Hospital Building Approach: -

Lighting Controls (Credit 6.6.1)

Provide individual lighting controls (manual switches, one switch for one light) for all building occupants can be enable adjustments to suit individual task need and preferences. And lighting system controllability for all shared multi-occupant spaces to enable lighting adjustment that meets group needs and preferences. All common areas and external lighting system connected with BMS and controlled it with the scheduled time and daylight sensors.

Points can be obtain = 1

Comfort Control (Credit 6.6.2)

A Government hospital building, can't provide individual comfort controls for 50% of occupants. Because most of the wards have common facilities (fans, Lights, Windows). So it cannot maintain individual facilities for the users.

Points can be obtain = 0

Credit 6.7 – Thermal Comfort, Design and Verification

Intent: - Provide a comfortable thermal environment that supports the productivity and well-being of building occupants and monitor the thermal comfort over time.

Hospital Building Approach: - This proposed hospital building cannot be applied an HVAC system, because it causes to spread the of viruses rapidly. Proposed to the solar system for whole roof area, mac form under layer for roofing sheets and fixing more windows for wards. Those will help to reduce the heat of inside the building.

Point can obtain = 0

Credit 6.8 – Air Purification and Distribution

Intent: - Provide a safer environment for occupants in building during normal operations and pandemics to mitigate the transmission of viruses through the use of mechanical system.

Hospital building Approach: - Due to infectious disease hospital building projects cannot use air conditioning systems, because they cause to spread the of viruses rapidly, and also contaminated patients always should supply fresh air. In this project, there are many windows to supply fresh air to the wards and staff areas.

Points can be obtain = 0

Credit 6.9 – Daylight & Views

Intent: - Provide for the building occupants a connection between indoor spaces and the outdoors through the introduction of daylight and views into the regularly occupied areas of the building.

Hospital Building Approach: -

Credit 6.9.1 – Daylight

The building windows oriented to the north-South directions to get daylight as much and reduce the heat too. Transparent sun control films pasting to the windows for cut glare and reduce heat. Daylight factor calculation given 11%-13%, so that it more than minimum day light factor 5%.

Point can be obtain = 1

Credit 6.9.2 Views

Achieved direct line of sight to outdoor by fixing more windows and pasting sun control films to cut the glare for the comfortable view.

Point can be obtain = 1

7.0 INNOVATION AND DESIGN PROCESS

7.1 Innovation in Design

Intent: - To provide design teams and projects with the opportunity to be awarded points for exceptional performance above the requirements set by the GREENSL Rating System and/or innovative performance in Green Building categories not specifically addressed by the GREENSL Rating System.

Hospital Building Approach: - Due to the hospital building project, it cannot be apply innovative criteria and should work with standards criteria because cannot do experiments with patients' lives in hospital environment.

Point can obtain = 0

8.0 SOCIAL & CULTURAL AWARENESS

Prerequisite 1 – Archeological Sites & Heritage Buildings

Intent: - Protect archeological sites and heritage buildings and discourage building construction that may affect the cultural identity of the site and the heritage value of the building.

Hospital Building Approach: - The elected site location for this project is not designated as an archeological site and there is no any heritage buildings, no need to take any prior approvals from Department of Archeology.

Credit 8.1 – Social Wellbeing, Public Health & Safety

Intent: - Ensure the building developments address of maintaining and improving public health and social wellbeing. The social benefits of sustainable design are related to improvements in the quality of life, health, and well-being. These benefits can be realized at different levels; buildings, the community, and society in general. At a building level, research on the human benefits of sustainable design has centered on three primary topics: health, comfort, and satisfaction.

Hospital Building Approach: - The design of building fully comply with the fire regulations and local authority regulations. All areas of the building are accessible to persons with disabilities

and elderly via appropriately sized doorways low levels. Adequate Fire extinguishers placed properly about the usage of the equipment. Establishing good security force to prevent contaminated patients contact with decontaminated persons. Cultivated native herbal plants garden that can be used for the patient and well landscape garden allocate for the patient and staff members separately as a rest area for their mental relaxation.

Point can obtain = 2

Credit 8.2 – Cultural Identity

Intent: - Make sure the building designs and developments contribute to the cultural identity of the regional, community, locality, or neighborhood settings.

Hospital Building Approach: - The proposed hospital building build in existing IDH hospital situated land, so the surrounded people are well aware about the situation and they are used to managing their day today work safely from long time ago.

Point can be obtain = 2

9. Conclusion and Recommendation

The following table summarized the green points claimed by the apartment building through the project design with accordance to criteria of Green Rating System for New Construction V.2.1, 2022.

Total points to be obtain from the design

Description	Points Available	Points Claimed
1.0 Management	4	4
2.0 Sustainable Sites	25	21
3.0 Water Efficiency	14	4
4.0 Energy and Atmosphere	22	16
5.0 Materials and Resources	14	9
6.0 Indoor Environmental Quality	13	10
7.0 Innovation and Design Process	4	0
8.0 Social and Cultural Awareness	4	4
Total	100	69

According to the expected points (69 points) Gold certificate can be achieved for the proposed Hospital building Kotikawatta, Mulleriyawa from the GBCSL. According to the above details Hospital building can recommended as an eco-friendly, productive and economical building project. Therefore this project will motivate the construction industry to execute projects by adapting green concepts.

Appendixes of New IDH Hospital Building Green Rating for Built Environment Report

COMMISSIONING & BUILDING TUNING PLAN

Proposed IDH Hospital Building Kotikawatta, Mulleriyawa

Project Name	Proposed IDH Hospital Building
Project address	IDH Hospital, Mandawila Rd, Mulleriyawa
Project Description	Infectious Diseases Hospital
Total Project area	4.5 Acre
Client	Ministry of Health
Construction period	6 months

Commissioning team information

No	Name	Responsibility	Contact Information

Items Checked	YES/NO	Comments
Client brief document		
Design brief document		
Construction design drawings, including system schematics		
General specifications		
Mechanical schedules		
Electrical schedules		
Control schedules		
Plumbing schedules		
Construction programme		
As-built drawings		
Safety codes		
O&M manuals		
Health and safety codes and standards		
Commissioning specifications		
Commissioning method statement		
Commissioning programme		
Suppliers technical submittals		
Testing and commissioning certificates		

The systems that will be commissioned in this project are shown in the following tables

Heating, Ventilation and Air conditioning Systems

Element description	YES/NO	Notes and comments
Heat generation plant		
Cooling generation plant		
Refrigeration systems		
High temperature hot water		
Low temperature hot water		
Steam heating systems		
Ventilation systems		
Smoke evacuation systems		
Gas installations		
Other Systems (Specify)		

Electrical and Control Systems

Element description	YES/NO	Notes and comments
High voltage power systems		
Low voltage power systems		
Lighting installations		
Emergency power systems		
Uninterruptible Power Supply (UPS) systems		
Standby generators		
Fire and smoke alarm systems		
Communications system		
Public address/paging systems		
Lightning protection systems		
Information and communication technologies (ICT) installations Building management system		
Renewable power generation		
Other systems (Specify)		

Plumbing Systems

Element description	YES/NO	Notes and comments
Waste water systems		
Sewerage System		
Cold water System		
Sanitary Fittings		
Fixtures		
Hot water systems		
Flush and vent systems		
Other systems (Specify)		

Specialist Systems

Element description	YES/NO	Notes and comments
Lifts		
Escalators		
Fire detection system		
Alarms		
Heat detectors		
Smoke Detectors		
Other (Specify)		
Fire Protection systems		
Fire Extinguishers		
Hose reel systems		
Wet risers		
Fire pumps		
Fire Panel		
Landing Valves		
Breaching Inlets		
Sprinkler installation		
Other (specify)		

The following tables show the commissioning activities that will be undertaken on the construction project. The lead and support responsibility for each activity will be supplied by members of the commissioning team. This activity checklist sheet will be used to ensure all activities are planned against the project programme and project cost plan.

Stage	Activities	Lead role	Support role	Comments
Preparation	Define the design requirement			
	Develop the design brief			
	Appoint commissioning management specialist			
	Form the commissioning team			
	Review of design brief for commissioning requirement			
	Develop the outline budget for commissioning process			
Design	Review and clearly define the responsibilities of commissioning			
	Plan for commissioning meetings to be attended by all members of the commissioning team			
	Provide input to the development of design drawings and specifications to ensure that systems can be commissioned properly including: Schematic drawings Detail design drawings Installation wiring diagrams			
	Determine the equipment and system to be commissioned.			
	Develop commissioning method statements for different equipment and systems.			

Pre-Construction	Ensure that the commissioning information included in tender documentation is clear, complete and fully coordinated			
	Participate in the tender phase meetings to clearly communicate all information relating to the commissioning process			
	Assist with the selection of construction specialists to ensure that commissioning requirements will be met			
Construction	Verify technical submittal and installation drawings for compliance with commissioning requirements			
	Prepare the equipment and systems tracking forms			
	Attend regular commissioning meetings			
	Prepare verification checklists			
	Define, and plan for key commissioning milestone dates			
	Verify the standards of equipment and system installations			
	Log and report construction issues on issue tracking forms			
	Correct construction issues logged in the verification checklists before system start ups			
	Conduct point to point control checks and correct any issues			

Commissioning Of engineering services	Carry out pre-performance tests, including off-site works testing and correct any issues found (CIBSE ACT 12)			
	Carry out water and air balancing			
	Agree on the dates of performance tests			
	Set systems and equipment to work and carry out performance tests			
	Correct any issues found during performance tests			
	Review performance tests results			
Pre-handover	Check O&M document for: Warranties documents As-built documents Control layout prints and schedules Training documents (hard and soft copies) Equipment technical manuals			
	Train O&M staff			
	Set meeting for handover date			
	Submit interim commissioning report (subject to post-seasonal checks)			
Initial Occupation	Carry out a survey logging occupant feedback and help new occupants			
	Fine tune the building systems and controls to satisfy the actual building load			
	Carry out post-seasonal performance tests			

Review post-occupancy, seasonal performance tests results			
Submit final commissioning report			
Sign-off commissioning project			

Building User Guide

Proposed IDH Hospital Building Kotikawatta, Mulleriyawa

Project Name	Proposed IDH Hospital Building
Project address	IDH Hospital, Mandawila Rd, Mulleriyawa
Project Description	Infectious Diseases Hospital
Total Project area	4.5 Acre
Client	Ministry of Health
Construction period	6 months

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 - 3.3 Annual building energy consumption
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8. REPORTING PROVISION
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 - 8.2 Responsible parties

BUILDING USER GUIDE PURPOSE

The efficient and safe operation of a building depends on the interaction of the building's users and occupants. This Building Users' Guide (BUG) provides building occupants and building managers with guidance on how to operate the building in accordance with design intent and efficiently. The BUG also includes details of sustainability initiatives incorporated into the building's design, which when implemented correctly facilitate the identification of further tuning that may be required to optimize the building's environmental performance and continuously improve the building's performance. To help with this ongoing interaction, this bug has been developed as a simple and easy-to-use manual. Errors include:

- ❖ Targets for energy, water and waste reduction;
- ❖ A description of the building services and operational requirements for the efficient and safe use of these systems;
- ❖ Building initiatives to reduce energy and water use;
- ❖ Monitor arrangements for energy, water and indoor environmental quality;
- ❖ Transport facilities including parking provision, cyclist facilities and public transport information;
- ❖ Waste management strategy and provision for tenants and building users.
- ❖ Emergency contact information;
- ❖ Considerations for refurbishment or repair;
- ❖ References and further information.

1. BUILDING USER GUIDE UPDATES AND REVIEW

1.1 General Building Information

Building description
Location map
General floor plan –Ground floor
Site plan
Visitors Information

1.2 Building Environment

Element description	Distribution/attenuation method	Photos
Cooling	Natural/ Mechanical by ceiling mounted fans, windows and split AC machines	
Ventilation	Natural/ Mechanical by ceiling mounted fans, windows and split AC machines	
lighting	Natural day light from windows and openings Artificial lights for night by using LED lamps	

1.3 Lift and Escalators

How to operate lifts and escalators		
Procedure	Description	Photo
Standard operation		
Emergency/stop button.		
In case of fault/failure, call button/intercom		
In case of fire		

1.4 Security System

Security system description	
Links to external organization	
Name and contact details of authorized personal	Telephone number
Normal operating	Times
Entry procedure during normal working hours	Photos
Exit procedure during normal working hours	Photos
Entry procedure outside normal working hours	Photos
Exit procedure outside normal working hours	Photos

2. EMERGENCY INFORMATION

2.1 Provide reference to Health & Safety documents

Health and Safety documents
Health and safety Policy – attached
Emergency Preparedness Plan – attached
Emergency Contact details
Fire Team
Health and safety team

2.2 Fire response and Alarm system

Type of alarm system

2.3 Fire evacuation procedures

Fire emergency procedure
Use of fire equipment
Fire extinguishers - all trained workers

2.4 First aid

Calling for assistance	
Emergency first-aid procedure	Photo
Minor injury/illness first-aid procedure	

3. BUILDING UTILITY AND ENVIRONMENTAL INFORMATION

3.1 Overview of policy and practices

Policies	
Quality Management Policy	
Environmental Management Policy	
Water management Policy	
Waste Management Policy	
Energy Management Policy	
Emission Management Policy	
Health and Safety Policy	
Canteen, refreshments and public amenities	Photos

3.2 Energy and environmental strategy

Energy and environmental policies and protocols	Photos

3.3 Annual building energy consumption

Management monitoring	
Low or zero carbon technology and renewable energy sources	
List of certificates and reports	Location

3.4 Energy conservation

List actions that affect efficiency and conservation

3.5 Mechanical

Ventilation strategy

3.6 Electrical

Lighting and low voltage power strategy	Photos
Lighting - LED - Ceylon Electricity Board - Manual operated	
Water pump - Solar Power	
Uninterruptible power supply (UPS)	
Emergency lighting	
Switch-off policy	
Light Fittings - Switch on - entering (manual)	
Switch off - leaving (manual)	

3.7 Communications

Communication procedures and policies
Computer system connectivity
Hospital network options

4. WATER MANAGEMENT

4.1 Water strategy

Water supply and management strategy		
Drinking - Utility main		
Total Flushing - Tube well water		
Washing - Utility main		
Water metering	Sub-metering	Monitoring
Water saving features		Photos
Internal landscape areas		Photos
External landscape areas		Photos

4.2 Domestic water

Potable water locations	
Water cooler/bottled water locations	Photos
Hot water supplies	Photos

5. MATERIALS AND WASTE MANAGEMENT

5.1 Materials purchasing policy

Material purchasing policy

5.2 Waste management policy

Recycling facilities
Recycling strands
Contact details

6. TRANSPORT FACILITIES

6.1 Transport

Public transport
Alternative transport

6.2 Parking

Parking and cycle racks

7. REFIT AND REARRANGEMENT CONSIDERATIONS

7.1 Re-fit building/building sections

Design load/occupational densities
Design levels/limitations of existing building services
Additional building services
Material and waste management policies

7.2 Re-arrangement/addition of furniture

Furniture and fittings

8. REPORTING PROVISION

8.1 Reporting Procedures

Conditional requirements
General maintenance requirements
Operational maintenance requirements
Emergency requirements

8.2 Responsible Parties

Department	Contact information	
Facilities Manager	Name:	
	Telephone:	
	Email:	
Facilities Maintenance Manager	Name:	
	Telephone:	
	Email:	
Administration Manager	Name:	
	Telephone:	
	Email:	
Health & Safety Officer	Name:	
	Telephone:	
	Email:	
Reception (Help Desk)	Name:	
	Telephone:	
	Email:	

9. TRAINING

9.1 Compulsory training

Site induction	
Specialist training for building services	
Emergency procedures	

Additional training

Additional training

**PROPOSED NEW QUARANTINE HOSPITAL FOR INFECTIOUS DISEASES (IDH) IN
KOTIKAWATTA, MULLERIYAWA, SRI LANKA**

ITEM	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QTY	RATE	AMOUNT
A	<u>PRELIMINARIES</u>				
1	Allow for erection of contractor's office, stores, labour accommodation, work shops and sanitary facilities and arrangement for temporary electricity.	Item	1.00	160,000.00	160,000.00
2	Allow for payments for consumption of water including providing alternate supply if necessary.	Mth	6.00	22,000.00	132,000.00
3	Allow for payments for consumption of electricity including providing alternate supply if necessary.	Mth	6.00	48,000.00	288,000.00
	TOTAL FOR PRELIMINARIES CARRIED TO THE SUMMARY				580,000.00

ITEM	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QTY	RATE	AMOUNT
B	<u>EXCAVATION & EARTH WORK</u>				
1	Excavation for foundation including part return filling and disposal of the surplus, compacted bottom of the trenches in the following	Cube	58.20	4,600.00	267,720.00
2	Dewatering,	Item	1.00	188,000.00	188,000.00
3	site clening, leveling	Item	1.00	188,000.00	188,000.00
4	Excavation for staire foundation	Cube	1.20	4,600.00	5,520.00
5	Excavation for column footings	Cube	183.00	4,600.00	841,800.00
6	Leveling Soil compacting & Pholithene laying under the GB	Item	1.00	3,800.00	3,800.00
	<u>Filling under floors</u>				
7	Earth for filling in(6"-12")thk layers well compacted (with Imported soil)	Cube	336.60	9,300.00	3,130,380.00
	<u>Anti termite Treatment</u>				
	Termite treatment to be carried out by a specialist Contractor Lankem and shall provide 10 years gurantee Chemical type- Byflex				
8	Approved Anti termite treatment in ground floor	Sqr	224.50	4,800.00	1,077,600.00
	TOTAL FOR EXCAVATION AND EARTH WORK CARRIED TO THE SUMMARY				5,702,820.00

ITEM	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QTY	RATE	AMOUNT
C	CONCRETE WORK				
	All in SLS approved type Cement				
	Work up to DPC level				
	Grade 15 Blinding concrete				
	50 mm Thick Lean concrete in the following				
	1 Under column footings	Sqr	26.70	24,300.00	648,810.00
	2 Under stair case foundation	Sqr	3.40	24,300.00	82,620.00
	3 Under Rubble foundation	Sqr	19.40	24,300.00	471,420.00
	4 Grade 20, 3"thk Concrete for Ground Floor	Sqr	224.00	33,400.00	7,481,600.00
	UP TO SUB STRUCTURE				
	Grade 25 reinforced concrete in the following				
	5 Staircase footing and shaft	Cube	0.96	123,000.00	118,080.00
6 Column footings	Cube	26.30	123,000.00	3,234,900.00	
7 Column shaft	Cube	8.70	123,000.00	1,070,100.00	
8 Ground Beams	Cube	61.80	123,000.00	7,601,400.00	
SUPPER STRUCTURE					
From Ground floor level to first level					
Grade 25 reinforced concrete in the following					
9 First floor slab	Cube	74.60	132,840.00	9,909,864.00	
10 Second floor slab	Cube	74.60	143,600.00	10,712,560.00	
Lintels 6"X6" high reinforced with 2 nos 1/2 " dia tor steel rods at top & bottom and 1/4 dia stirrups at 8" centers and necessary formwork in the following					
11 Ground floor	L.ft	970.00	788.00	764,360.00	
12 First floor	L.ft	970.00	860.00	834,200.00	
	TOTAL FOR CONCRETE WORK CARRIED TO THE SUMMARY				42,929,914.00

ITEM	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QTY	RATE	AMOUNT
D	Form work				
	Up to DPC Level				
1	Column Footing	Sqr	16.40	22,300.00	365,720.00
2	Column Shaft	Sqr	12.40	22,300.00	276,520.00
3	Plinth Beam	Sqr	58.20	22,300.00	1,297,860.00
	First Floor Level				
4	First floor slab (Steel decking Board)	Sqr	224.00	24,100.00	5,398,400.00
	Second Floor Level				
5	Second floor slab (Steel decking Board)	Sqr	224.00	26,100.00	5,846,400.00
	TOTAL FOR FORM WORK CARRIED TO THE SUMMARY				13,184,900.00

ITEM	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QTY	RATE	AMOUNT
E	REINFORCEMENT All reinforcement steel in SLS approved type "Lanwa" ,"Melwa" UP TO DPC LEVEL Grade 25 reinforced concrete in the following Work up to DPC level				
1	Staircase footing and shaft	T	0.48	522,000.00	250,560.00
2	Column footings	T	3.10	522,000.00	1,618,200.00
3	Column shaft	T	0.52	522,000.00	271,440.00
4	Plinth Beam	T	1.70	522,000.00	887,400.00
	SUPER STRUCTURE				
5	First floor slab (Mesh)	T	6.80	522,000.00	3,549,600.00
6	Second floor slab (Mesh)	T	6.80	563,760.00	3,833,568.00
	TOTAL FOR REINFORCEMENT WORK CARRIED TO THE SUMMARY				10,410,768.00

ITEM	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QTY	RATE	AMOUNT
E	STRUCTURAL STEEL				
	<u>DPC level to First Floor level</u>				
1	Supply fabricate & installation of 254x254x 73Kg/m H Iron Columns . Rate includes cutting, drilling, welding and necessary connection support.	T	18.1	588,000.00	10,642,800.00
	<u>First Floor level to second Floor level.</u>				
2	Supply fabricate & installation of 254x254x 73Kg/m H Iron Columns . Rate includes cutting, drilling, welding and necessary connection support.	T	18.10	588,000.00	10,642,800.00
	<u>Second Floor level to Roof level</u>				
3	Supply fabricate & installation of 203x203x 60Kg/m H Iron Columns . Rate includes cutting, drilling, welding and necessary connection support.	T	12.90	588,000.00	7,585,200.00
4	Supply fabricate & installation of 457x191- 113 Kg/m, H Iron Beams . Rate includes cutting, drilling, welding and necessary connection support.	T	15.30	588,000.00	8,996,400.00
5	Supply fabricate & installation of 457x191- 81 Kg/m, H Iron Beams . Rate includes cutting, drilling, welding and necessary connection support.	T	24.60	588,000.00	14,464,800.00
6	Supply fabricate & installation of 356x127- 39 Kg/m, H Iron Beams . Rate includes cutting, drilling, welding and necessary connection support.	T	8.10	588,000.00	4,762,800.00
7	Brasing	Item	1.00	3,822,000.00	3,822,000.00
	TOTAL FOR REINFORCEMENT WORK CARRIED TO THE SUMMARY				60,916,800.00

ITEM	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QTY	RATE	AMOUNT
F	<u>MASONRY WORK</u>				
	<u>Rubble work</u>				
1	Random rubble masonry wall in cement and sand mix 1:5	Cube	58.20	56,000.00	3,259,200.00
	<u>Brick Work in Ground floor</u>				
2	6" thick Block in cement and sand 1:5	Sqr	92.40	69,000.00	6,375,600.00
	<u>Brick Work in First floor.</u>				
4	6" thick Block in cement and sand 1:5	Sqr	75.90	69,000.00	5,237,100.00
	<u>Brick Work in Second floor</u>				-
	6" thick Block in cement and sand 1:5	Sqr	75.90	80,600.00	6,117,540.00
	TOTAL FOR MASONRY WORK CARRIED TO THE SUMMARY				20,989,440.00

ITEM	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QTY	RATE	AMOUNT
G	ROOF & ROOF PLUMBING				
	Rate shall include for all shops fabrication work, waiste, including cutting , drilling,bolting, delevering,unloading, hoisting,errecting and fixing in posision,complete with all nails screws , clips and straight and squire				
1	ZNAL roofing sheet laid on Steel frame work according to Engineering Drawings of roof &Ridge cover etc with suspended sheet ceiling .rate include to frame work, covering and apply painting , laying heat insulation sheet etc (Rate shall include for all canofy roofs)	Sqr	170.50	216,000.00	36,828,000.00
	VALANCE BOARD & BARGE BOARD				
2	Supply and fixing of ZNAL Valance board 9" wide , rate shall include all necessary extrass.	L.ft	970.00	760.00	737,200.00
	EVE GUTTER				
3	ZN/AL (Bluescope or Equivalant) 0.47 thk Rain water gutter in approved colour 4" fixed to the sides of valance board with brackets at suitable centers including all necessary gutter fittings.	L.ft	1,130.00	880.46	994,919.80
	DOWN PIPE				
4	ZN/AL(0.47 thk) down pipe in approved colour 4"x 4" fixed to the wall / structure with brackets at suitable centers including all necessary fittings.	L.ft	580.00	880.00	510,400.00
	TOTAL FOR ROOF WORK CARRIED TO THE SUMMARY				39,070,519.80

ITEM	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QTY	RATE	AMOUNT
H	DOORS & WINDOWS				
	Supply and fixing AL door windows with all Ironmongeries, door closer, Door stopper & necessary extras.				
1	D1	Nos.	39.00	73,400.00	2,862,600.00
2	D2	Nos.	52.00	37,200.00	1,934,400.00
3	D3	Nos.	24.00	37,200.00	892,800.00
4	W1	Nos.	12.00	160,000.00	1,920,000.00
5	W2	Nos.	18.00	310,000.00	5,580,000.00
6	W3	Nos.	1.00	178,000.00	178,000.00
7	W4	Nos.	1.00	94,000.00	94,000.00
8	W5	Nos.	79.00	136,000.00	10,744,000.00
9	W6	Nos.	9.00	34,000.00	306,000.00
10	W7	Nos.	4.00	330,000.00	1,320,000.00
11	W8	Nos.	8.00	126,000.00	1,008,000.00
12	W9	Nos.	2.00	46,000.00	92,000.00
13	FL	Nos.	16.00	8,000.00	128,000.00
	TOTAL FOR DOORS & WINDOWS CARRIED TO TENDER SUMMARY				27,059,800.00

ITEM	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QTY	RATE	AMOUNT
I	<u>FLOOR, WALL & CEILING FINISHES</u>				
	<u>Floor Finishes</u>				
	All floor tiles shall be "Rocell " and wall tiles would be "Lanka Wall Tiles " with Floor tiles, 600 x 600 size as approved manufacture, colour , quality and design laid to a pattern including 3/4" thick 1:3 cement sand bedding and pointing to match the colour of tiles in the following	Note			
	Ground Floor				
1	Floor Tile	Sqr	224.00	81,000.00	18,144,000.00
	First Floor				
2	Floor Tile	Sqr	224.00	87,600.00	19,622,400.00
	Second Floor				
3	Floor Tile	Sqr	224.00	94,600.00	21,190,400.00
	<u>Skirting</u>				
	Tile skirting 4" high 3/4" thick in cement and sand 1:3 in Followings				
4	Ground Floor	L.ft	910.00	478.00	434,980.00
5	First Floor	L.ft	932.00	520.00	484,640.00
6.00	Second Floor	L.ft	932.00	565.00	526,580.00
	<u>Wall Finishes</u>				
	<u>Internal Wall Plaster</u>				
	Internal plaster in cement, and sand 1:5(with febmix) to a thickness not less than 5/8" finished satisfaction of the Architect and including forming door and window reveals to the following-				
7	Ground floor	Sqr	91.00	13,600.00	1,237,600.00
8	First Floor	Sqr	73.00	14,688.00	1,072,224.00
9	Second Floor	Sqr	73.00	15,865.00	1,158,145.00

ITEM	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QTY	RATE	AMOUNT
	Gglazed wall tiles, 1" x 1" size in an approved manufacture, colour and design laid on and including 3/4" thick cement and sand 1:3 bedding and pointing with 1/4" tile grout to match the colour of tiles7'-0" high to toilets in the following.				
10	Ground Floor	Sqr	8.40	91,000.00	764,400.00
11	First Floor	Sqr	10.50	98,280.00	1,031,940.00
12	Second Floor	Sqr	10.50	106,140.00	1,114,470.00
	<u>External wall plaster</u>				
	External plaster in cement, and sand 1:5 to a thickness not less than 5/8" thick finished semi rough with wood float to walls in the following				
13	Ground Floor	Sqr	102.00	14,600.00	1,489,200.00
14	First Floor	Sqr	81.50	15,770.00	1,285,255.00
15	second floor	Sqr	81.50	17,100.00	1,393,650.00
16	Plinth plaster in cement, and sand 1:3 to a thickness not less than 5/8" thick finished smooth cemel floating.	Sqr	14.50	16,600.00	240,700.00
	TOTAL FLOOR, WALL & CEILING FINISHES CARRIED TO TENDER SUMMARY				71,190,584.00

ITEM	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QTY	RATE	AMOUNT
J	<u>PAINING WORK</u>				
	<u>Internal wall paint</u>				
	Prepare plastered surfaces (Smooth) of brick walls, apply Two coat of skim coat/ Approved wall putty with spot fill apply filler leveling compound with spot filler and apply two coats of approved interior quality, emulsion paint with one coat of primer as				
1	Ground Floor	Sqr	91.00	11,800.00	1,073,800.00
2	First Floor	Sqr	73.00	12,744.00	930,312.00
3	second floor	Sqr	73.00	13,770.00	1,005,210.00
	<u>External wall paint</u>				
	Application of two coats of weather shield painting with a primer under coat of "Roof coat" or equivalent external water proofing applicat including preparation of surfaces of external walls in followings				
4	Ground Floor	Sqr	102.00	11,000.00	1,122,000.00
5	First Floor	Sqr	81.50	11,880.00	968,220.00
6	second floor	Sqr	81.50	12,830.00	1,045,645.00
	TOTAL FOR PAINTING WORK CARRIED TO TENDER SUMMARY				6,145,187.00

ITEM	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QTY	RATE	AMOUNT	
K	<u>INTERNAL PLUMBING AND SANITARY INSTALLATION</u>					
	<u>Sanitary Fittings and Toilet Accessories</u>					
	Supply & Installation of wash basin and sink pedestal type "White" colour in American standard or equalant with rubber plug and chromium plated chain waste with water supply and waste water connection including angle valves, tap and high quality flexible connection.					
	1	Ground floor	nr	14.00	24,000.00	336,000.00
	2	First floor	nr	16.00	25,920.00	414,720.00
	3	second floor	nr	16.00	28,000.00	448,000.00
	Supply & Installation of WC suite "White" colour with "P" or "S" trap as directed including hinged seat with lid in plastic and low level cistern "White" colour 9.00 Ltr. complete with 12mm dia. angle valve					
	4	Ground floor	nr	9.00	56,000.00	504,000.00
	5	First floor	nr	12.00	60,480.00	725,760.00
	6	second floor	nr	12.00	66,000.00	792,000.00
	Supply & Installation of URINAL suite "White" colour in American standard or equivalent closet with "P" or "S" trap as directed including "White" colour 9.00 Ltr. complete with 12mm dia. angle valve					
7	First floor	nr	6.00	36,000.00	216,000.00	
8	second floor	nr	6.00	38,880.00	233,280.00	
Supply & Installation of Bidet spray with all necessary accessories in approved kind and quality including flexible connection and angle valves complete to working order to the toilets in the following.						
9	Ground floor	nr	9.00	4,600.00	41,400.00	
10	First floor	nr	12.00	4,970.00	59,640.00	
11	second floor	nr	12.00	5,365.00	64,380.00	

ITEM	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QTY	RATE	AMOUNT
	Supply & Installation of Shower rose with shower arm with all necessary accessories in approved kind and quality including flexible connection and angle valves complete to working order to the toilets in the following.				
12	Ground floor	nr	4.00	7,800.00	31,200.00
13	First floor	nr	6.00	8,424.00	50,544.00
14	second floor	nr	6.00	9,100.00	54,600.00
	Toilet Accessories				
	Supply & Installation of Mirror , size 800 x 1100 mm approx over wash basin comprising with silvered float glass mirror with slightly rounded ground edges free from effect of wavy image including 19mm thick hardwood backing, French polished chromium pl				
15	Ground floor	nr	6.00	9,000.00	54,000.00
16	First floor	nr	9.00	9,720.00	87,480.00
17	second floor	nr	9.00	10,400.00	93,600.00
	Supply & Installation of Soap holders fixed to wall with fiber plugs and chromium plated brass screws to the approval of the architect. Labour only				
18	Ground floor	nr	6.00	1,300.00	7,800.00
19	First floor	nr	9.00	1,400.00	12,600.00
20	second floor	nr	9.00	1,520.00	13,680.00
	Supply & Installation of 1/2" dia. High quality chromium plated bib tap and all complete to working order in the following.				
21	Ground floor/First floor /Second floor	nr	16.00	2,200.00	35,200.00
	Towel rails				
22	Ground floor/First floor /Second floor	nr.	24.00	1,800.00	43,200.00

ITEM	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QTY	RATE	AMOUNT
	<p>Water Distribution system</p> <p>Rate for all pipes shall include for pipe supports saddles, clips screws, nails, hardware fixing, joint cutting holes, chasing in brick work, concrete etc. and making good the same in all trades and under ground piping all necessary excavation, backfilling, planking and strutting, concrete bedding and haunching, dewatering and disposal of surplus material as directed. the proposal for pipe fixing method to be submitted for prior approval of the consultant.</p> <p>Rate shall include for all pipe fittings and pipe hanging system</p>				
	Distribution				
23	20mm	Lft	360.00	120.00	43,200.00
24	25mm	Lft	610.00	160.00	97,600.00
25	32mm	Lft	2,230.00	200.00	446,000.00
26	40mm	Lft	280.00	260.00	72,800.00
27	50mm	Lft	430.00	310.00	133,300.00
28	63mm	Lft	30.00	370.00	11,100.00
29	GI 2" pipe	Lft	132.00	420.00	55,440.00
	Valves				
	All control valve and fittings shall be "Pegler" or equalent supply and install gate valve and angle valve.				
30	32 mm Boll valve	nr	24.00	3,600.00	86,400.00
31	32 mm foot valve	nr	3.00	2,400.00	7,200.00
32	25mm Gate valve	nr	24.00	3,100.00	74,400.00
33	Supply and installation of water pump " Jinasena "	nr	3.00	190,000.00	570,000.00
34	Construction of pump location as per the detail drawing	Item	1.00	30,000.00	30,000.00
	Sewer Disposal / waste Disposal				
	Rate for pipes shall include for all pipe fittings such as bends tees, reducers, connectors etc. and inspection openings as necessary for total completion of the work.				

ITEM	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QTY	RATE	AMOUNT
	Sewer & waste pipes				
35	110 mm sewere pipes	Lft	182.00	610.00	111,020.00
36	63 mm Waste pipes	Lft	154.00	370.00	56,980.00
	Manhole waste and sewer				
37	14" X 14" x 18" Brick manhole	nr	24.00	38,000.00	912,000.00
38	16" X 16" x 18" Brick manhole	nr	9.00	44,000.00	396,000.00
39	Intersepter	nr	3.00	49,000.00	147,000.00
40	Allow for the construction of septic tank as per the detail drawiing	nr	1.00	223,000.00	223,000.00
41	Allow for the construction of soakage pit as per the detail drawiing	nr	3.00	116,000.00	348,000.00
	TOTAL FOR PLUMBING WORK CARRIED TO TENDER SUMMARY				8,140,524.00

ITEM	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QTY	RATE	AMOUNT
L	METAL WORK				
	<u>Steel hand rail</u>				
	Steel hand rail for stair case and balcony fixed to concrete floor as per detail drawing and specification. Rate shall include for fabricating and fixing. And painting				
	1 Ground Floor	L.ft	216.00	4,400.00	950,400.00
2 First Floor	L.ft	216.00	4,760.00	1,028,160.00	
4 Steel Staircase	Item	4.00	268,000.00	1,072,000.00	
	TOTAL FOR METAL WORK CARRIED TO TENDER SUMMARY				3,050,560.00

ITEM	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QTY	RATE	AMOUNT
N	ELECTRICAL INSTALLATION All the wiring work done under this contract shall conform to BS 7671: 1992-IEE wiring regulations-16th editions and any other regulations stipulated by the CEB Rate point wiring shall include for all the conduits, conduit fittings, casing ,fixing material switches, wiring and terminations , holder for light fittings and socket outlet for power point ,swithes and socket outlets are Clipsal/ Orange wires in " ACL Cable " This electrical system is wall embeded type Main Switch Board (F&G) 20A/1P/ MCCB- 16A/1P/ MCCB- 16A/1P/ MCCB- 6A/1P/ MCCB - 10A/1P/ MCCB - 1 With powder coated metal encloser 450mmX600mmX150mm	Note Item			
	Point wiring				
2	Industrial socket outlet	Nos	77.00	9,400.00	723,800.00
3	13A socket outlet	Nos	736.00	7,600.00	5,593,600.00
4	Wall & ceiling mounted lamps including light fitting	Nos	4,472.00	6,600.00	29,515,200.00
5	Ceiling fan including fan	Nos	117.00	16,400.00	1,918,800.00
6	Earthing system Below 10 ohm	Item	1.00	360,000.00	360,000.00
	TOTAL FOR ELECTRICAL INSTALLATION CARRIED TO THE SUMMARY				39,599,400.00

ITEM	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QTY	RATE	AMOUNT
O	<u>AIRCONDITION INSTALLATION</u>				
	Rate shall include for all the conduits, conduit fittings, casing ,fixing material wiring and terminations , holder or bracket with necessary extrass				
1	24000 BTU inverter type Air condition complet unit	nr	63.00	765,000.00	48,195,000.00
2	360000 BTU inverter type Air condition complet unit	nr	6.00	975,000.00	5,850,000.00
TOTAL FOR AIRCONDITION INSTALLATION CARRIED TO THE SUMMARY					54,045,000.00
P	<u>FIRE SAFTYUBIT INSTALLATION</u>				
	Rate shall include for all the conduits, conduit fittings, casing ,fixing material wiring and terminations , holder or bracket with necessary extrass. GI Pipes and connections, cabinets and necessary all fixing goods.				
1	Fire Panel Unit	nr	1.00	480,000.00	480,000.00
2	Fire ditector units	nr	257.00	23,000.00	5,911,000.00
3	Fire Alarm system	nr	30.00	216,000.00	6,480,000.00
4	Fire hose reel with wet riser	nr	4.00	468,000.00	1,872,000.00
TOTAL FOR IRE SAFTYUBIT INSTALLATION CARRIED TO THE SUMMARY					14,743,000.00

SUMMARY

ITEM	DESCRIPTION	AMOUNT
A	PRELIMINARIES	580,000.00
B	EARTH WORK	5,702,820.00
C	CONCRETE	42,929,914.00
D	FORMWORK	13,184,900.00
E	REINFORCEMENT	10,410,768.00
E	STRUCTURAL STEEL	60,916,800.00
F	MASONRY WORK	20,989,440.00
G	ROOF AND ROOF PLUMBING	39,070,519.80
H	DOORS & WINDOWS	27,059,800.00
I	FLOOR , WALL & CEILING FINISHES	71,190,584.00
J	PAINTING	6,145,187.00
K	INTERNAL PLUMBING	8,140,524.00
L	METAL WORK	3,050,560.00
N	ELECTRICAL WORK	39,599,400.00
O	AIRCONDITION INSTALLATION	54,045,000.00
P	FIRE SAFTYUBIT INSTALLATION	14,743,000.00
	TOTAL (Excluding VAT)	<u>417,759,216.80</u>